

DUST Theory Manual

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1 Introduction

DUST is a code for three-dimensional unsteady aerodynamic simulations around complex configurations. It is written in `Fortran`, exploiting the Object Oriented paradigms available in the latest standards.

Complex aircraft configurations can be composed of both thick bodies and zero-thickness surfaces. Body surfaces are mainly composed of 2-dimensional panels. Constant-strength surface singularities are used. Sources and doublets are assigned to panels on thick bodies while zero-thickness surfaces are modelled with doublets only. The equivalence between surface doublet and vortex ring is exploited. Other aerodynamic elements, such as lifting lines are implemented. Vortex particle method is used for modelling free wakes, aiming at reliable and efficient simulations of wake-body interactions.

The document is organised as follows. First in section 2 the general mathematical formulation of the problem is provided.

In the following sections more details are provided on the formulation and implementation of different topics of the formulation. In section 3 the details about the potential velocity formulation are provided, while in section 4 are illustrated the ones about the rotational velocity and the wake shedding. In section 5 the full theoretical framework of the employed fast multipole method for particles interaction acceleration is illustrated, as well as its implementation. Finally some details are provided on the loads computations and geometry movement in sections 6 and 9.

2 Mathematical formulation

The mathematical formulation of the aerodynamic solver relies on a vorticity-velocity formulation of the aerodynamic problem, founded on the Helmholtz's decomposition of the velocity field and a Lagrangian description of the vorticity field. The Helmholtz's decomposition of the velocity field states that the velocity field $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r},t)$ can be written as the sum of an irrotational field, the potential velocity, $\mathbf{u}_\phi = \nabla\phi$, and a solenoidal field, the rotational velocity, $\mathbf{u}_\psi = \nabla \times \psi$,

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r},t) = \mathbf{u}_\phi(\mathbf{r},t) + \mathbf{u}_\psi(\mathbf{r},t) . \quad (1)$$

Since the rotational velocity is a solenoidal vector field, the incompressibility constraint reduces to the Laplace equation for the kinetic potential $\phi(\mathbf{r},t)$ in the fluid domain Ω_f ,

$$0 = \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_\phi + \underbrace{\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_\psi}_{\nabla \cdot (\nabla \times \psi) \equiv 0} \rightarrow \Delta\phi = 0 . \quad (2)$$

Since the potential velocity is an irrotational velocity field, the vorticity field $\boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r},t)$ acts as a volume forcing of a Poisson's equation for the vector potential $\boldsymbol{\psi}(\mathbf{r},t)$,

$$\boldsymbol{\omega} = \underbrace{\nabla \times \mathbf{u}_\phi}_{\nabla \times \nabla\phi \equiv 0} + \nabla \times \mathbf{u}_\psi \rightarrow -\Delta\boldsymbol{\psi} = \boldsymbol{\omega} , \quad (3)$$

given the vector identity $\Delta\boldsymbol{\psi} = \nabla(\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\psi}) - \nabla \times \nabla \times \boldsymbol{\psi}$ and the gauge condition $\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\psi} = 0$. The Lagrangian description of the dynamical equation governing the vorticity field $\boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r},t)$ of a incompressible flow reads,

$$\frac{D\boldsymbol{\omega}}{Dt} = (\boldsymbol{\omega} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{u} + \nu\Delta\boldsymbol{\omega} , \quad (4)$$

where ν is the kinematic viscosity of the flow and the material derivative of the vorticity field $D\boldsymbol{\omega}/Dt$ represents the time derivative of the vorticity associated with a material particle. The differential problems defined in the fluid domain Ω_f are manipulated using Green's function method, in order to obtain a volume-grid free formulation of the aerodynamic problem. Eq. (2) is recast as a boundary integral problem, describing the potential velocity field \mathbf{u}_ϕ as the superposition of the free-stream velocity \mathbf{U}_∞ and the fields induced by surface doublet and source distributions with intensity μ and σ respectively, as described in Sec. §2.1. A mixed panel-vortex particle representation of the wake is obtained condensing wake panels in equivalent vortex particles as described in Sec. §2.2 and induce the rotational velocity field \mathbf{u}_ψ , defined as the curl of the vector potential $\boldsymbol{\psi}$ and evaluated with a vortex particle approximation of the free-volume solution of Eq. (3), as detailed in Sec. §2.3. The formulation of the problem naturally fits a time-stepping method described in Sec. §2.4 for time evolution of the aerodynamic field around a model.

2.1 Potential velocity – Body

The potential velocity satisfies a boundary element formulation of the aerodynamic problem, whose solution relies on the superposition principle of surface elementary singularities, associated with three aerodynamic element types: surface panels, vortex rings and

lifting lines. Each element type is defined by its singularity distribution, its boundary condition and load computation. Surface panels provide the aerodynamic elements for modelling the surface S_s of solid thick bodies, with a combination of source and doublets and a boundary condition for the kinetic potential. Vortex lattice elements provide a zero-thickness model for the surface S_v of thin lifting bodies with a distribution of vortex rings and non-penetration boundary conditions for the velocity field. Lifting line elements provide a 1-D line vortex model for thin lifting bodies, with tabulated sectional aerodynamic coefficients naturally including the viscous effects. Lifting line elements are modelled as vortex rings, whose streamwise sides are represented by the trailing vorticity, and vortex-doublet equivalence reduces the solid body modelling to a surface distribution of doublets and sources. Vortex ring elements also provide the model for the surface S_w of the potential part of the wake.

2.1.1 Surface panels (SP)

The potential part of the velocity field is governed by the Laplace equation (2) for the kinetic potential in the fluid domain Ω_φ delimited by potential aerodynamic elements, $\partial\Omega_\varphi = S_b \cup S_w = S_s \cup S_v \cup S_l \cup S_w$. The problem is reformulated using the perturbation kinetic potential $\varphi := \phi - \phi_\infty$ and the perturbation potential velocity $\mathbf{u}_\varphi = \nabla\varphi = \mathbf{u}_\phi - \mathbf{U}_\infty$, leading to the Laplace equation for the perturbation kinetic potential

$$\Delta\varphi = 0 \quad \text{in } \Omega_\varphi, \quad (5)$$

supplemented with the far-field boundary condition,

$$\varphi \rightarrow 0 \quad |\mathbf{r}| \rightarrow \infty, \quad (6)$$

and the Neumann's non-penetration boundary condition, $\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \mathbf{u} = \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_b$, on the surface S_s of solid bodies modelled with surface panel elements, reading

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial\varphi}{\partial n} &= \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \nabla\varphi = \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_\varphi = && \text{on } S_s \\ &= \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot (\mathbf{u}_b - \mathbf{U}_\infty - \mathbf{u}_\psi) =: \sigma(\mathbf{u}_\psi; \mathbf{U}_\infty, \mathbf{u}_b), \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

and introducing the influence of the free-stream condition, the motion of the surface S_s and the rotational part of the velocity field \mathbf{u}_ψ . Using Green's function method (Morino and Kuot, 1974), problem (5-7) is recast as a boundary element problem,

$$\begin{aligned} E(\mathbf{r})\varphi(\mathbf{r}, t) &= + \oint_{\partial\Omega_\varphi} \hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \cdot \nabla_0 G(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}) \varphi(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \\ &- \oint_{S_s} G(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}) \hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \cdot \nabla_0 \varphi(\mathbf{r}_0, t), \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}_0, t)$ is the unit normal vector on the surface $\partial\Omega_\varphi$, pointing outward the solid bodies on S_s , and $G(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}) = 1 / (4\pi|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0|)$ is the Green's function of the Laplace problem in the three-dimensional space and $E(\mathbf{r}_0)$ is the indicator function of the fluid domain Ω ,

$$E(\mathbf{r}_0) = \begin{cases} 0, & \mathbf{r}_0 \in \Omega_\varphi \\ \frac{1}{2}, & \mathbf{r}_0 \in \partial\Omega_\varphi \\ 1, & \mathbf{r}_0 \notin \Omega_\varphi \end{cases}. \quad (9)$$

A detailed derivation of Eq. (8) is provided in Sec. §3.2. The formulation (8) of the problem is interpreted as the superposition principle for the perturbation kinetic potential, identifying the Green's function $G(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r})$ and the term $\hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \cdot \nabla_0 G(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r})$ with the opposite of the kinetic potential induced in \mathbf{r} by a unitary source and a unitary doublet singularity located in \mathbf{r}_0 , respectively. A doublet distribution is associated with the whole boundary $\partial\Omega_\varphi$ of the fluid domain for the potential velocity, while S_v , S_l and S_w have no source contribution because of the normal velocity boundary conditions on zero-thickness surfaces.

The problem is solved by collocation method. The surface of the solid bodies S_b and the potential part of the wake S_w are subdivided into panels. Using a uniform-intensity panel discretisation and defining the intensity of the doublets, $\mu_{i_s} = -\varphi_{i_s}$, and the sources, $\sigma_{i_s} = \hat{\mathbf{n}}_{i_s} \cdot (\mathbf{u}_b - \mathbf{U}_\infty - \mathbf{u}_\psi)_{i_s}$, the discrete counterpart of the problem reads

$$\sum_{k_s=1}^{N_s} A_{i_s k_s} \mu_{k_s} + \sum_{k_v=1}^{N_v} A_{i_s k_v} \mu_{k_v} + \sum_{k_l=1}^{N_l} A_{i_s k_l} \mu_{k_l} + \sum_{k_s=1}^{N_s} B_{i_s k_s} \sigma_{k_s} + \sum_{k_w=1}^{N_w} A_{i_s k_w} \mu_{k_w} = 0, \quad \forall i_s = 1 : N_s, \quad (10)$$

where A_{ik} and B_{ik} represents the induced potential of the k^{th} doublet and source panel at the point \mathbf{r}_i ,

$$\begin{aligned} A_{ik} &= - \int_{S_k} \hat{\mathbf{n}}_{k_s} \cdot \nabla_0 G(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}_i) \\ B_{ik} &= - \int_{S_k} G(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}_i) . \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

except for the self-induction potential AIC of a doublet,

$$A_{i_s i_s} = E(\mathbf{r}_{i_s}) - \int_{S_{i_s}} \hat{\mathbf{n}}_{i_s} \cdot \nabla_0 G(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}_{i_s}) = \frac{1}{2} . \quad (12)$$

At each time step, the intensity σ_{k_s} of the sources is provided by boundary condition (7) as a function of the velocity of the body surface \mathbf{u}_b and the rotational velocity \mathbf{u}_ψ at the collocation points \mathbf{r}_{i_s} , while the intensity μ_{k_w} of the wake doublet elements is known from previous time steps. The boundary element problem (10) for the solid bodies modelled with surface panels is a N_s -equation linear system in the $N = N_s + N_v + N_l$ unknown doublet intensities μ_k , associated with all the surface panels, vortex lattice and lifting line elements. This linear system is under-determined if vortex lattice or lifting line elements are used to build the model, along with surface panels.

2.1.2 Vortex Lattice (VL)

Thin lifting bodies can be modelled as a zero-thickness two-dimensional vortex sheet S_v , where non-penetration boundary condition,

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_\varphi = \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot (\mathbf{u}_b - \mathbf{U}_\infty - \mathbf{u}_\psi) =: \sigma \quad \text{on } S_v, \quad (13)$$

must hold. Vortex lattice method provides the aerodynamic elements for the discrete representation of the mean surface of thin lifting bodies, modelled as a sheet of vortex

rings of intensity Γ_{i_v} , equivalent to a piecewise-uniform surface doublet distribution with the same intensity $\mu_{i_v} = \Gamma_{i_v}$, $i_v = 1 : N_v$. The boundary condition at the collocation point \mathbf{r}_{i_v} reads

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k_s=1}^{N_s} C_{i_v k_s} \mu_{k_s} + \sum_{k_v=1}^{N_v} C_{i_v k_v} \mu_{k_v} + \sum_{k_l=1}^{N_l} C_{i_v k_l} \mu_{k_l} + \\ + \sum_{k_s=1}^{N_s} D_{i_v k_s} \sigma_{k_s} + \sum_{k_w=1}^{N_w} C_{i_v k_w} \mu_{k_w} = \sigma_{i_v}, \quad \forall i_v = 1 : N_v, \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where C_{ik} and D_{ik} represents the induced velocity of the k^{th} doublet and source panel at the point \mathbf{r}_i ,

$$\begin{aligned} C_{ik} &= -\nabla \int_{S_k} \hat{\mathbf{n}}_{k_s} \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{0}} G(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}_i) \\ D_{ik} &= -\nabla \int_{S_k} G(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}_i). \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Given the value of the surface variables σ_k , from the motion of the body and the rotational part of the velocity, and the intensity of the wake doublet elements μ_{k_w} , from previous time steps, the boundary conditions (14) are N_v linear equations in the N unknown doublet intensities μ_k . This linear system is under-determined if surface panels or lifting line elements are used to build the model, along with vortex lattice elements.

2.1.3 Lifting Lines (LL)

A lifting line is a 1-D model of thin slender lifting bodies, whose sectional aerodynamic coefficients are provided as a function of the local angle of attack α , the local Reynolds number Re and the local Mach number M ,

$$\{c_\ell, c_d, c_m\}(\alpha, Re, M; \mathbf{r}). \quad (16)$$

The circulation $\Gamma_l(\mathbf{r}, t)$ of the lifting line is determined as the solution of a nonlinear problem, connecting $\Gamma_l(\mathbf{r}, t)$ with the tabulated aerodynamic coefficients of its lifting sections.

Both a loosely-coupled α -method (Piszkin and Levinsky, 1976) and a Γ -method (Gallay and Laurendeau, 2015) solver are available. The first method consists in the equality between the angle of incidence resulting from the induced velocity field and the angle of attack used to enter tabulated aerodynamic data,

$$\alpha(\mathbf{r}, t) = \text{atan2} \left(\mathbf{u}_{rel}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}, t), \mathbf{u}_{rel}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{t}}(\mathbf{r}, t) \right), \quad (17)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{t}}$ are the normal and streamwise tangent unit vector of the aerodynamic sections of the component and the relative velocity, $\mathbf{u}_{rel} = \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_b$, is a function of the lifting line intensity $\Gamma_l(\mathbf{r}, t)$ through the induced velocity, and thus it is a function of the angle of attack $\alpha(\mathbf{r}, t)$. The latter method consists in the equivalence of the semi-empirical

expression of the sectional lift and its analytical expression from Kutta-Joukowski theorem,

$$\frac{1}{2}\rho |\mathbf{u}_{rel}(\mathbf{r},t)|^2 c(\mathbf{r}) c_\ell(\alpha(\mathbf{r},t); \mathbf{r}) = -\rho |\mathbf{u}_{rel}(\mathbf{r},t)| \Gamma(\mathbf{r},t) , \quad (18)$$

where $c(\mathbf{r})$ and $c_\ell(\alpha; \mathbf{r})$ represent the chord and the lift curve of the aerodynamic sections of the component, and the local angle of attack α and the relative velocity \mathbf{u}_{rel} are functions of the lifting line circulation Γ_l through the induced velocity. A combination of uniform-circulation lifting line elements provide a discrete representation of a lifting line components. Each lifting line element with circulation Γ_{i_l} constitutes a vortex ring along with its trailing vortices and the last line vortex released in the wake aligned with the spanwise direction. This vortex ring of intensity Γ_{i_l} is equivalent to a uniform surface doublet, $\mu_{i_l} = \Gamma_{i_l}$.

Given the intensity of the surface panel, vortex lattice and potential wake singularities, the motion of the body and the rotational velocity, the discrete representation of both the α -method (17) and the Γ -method (18) can be formally formulated as a fixed point problem,

$$\mu_{i_l} = f_{i_l}(\mu_{k_s}, \mu_{k_v}, \mu_{k_l}, \sigma_{k_s}, \mu_{k_w}), \quad i_l = 1 : N_l . \quad (19)$$

2.1.4 Coupled governing equations

The potential contribution of the velocity field is the results of the superposition of the free stream velocity and the induced velocity from doublet and source singularities, modelling the bound vorticity on the surface of the investigated bodies. Given the free stream velocity, the rotational component of the velocity field, the state of the wake and the motion of the solid components of the model, the intensity of the surface doublets are the actual unknowns of the potential problem, obtained combining Eq.s (10), (14) and (19),

$$\begin{cases} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_{ss} & \mathbf{A}_{sv} & \mathbf{A}_{sl} \\ \mathbf{C}_{vs} & \mathbf{C}_{vv} & \mathbf{C}_{vl} \end{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\mu} = - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{B}_{ss} & \mathbf{0}_{sv} \\ \mathbf{D}_{vs} & -\mathbf{I}_{vv} \end{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\sigma} - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_{sw} \\ \mathbf{C}_{vw} \end{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\mu}_w \\ \boldsymbol{\mu}_l = \mathbf{f}_l(\boldsymbol{\mu}; \boldsymbol{\sigma}, \boldsymbol{\mu}_w) , \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

where the vector $\boldsymbol{\mu}_w$ collects the intensity of the wake doublets, the vector $\boldsymbol{\mu} = (\boldsymbol{\mu}_s, \boldsymbol{\mu}_v, \boldsymbol{\mu}_l)$ collects the intensity of the body doublets on surface panel, vortex lattice and lifting line elements, the vector $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = (\boldsymbol{\sigma}_s, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_v)$ contains the unperturbed relative normal velocity at the collocation points of surface panels and vortex lattice elements, $\mathbf{0}_{sv}$ is a $N_s \times N_v$ null matrix, \mathbf{I}_{vv} is the $N_v \times N_v$ identity matrix. Matrices \mathbf{A}_{xy} , \mathbf{B}_{xy} , \mathbf{C}_{xy} and \mathbf{D}_{xy} collect the aerodynamic influence coefficients of the elements of type y on the elements of type x . Matrices \mathbf{A}_{xy} and \mathbf{C}_{xy} ,

$$[\mathbf{A}_{xy}]_{ik} = - \int_{S_{k_y}} \hat{\mathbf{n}}_{k_y} \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{0}} G(\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{0}}, \mathbf{r}_{i_x}) \quad (21)$$

$$[\mathbf{C}_{xy}]_{ik} = - \nabla \int_{S_{k_y}} \hat{\mathbf{n}}_{k_y} \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{0}} G(\mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{0}}, \mathbf{r}_{i_x}) \quad (22)$$

collect the potential and velocity aerodynamic influence coefficients of the k_y^{th} surface doublet on the collocation point of the i_x^{th} . Matrix \mathbf{B}_{ss} ,

$$[\mathbf{B}_{ss}]_{ik} = - \int_{S_{k_s}} G(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}_{i_s}) \quad (23)$$

collects the potential aerodynamic influence coefficients of the k_s^{th} surface panel source on the collocation point of the i_s^{th} surface panel, while matrix \mathbf{D}_{vs} ,

$$[\mathbf{D}_{vs}]_{ik} = - \nabla \int_{S_{k_s}} G(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}_{i_v}) \quad (24)$$

collects the velocity aerodynamic influence coefficients of the k_s^{th} surface panel source on the collocation point of the i_v^{th} vortex lattice element.

The aerodynamic problem (20) can be written in a compact form as,

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{Y}\boldsymbol{\mu} = -\mathbf{Z}\boldsymbol{\sigma} - \mathbf{Y}_w\boldsymbol{\mu}_w \\ \boldsymbol{\mu}_l = \mathbf{f}_l(\boldsymbol{\mu}; \boldsymbol{\sigma}, \boldsymbol{\mu}_w) \end{cases}, \quad (25)$$

having defined the matrices

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Y} &= [\mathbf{Y}_s \ \mathbf{Y}_v \ \mathbf{Y}_l] = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_{ss} & \mathbf{A}_{sv} & \mathbf{A}_{sl} \\ \mathbf{C}_{vs} & \mathbf{C}_{vv} & \mathbf{C}_{vl} \end{bmatrix}, \\ \mathbf{Z} &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{B}_{ss} & \mathbf{0}_{sv} \\ \mathbf{D}_{vs} & -\mathbf{I}_{vv} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{Y}_w = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_{sw} \\ \mathbf{C}_{vw} \end{bmatrix}, \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

collecting the AICs of the body doublets, body boundary conditions and the wake doublets, respectively.

2.2 Wake shedding

Lifting bodies release wakes from their trailing edges. Kutta condition represents the vorticity balance at the trailing edge and determines the intensity of the wake panel shed into the domain. Kutta condition is naturally satisfied by vortex lattice and lifting line description of a lifting surface, while a row of implicit wake panels is introduced at the trailing edge of thick bodies modelled with surface panels, in order to satisfy the potential jump equivalent to the Kutta condition. The intensity $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{wTE}$ of the trailing edge doublets and the intensity $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_w$ of the wake doublets released at the previous time steps are identified in the wake doublet vector, $\boldsymbol{\mu}_w = (\boldsymbol{\mu}_{wTE}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_w)$. Kutta condition relates the intensity of the i_{TE}^{th} element of the first row of the wake panels with the doublet intensity of the surface panels at the trailing edge,

$$\mu_{w, i_{TE}} = \mu_{s^u, i_{TE}} - \mu_{s^l, i_{TE}} \quad , \quad \boldsymbol{\mu}_{wTE} = \mathbf{T}\boldsymbol{\mu}_s \quad (27)$$

where s^u is the SP element with the unit normal approximately aligned with the unit normal vector of the wake surface, s^l is the SP on the opposite side of the trailing edge and the connectivity array \mathbf{T} provides the matrix form of the Kutta condition. The

implicit contribution of the trailing edge doublets in Eq. (25) are separated from the explicit wake terms,

$$\mathbf{Y}_w \boldsymbol{\mu}_w = [\mathbf{Y}_{w_{TE}} \ \mathbf{Y}_{\tilde{w}}] \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{w_{TE}} \\ \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\tilde{w}} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{Y}_{w_{TE}} \mathbf{T} \boldsymbol{\mu}_s + \mathbf{Y}_{\tilde{w}} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\tilde{w}} , \quad (28)$$

so that the boundary value problem for the potential velocity becomes,

$$\begin{cases} \tilde{\mathbf{Y}} \boldsymbol{\mu} = -\mathbf{Z} \boldsymbol{\sigma} - \mathbf{Y}_{\tilde{w}} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\tilde{w}} \\ \boldsymbol{\mu}_l = \mathbf{f}_l(\boldsymbol{\mu}; \boldsymbol{\sigma}, \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\tilde{w}}) , \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

where the matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{Y}}$ collects the AICs contributions of the body singularities along with the trailing edge wake doublets shed by SP elements,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{Y}} = [\tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_s \ \mathbf{Y}_v \ \mathbf{Y}_l] \quad , \quad \tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_s = \mathbf{Y}_s + \mathbf{Y}_{w_{TE}} \mathbf{T} . \quad (30)$$

2.3 Rotational velocity – Vortex particle method

The rotational part of the velocity $\mathbf{u}_\psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is produced by line vortices and vortex particles used to model free vorticity in the domain with a mixed panel-vortex particle model of the wake. The vorticity field $\boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is the curl of the rotational velocity fields and acts as a volume forcing of the Poisson equation (3) for the vector potential $\boldsymbol{\psi}$. Using Green's function method, the vector potential and the rotational velocity can be expressed as a function of the vorticity field as,

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\psi}(\mathbf{r}, t) &= \int_{\Omega_f} G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r}_0, t) , \\ \mathbf{u}_\psi(\mathbf{r}, t) &= \nabla \times \boldsymbol{\psi} = \\ &= \int_{\Omega_f} \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) \times \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r}_0, t) , \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

where $\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) = \nabla G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0)$ is the Biot–Savart kernel.

The vortex particle method (VPM) provides a Lagrangian grid-free approximation of the vorticity field, as the sum of the contribution of vortex particles of intensity $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_p(t)$ and position $\mathbf{r}_p(t)$,

$$\boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \sum_{i_p=1}^{N_p} \boldsymbol{\alpha}_{i_p}(t) \zeta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_{i_p}(t)) , \quad (32)$$

where $\zeta(\mathbf{r})$ is a cut-off function determining the distribution of the vorticity induced by the vortex particles, while the rotational velocity field becomes,

$$\mathbf{u}_\psi(\mathbf{r}, t) = \sum_{i_p=1}^{N_p} \mathbf{K}_\zeta(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_{i_p}(t)) \times \boldsymbol{\alpha}_{i_p}(t) , \quad (33)$$

where $\mathbf{K}_\zeta(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_p)$ is the consistent velocity kernel, determined by the choice of the cut-off function $\zeta(\mathbf{r})$. (Winckelmans, 1989)

The evolution of the vorticity field $\boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r},t)$ is governed by the vorticity equation (4). The vortex particle method provides a Lagrangian discrete approximation of the vorticity field, through the dynamical equations of the position $\mathbf{r}_{i_p}(t)$ and the intensity $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_{i_p}(t)$ of the vortex particles,

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d\mathbf{r}_{i_p}}{dt} = \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r}_{i_p}(t),t) \\ \frac{d\boldsymbol{\alpha}_{i_p}}{dt} = \nabla\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r}_{i_p}(t),t) \cdot \boldsymbol{\alpha}_{i_p} + \nu \text{“}\Delta\boldsymbol{\alpha}_{i_p}\text{”} \end{cases} \quad (34)$$

for all the particles, $i_p=1:N_p$. The first equation describes the convection of the i_p^{th} material vortex particles transported by the local flow velocity, while the latter equation describes the influence of vortex stretching-tilting and vortex diffusion on the intensity of the vortex particle. In Eq. (34), vortex stretching-tilting is formulated with a transpose scheme [Winckelmans \(1989\)](#), while the quotation marks indicate the need for a model of the diffusion term, since the intensity of the i_p^{th} particle $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_{i_p}(t)$ is not a function of space and, thus, its Laplacian is meaningless. The particle strength exchange method (PSE) method is used here, exploiting the approximation of the Laplacian operator with a integral operator, whose discrete counterpart involves the sum of short-range particle interactions. Introducing Helmholtz decomposition of the velocity field in Eq. (34), it is possible to highlight the influence of the potential velocity \mathbf{u}_ϕ on the vorticity field evolution and, consequently, on the rotational part of the velocity field \mathbf{u}_ψ ,

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d\mathbf{r}_{i_p}}{dt} = \mathbf{u}_\phi(\mathbf{r}_{i_p}(t),t) + \mathbf{u}_\psi(\mathbf{r}_{i_p}(t),t) \\ \frac{d\boldsymbol{\alpha}_{i_p}}{dt} = \nabla\mathbf{u}_\phi(\mathbf{r}_{i_p}(t),t) \cdot \boldsymbol{\alpha}_{i_p} + \\ + \nabla\mathbf{u}_\psi(\mathbf{r}_{i_p}(t),t) \cdot \boldsymbol{\alpha}_{i_p} + \nu \text{“}\Delta\boldsymbol{\alpha}_{i_p}\text{”} \end{cases} \quad (35)$$

The computation of particle interactions is accelerated by a Cartesian FMM ([Lindsay and Krasny, 2001](#)), aiming at reducing the computational cost from the $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ cost of the direct computation of the N particle interactions to the $\mathcal{O}(N)$ cost of the FMM evaluation, in the ideal case. An adaptive Octree structure generates a background hierarchical decomposition of the domain into clusters of cells and the interactions between clusters of well separated particles are evaluated with the Cartesian FMM, based on a polynomial representation of the Plummer potential and the consistent Rosenhead kernel, $\mathbf{K}_\zeta(\mathbf{r},\mathbf{r}_{i_p})$.

2.4 Coupled system and time evolution

The governing equations of the mixed potential-rotational model of the flow are obtained coupling the system of equations (29) for the intensity of body singularities, with the Lagrangian evolution of the vortex particles (34), along with the convection of the potential part of the wake and the transformation of wake panels into vortex particles described in Sec. §2.2. Introducing the definition of the variables \mathbf{v}_w and \mathbf{v}_p collecting the variables representing the position and the intensity of the panel and particle wake and the corresponding forcing \mathbf{f}_w and \mathbf{f}_p , the full system of equations can be formally written as,

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{v}_p; \mathbf{U}_\infty, \mathbf{u}_b) \quad (36a)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{Y}}\boldsymbol{\mu} = -\mathbf{Z}\boldsymbol{\sigma} - \mathbf{Y}_{\tilde{w}}\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\tilde{w}} \quad (36b)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_l = \mathbf{f}_l(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\sigma}, \mathbf{v}_p, \mathbf{v}_w; \mathbf{U}_\infty, \mathbf{u}_b) \quad (36c)$$

$$\frac{d\mathbf{v}_w}{dt} = \mathbf{f}_w(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\sigma}, \mathbf{v}_p, \mathbf{v}_w; \mathbf{U}_\infty) \quad (36d)$$

$$\frac{d\mathbf{v}_p}{dt} = \mathbf{f}_p(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\sigma}, \mathbf{v}_p, \mathbf{v}_w; \mathbf{U}_\infty) , \quad (36e)$$

where Eq. (36a) synthetically represents the influence of the rotational velocity, free stream conditions and the motion of the body on the boundary conditions for surface panels (7) and vortex lattice elements (14). Eq. (36b) collects the boundary element problem for the surface panels and vortex lattice elements, Eq. (36c) represents the fixed point problem for the lifting line elements. Eq. (36d) describes the evolution of the potential part of the wake and Eq. (36e) governs the evolution of the vortex particles. These set of nonlinear equations describes the flow evolution as a function of the prescribed free stream velocity and the motion of the solid surfaces of the model.

The very structure of the system (36), replicating the Helmholtz's decomposition of the velocity field, naturally fits an explicit time-stepping algorithm for time integration, alternately solving for the potential part and the rotational part of the velocity field. The boundary conditions for SP and VL elements is computed as a function of the free-stream velocity, the motion of the body and the state of the rotational part of the wake,

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^n = \boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{v}_p^{n-\frac{1}{2}}; \mathbf{U}_\infty^n, \mathbf{u}_b^n) . \quad (37)$$

Given these boundary conditions and the state of the potential part of the wake, the intensity of the SP and VL elements are evaluated as,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_{s,v}\boldsymbol{\mu}_{s,v}^n = -\mathbf{Z}\boldsymbol{\sigma}^n - \mathbf{Y}_{\tilde{w}}\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\tilde{w}}^n - \mathbf{Y}_l\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_l^n , \quad (38)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_{s,v} = [\tilde{\mathbf{Y}}_s \ \mathbf{Y}_v]$ and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{s,v}^n = (\boldsymbol{\mu}_s^n, \boldsymbol{\mu}_v^n)$ collect the doublet AICs and intensities of the SP and VL elements, while $\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_l^n$ is an approximation of the LL intensity, introduced to independently solve the linear part of the potential velocity field and the fixed-point problem for the LL elements,

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_l^n = \mathbf{f}_l\left(\boldsymbol{\mu}_l^n; \boldsymbol{\mu}_{s,v}^n, \mathbf{v}_p^{n-\frac{1}{2}}, \mathbf{v}_w^{n-\frac{1}{2}}; \mathbf{U}_\infty^n, \mathbf{u}_b^n\right) . \quad (39)$$

After the evaluation of the intensity of the body singularities, the advancement in time of the panel wake,

$$\mathbf{v}_w^{n+\frac{1}{2}} = \mathbf{v}_w^{n-\frac{1}{2}} + \Delta t \hat{\mathbf{f}}_w^{n+\frac{1}{2}} , \quad (40)$$

and the evolution of the vortex particles,

$$\mathbf{v}_p^{n+\frac{1}{2}} = \mathbf{v}_p^{n-\frac{1}{2}} + \Delta t \hat{\mathbf{f}}_p^{n+\frac{1}{2}} , \quad (41)$$

follows, where the forcing terms $\hat{\mathbf{f}}_{w,p}^{n+\frac{1}{2}}$ represent the numerical approximation of the time derivatives $\mathbf{f}_{w,p}$ of the variables $\mathbf{v}_{w,p}$, whose expression depends on the time integration scheme and whose value is a function of the variables

$$\left\{ \boldsymbol{\mu}^{n-i}, \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{n-i}, \mathbf{v}_w^{n-\frac{1}{2}-i}, \mathbf{v}_p^{n-\frac{1}{2}-i}; \mathbf{U}_\infty^{n-i}, \mathbf{u}_b^{n-i} \right\}_{i=0:n-1} \quad (42)$$

in a n -step explicit scheme.

3 Potential velocity

The potential part of the velocity field of an incompressible flow satisfies a Poisson's problem for the kinetic potential. The Laplace's equation for the perturbation kinetic potential φ ,

$$\Delta\varphi = 0 , \quad (43)$$

must be supplied with the non-penetration boundary condition on the surfaces of solid bodies, the far-field condition $\varphi \rightarrow 0$ and the state of free wakes, namely their position and intensity. This differential problem in the three-dimensional fluid domain is recast as a boundary element problem using the Green's function method. The contributions appearing in the integral formulation of the problem can be associated with surface distribution of elementary solutions of the Laplace's equation. Given the state of the free wakes, the boundary value problem can be interpreted as the superposition principle for the kinetic potential, resulting in a linear problem in the intensity of these elementary solutions. The problem is solved by collocation. The surface of the solid bodies and free wakes is subdivided into two-dimensional elements to obtain the panel method solving a discrete counterpart of the boundary element problem.

In this chapter, the point elementary solutions of the Laplace's equation are introduced in Sec. §3.1. The details of the continuous and discrete boundary value formulation of the potential aerodynamic problem are provided in Sec. §3.2. Eventually, the mathematical expression of the aerodynamic influence of coefficients of the surface distribution of the elementary solutions is derived in Sec. §3.7.

3.1 Elementary solutions: point singularities

The two elementary solutions presented in this section are associated with two point singularities, point source and point doublet namely. The velocity field produced by these singularities is regular and irrotational in all the points of the domain, except for the location of the singularities themselves.

Point source. The kinetic potential induced in \mathbf{r} by a point source located in \mathbf{r}_0 with unitary intensity is a function of the distance vector $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0$. The kinetic potential induced by a point source with unitary intensity is

$$\varphi^s(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) = \varphi^s(\mathbf{x}) = -\frac{1}{4\pi|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0|} . \quad (44)$$

The induced velocity $\mathbf{u}^s(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) = \mathbf{u}^s(\mathbf{x}) = \nabla\varphi^s(\mathbf{x})$ reads

$$\mathbf{u}^s(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\mathbf{x}}{4\pi|\mathbf{x}|^3} , \quad (45)$$

and the induced velocity gradient reads,

$$\nabla\mathbf{u}^s(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \left\{ \frac{1}{|\mathbf{x}|^3}\mathbb{I} - \frac{3}{|\mathbf{x}|^5}\mathbf{x} \otimes \mathbf{x} \right\} , \quad (46)$$

where \mathbb{I} is the identity tensor.

Point doublet. The kinetic potential induced in \mathbf{r} by a point doublet located in \mathbf{r}_0 with unitary intensity is a function of the distance vector $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0$. The kinetic potential induced by a point doublet with axis $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ and unitary intensity is

$$\varphi^d(\mathbf{x}) = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \mathbf{x}}{|\mathbf{x}|^3}. \quad (47)$$

The induced velocity $\mathbf{u}^d(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) = \mathbf{u}^d(\mathbf{x}) = \nabla \varphi^d(\mathbf{x})$ reads

$$\mathbf{u}^d(\mathbf{x}) = \nabla \varphi^d(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \left\{ -\frac{\hat{\mathbf{n}}}{|\mathbf{x}|^3} + 3 \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \mathbf{x} \frac{\mathbf{x}}{|\mathbf{x}|^5} \right\}. \quad (48)$$

and the induced velocity gradient reads,

$$\nabla \mathbf{u}^d(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \left\{ \frac{3}{|\mathbf{x}|^5} \left(\hat{\mathbf{n}} \otimes \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{x} \otimes \hat{\mathbf{n}} + (\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \mathbf{x}) \mathbb{I} \right) - 15 \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \mathbf{x} \frac{\mathbf{x} \otimes \mathbf{x}}{|\mathbf{x}|^7} \right\}. \quad (49)$$

where \mathbb{I} is the identity tensor.

3.2 Mixed potential-velocity Morino formulation and panel method

A numerical model is built as the assembly of its components, each of which can be modeled with different aerodynamic elements. Three aerodynamic elements are available to represent solid bodies: surface panels (SP), vortex lattice (VL) and lifting line (LL) elements. Each component is associated to its own distribution of singularities, introduce its own boundary conditions in the dynamical system of the aerodynamic problem and has its own methods for computing induced potential, velocity and loads. As it will be clear in the following sections, source and doublet distributions are associated with surface panel (SP) elements, used to model thick solid bodies. A doublet distribution is associated with vortex lattice (VL) and lifting line (LL) elements, used to model thin lifting components, such as high-aspect ratio wing and blades, as zero-thickness surfaces. Following the Morino's formulation of the aerodynamic problem, surface panels introduce Dirichlet boundary conditions for the velocity potential, as described in Sec. §3.3. Vortex lattice elements introduce Neumann boundary conditions for the velocity potential, corresponding to the normal component of the velocity, as described in Sec. §3.4. Lifting lines encompass viscosity contributions by means of tabulated aerodynamic coefficients, as functions of the angle of attack, Reynolds and Mach number of the aerodynamic section. Lifting lines introduce nonlinear equations, equating the Kutta-Joukowski and semi-empirical expressions of the lift of the aerodynamic section. Lifting line elements with their near-field wake are modeled as a vortex ring, equivalent to a surface doublet distribution, as detailed in Sec. §3.5.

3.3 Morino formulation of the aerodynamic problem

Morino's formulation of the aerodynamic problem exploits the Green's function method to recast the differential problem governed by the Laplace's equation for the perturbation kinetic potential, supplied with the appropriate boundary conditions, with a integral boundary problem. Green's function method is introduced in Sec. §3.3.1 and it is applied to the aerodynamic problem to obtain the Morino's formulation of the problem, as detailed in Sec. §3.3.2.

3.3.1 Green's function method applied to Laplace's equation

The Green's function method is applied to the potential aerodynamic problem, in order to recast a differential problem defined in the three-dimensional fluid domain as boundary value problem, involving only the boundary of the potential flow domain Ω_φ . The Green's function method exploit the property of the Dirac's delta,

$$\int_V f(\mathbf{r}_0) \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0) = E(\mathbf{r}) f(\mathbf{r}) , \quad (50)$$

where the integral is performed on the variable \mathbf{r}_0 and $E(\mathbf{r})$ is the indicator function of the domain V ,

$$E(\mathbf{r}) = \begin{cases} 1 & , \quad \mathbf{r} \in V \\ \frac{\Omega}{4\pi} & , \quad \mathbf{r} \in \partial V \\ 0 & , \quad \mathbf{r} \notin \bar{V} \end{cases} \quad (51)$$

where Ω is the solid angle of the domain V , seen from the point \mathbf{r} on its boundary ∂V . As an example, if the boundary of the domain is smooth in \mathbf{r} , the solid angle Ω is equal to 2π , and thus $E(\mathbf{r}) = 1/2$. The Green's function \mathcal{G} of a linear operator \mathcal{L} is defined as its impulse response. The free space Green's function of a linear differential operator is formally defined as,

$$\mathcal{L} \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) = \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0) . \quad (52)$$

where $\delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0)$ is the Dirac's delta function, centered in \mathbf{r}_0 .

Green's function of the Laplace problem. The Green's function of the homogeneous isotropic three-dimensional free-space Laplace's equation satisfies,

$$-\Delta \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) = \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0) \quad (53)$$

In a homogeneous space, the Green's function \mathcal{G} depends only on the vector distance $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0$, $\tilde{\mathcal{G}}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0)$. In a isotropic space, the solution does not depend on the orientation of the space, so that the Green's function only depends on the absolute value r of the vector \mathbf{x} , $G(r) = \tilde{\mathcal{G}}(\mathbf{x})$. Spherical coordinates provide a simple explicit expression of the problem (53) in homogeneous and isotropic space,

$$-\frac{1}{r^2} (r^2 G'(r))' = 0 , \quad \mathbf{x} \neq \mathbf{0} , \quad (54)$$

in all the points, except for the position of the Dirac's delta, identified by $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{0}$. The expression of the Green's function and its gradient is obtained integrating equation (54),

$$G(r) = \frac{A}{r} + Br \quad , \quad \nabla G(r) = -\frac{A}{r^3} \mathbf{x} + B \hat{\mathbf{x}} , \quad (55)$$

and the constants of integrations B and A are respectively determined with the far field condition,

$$\varphi \xrightarrow{r \rightarrow \infty} 0 \quad \rightarrow \quad B = 0 , \quad (56)$$

and the Dirac's delta property,

$$1 = \int_V \delta(r) = - \int_V \Delta G = - \oint_{\partial V} \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \nabla G = \oint_{\partial V} A \frac{\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \mathbf{x}}{r^3} = 4\pi A \quad \rightarrow \quad A = \frac{1}{4\pi}, \quad (57)$$

where V is a domain containing the location of the Dirac's delta and the surface integral is the solid angle equal to 4π of the surface ∂V seen from the location of the Dirac's delta, so that the Green's function of the Laplace's problem reads,

$$G(r) = \frac{1}{4\pi r} = \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) = \frac{1}{4\pi |\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0|}. \quad (58)$$

From a direct comparison of the Green's function (58) and the kinetic potential induced by a point source (44), it is possible to identify the Green's function as the opposite of the kinetic potential induced in \mathbf{r} by a unitary point source located in \mathbf{r}_0 (and viceversa),

$$\varphi^s(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) = -\mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0). \quad (59)$$

The gradient of the Green's function with respect to the first argument \mathbf{r} reads¹

$$\nabla \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0|^3}, \quad (61)$$

and its scalar product with a unit vector $\hat{\mathbf{v}}$ is equal to the kinetic potential (47) induced in \mathbf{r} by the point doublet with axis $\hat{\mathbf{v}}$ located in \mathbf{r}_0 ,

$$\varphi^d(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) = \hat{\mathbf{v}} \cdot \nabla \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0). \quad (62)$$

3.3.2 Morino formulation

In this section, the Green's function method is applied to the potential aerodynamic problem, governed by the Laplace's problem for the perturbation kinetic potential along with the wake evolution. The boundary value formulation of the aerodynamic problem is obtained applying property (50) of the Dirac's to the perturbation kinetic potential φ , along with the divergence theorem,

$$\begin{aligned} E(\mathbf{r})\varphi(\mathbf{r}) &= \int_{\Omega_\varphi} \delta(\mathbf{r}_0 - \mathbf{r}) \varphi(\mathbf{r}_0) = - \int_{\Omega_\varphi} \Delta_0 \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}) \varphi(\mathbf{r}_0) = \\ &= \int_{\Omega_\varphi} \nabla_0 \cdot [-\varphi(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \nabla_0 \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}) + \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}) \nabla_0 \varphi(\mathbf{r}_0, t)] - \int_{\Omega_\varphi} \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}) \Delta_0 \varphi(\mathbf{r}_0, t) = \\ &= - \oint_{\partial\Omega_\varphi} \varphi(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \cdot \nabla_0 \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}) + \oint_{\partial\Omega_\varphi} \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}) \tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \cdot \nabla_0 \varphi(\mathbf{r}_0, t) + \\ &\quad - \int_{\Omega_\varphi} \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}) \Delta_0 \varphi(\mathbf{r}_0, t) = \\ &= - \oint_{\partial\Omega_\varphi} \varphi(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \cdot \nabla_0 \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}) + \oint_{\partial\Omega_\varphi} \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}) \tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \cdot \nabla_0 \varphi(\mathbf{r}_0, t), \end{aligned} \quad (63)$$

¹The gradient of the Green's function with respect to the second argument is the opposite,

$$\nabla \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) = -\nabla_0 \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0). \quad (60)$$

where the differential integral operators act on the variable \mathbf{r}_0 and the unit normal vector $\tilde{\mathbf{n}}$ points outwards the potential flow domain Ω_φ . This unit vector has the opposite direction of the unit normal vector, $\hat{\mathbf{n}} = -\tilde{\mathbf{n}}$, pointing outwards solid bodies. The volume integral containing the Laplacian of the kinetic potential is equal to zero, because the Laplace's equation must be identically satisfied by the perturbation kinetic potential in the whole domain Ω_φ .

The boundary $\partial\Omega_\varphi$ of the potential flow domain is the union of the surfaces of solid bodies and both sides of zero-thickness surfaces involved in vortex lattice, lifting line and free panel wake models,

$$\partial\Omega_\varphi = S_s \cup S_v \cup S_l \cup S_w , \quad (64)$$

where $S_i = S_i^+ \cup S_i^-$, for $i \in \{v, l, w\}$.

The first contributions in the right-hand-side of equation (63) from the two sides of one of these surfaces become

$$\begin{aligned} & - \int_{S_i} \varphi(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \cdot \nabla_0 \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}) = \\ & = - \int_{S_i^+} \varphi^+(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \tilde{\mathbf{n}}^+(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \cdot \nabla_0 \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}) - \int_{S_i^-} \varphi^-(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \tilde{\mathbf{n}}^-(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \cdot \nabla_0 \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}) \\ & = - \int_{S_i^+} (\varphi^+(\mathbf{r}_0, t) - \varphi^-(\mathbf{r}_0, t)) \tilde{\mathbf{n}}^+(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \cdot \nabla_0 \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}) \\ & = - \int_{S_i} \varphi(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \tilde{\mathbf{n}}^+(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \cdot \nabla_0 \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}) , \end{aligned} \quad (65)$$

being the Green's function continuous across the jump and the unit normal vectors pointing in opposite directions on the two sides of the surface S_i . With an abuse of notation, the positive side S_i^+ of the surface S_i has been identified with the one-sided surface S_i , and the potential jump across this surfaces has been defined as $\varphi(\mathbf{r}_0, t) = \varphi^+(\mathbf{r}_0, t) - \varphi^-(\mathbf{r}_0, t)$.

The integral mass balance implies the continuity of the normal velocity across zero-thickness surfaces,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}^+ \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}^+ + \mathbf{u}^- \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}^- &= 0 \\ \rightarrow \tilde{\mathbf{n}}^+(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \cdot \nabla_0 \varphi^+(\mathbf{r}_0, t) + \tilde{\mathbf{n}}^-(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \cdot \nabla_0 \varphi^-(\mathbf{r}_0, t) &= 0 , \end{aligned} \quad (66)$$

so that the second contributions in the right-hand-side of equation (63) from the two sides of one of these surfaces are equal to zero,

$$\begin{aligned} & - \int_{S_i} \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}) \tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \cdot \nabla_0 \varphi(\mathbf{r}_0, t) = \\ & = - \int_{S_i^+} \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}) \tilde{\mathbf{n}}^+(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \cdot \nabla_0 \varphi^+(\mathbf{r}_0, t) - \int_{S_i^-} \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}) \tilde{\mathbf{n}}^-(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \cdot \nabla_0 \varphi^-(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \\ & = - \int_{S_i^+} \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}) (\tilde{\mathbf{n}}^+(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \cdot \nabla_0 \varphi^+(\mathbf{r}_0, t) + \tilde{\mathbf{n}}^-(\mathbf{r}_0, t) \cdot \nabla_0 \varphi^-(\mathbf{r}_0, t)) = 0 , \end{aligned} \quad (67)$$

having confused the negative side with the positive side of the surface as the domain of integration, having exploited the continuity of the Green's function across the jump and the integral mass balance (66) across the surface.

Using relations (65) and (67), the Morino formulation of the potential aerodynamic problem (63) is manipulated to obtain equation (8),

$$E(\mathbf{r})\varphi(\mathbf{r},t) = \oint_{\partial\Omega_\varphi} \hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}_0,t) \cdot \nabla_0 \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}_0,\mathbf{r}) \varphi(\mathbf{r}_0,t) - \int_{S_s} \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}_0,\mathbf{r}) \hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}_0,t) \cdot \nabla_0 \varphi(\mathbf{r}_0,t) = \quad (68)$$

having introduced the unit normal $\hat{\mathbf{n}} = -\tilde{\mathbf{n}}$, pointing outwards the surface of solid bodies. Identifying the surface contributions in (68) with the kinetic potential induced by a surface distribution of doublets with intensity $\mu(\mathbf{r}_0,t) = -\varphi(\mathbf{r}_0,t)$ on the whole $\partial\Omega_\varphi$ and sources with intensity $\sigma(\mathbf{r}_0,t) = \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \nabla_0 \varphi(\mathbf{r}_0,t)$ on S_s only, this equation can be interpreted as the superposition principle for the perturbation kinetic potential. Given the non-penetration boundary conditions on S_s ,

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot (\mathbf{u}_b - \mathbf{U}_\infty - \mathbf{u}_\psi)(\mathbf{r}_0,t) = \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_\varphi(\mathbf{r}_0,t) = \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \nabla_0 \varphi(\mathbf{r}_0,t) =: \sigma(\mathbf{r}_0,t) , \quad (69)$$

and the intensity of the doublet distribution on $S_v \cup S_l \cup S_w$, equation (68) reduces to the linear integral problem determining the intensity of the perturbation kinetic potential φ on the surface S_s of thick bodies modelled with surface panel elements,

$$E(\mathbf{r})\varphi(\mathbf{r},t) + \int_{S_s} \varphi^d(\mathbf{r},\mathbf{r}_0) \varphi(\mathbf{r}_0,t) = - \int_{\partial\Omega_\varphi \setminus S_s} \varphi^d(\mathbf{r},\mathbf{r}_0) \varphi(\mathbf{r}_0,t) + \int_{S_s} \varphi^s(\mathbf{r},\mathbf{r}_0) \sigma(\mathbf{r}_0,t) , \quad (70)$$

having defined the source and doublet kinetic potential kernels

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi^s(\mathbf{r},\mathbf{r}_0) &= -\mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r},\mathbf{r}_0) = -\mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}_0,\mathbf{r}) = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0|} \\ \varphi^d(\mathbf{r},\mathbf{r}_0) &= -\hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}_0,t) \cdot \nabla_0 \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}_0,\mathbf{r}) = -\hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}_0,t) \cdot \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0|^3} \end{aligned} \quad (71)$$

as the kinetic potential aerodynamic influence coefficients of a point elementary solution located in \mathbf{r}_0 inducing in the point \mathbf{r} .

3.4 Vortex lattice elements

While the distribution of singularities used to describe the surface panels comes from the solution of the Laplace equation for the potential velocity using the Morino formulation, for vortex lattice flat elements a distribution of singularities which already satisfy the laplace equation in the volume and the boundary conditions at infinity are postulated, and additional conditions are imposed to obtain the intensity of the singularity distribution.

The panels are described using a uniform distribution of doublets, and the non penetration condition is enforced on each panel centre

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot (\mathbf{U}_\infty + \mathbf{u}_\varphi + \mathbf{u}_\psi - \mathbf{u}_b)|_{\mathbf{c}_i} = 0 , \quad (72)$$

for every panel centre \mathbf{c}_i .

3.5 Lifting line elements

Lifting lines elements should comprise a single vortex line representing the circulation introduced by a lifting surface, whose intensity is obtained from the tabulated aerodynamic data of the airfoil section they should represent.

In DUST they are modelled as a single row of vortex lattice panels with uniform doublet distribution. Thanks to the equivalence between doublet surface distribution and vortex ring (see section 7.1.2) the panels describe both the lifting vortex with the leading edge side, and the beginning of the wake with the remaining sides.

While the panels used to model the lifting lines are equal to the ones of the vortex lattice components in terms of singularity distribution and hence in the computation of potential, velocity and gradient induction, there are no condition imposed on the panels, and their intensity is computed with iterative fixed point iterations to solve the nonlinear problem generated by the introduction of the tabulated aerodynamic data.

3.6 Updated formulation of Lifting line

Nomenclature:

- i : current panel
- j : panel
- k : time step
- N : number of strips
- M : number of performed time steps
- α : angle of attack
- $d\mathbf{l}$: vector along the aerodynamic center
- \hat{n} : normal to panel
- \hat{t} : tangent to panel in chordwise direction
- Γ_i : circulation of the i -th panel
- \mathbf{w}_{ikj} velocity induced by the vortex ring j at time step k on vortex ring i

Let consider the unsteady Kutta-Joukovsky theorem:

$$d\mathbf{F} = \rho\Gamma(\mathbf{V} \times d\mathbf{l}) + \rho c \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial t} + \rho c \Gamma \frac{d\hat{n}}{dt} \quad (73)$$

The calculated force must be equal to the one that calculated for the strip:

$$d\mathbf{F} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{V}^2 dAC_l\right)^2 + \left(\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{V}^2 dAC_d\right)^2} \quad (74)$$

We can calculate the aerodynamic coefficients from .c81 tables, interpolating the angle of attack. This one (α_i) is calculated as follows:

$$\alpha_i = \arctan\left(\frac{\mathbf{V}_i \cdot \hat{n}_i}{\mathbf{V}_i \cdot \hat{t}_i}\right) \quad (75)$$

where \mathbf{V}_i is total velocity acting on the center of the lifting line:

$$\mathbf{V}_i = -(U_\infty + U_{body}) + \sum_{j=1}^N \Gamma_j^n \mathbf{w}_{ij} + \sum_{k=2}^M \sum_{j=1}^N \Gamma_j^{n-k+1} \mathbf{w}_{ikj} \quad (76)$$

3.6.1 Residual assembly

for $i = 1:N$

$$R_i(\Gamma^n) = (E_i(\Gamma^n) + \frac{G_i}{\Delta t})\Gamma_i^n - \frac{c_i}{\Delta t}\Gamma_i^{n-1} - F_i(\Gamma^n) = 0 \quad (77)$$

The Jacobian is:

$$\frac{\partial R_i}{\partial \Gamma_j} \Big|_{\Gamma^k} = \left(E_i(\Gamma^k) + \frac{G_i}{\Delta t} \right) + \frac{\partial E_i}{\partial \Gamma_j} \Big|_{\Gamma^k} \Gamma_i^k - \frac{\partial F_i}{\partial \Gamma_j} \Big|_{\Gamma^k} = 0 \quad (78)$$

FIXME where

$$E_i = \sqrt{\left(C_i + \sum_{j=1}^N \Gamma_j^n (\mathbf{w}_{ij} \times \mathbf{d}_i) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i \right)^2 + \left(D_i + \sum_{j=1}^N \Gamma_j^n (\mathbf{w}_{ij} \times \mathbf{d}_i) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{t}}_i \right)^2} \quad (79)$$

$$C_i = \left\{ \left[-(\mathbf{U}_\infty + U_{body}) + \sum_{k=2}^M \sum_{j=1}^N \Gamma_j^{n-k+1} \mathbf{w}_{ikj} \right] \times \mathbf{d}_i \right\} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i \quad (80)$$

$$D_i = \left\{ \left[-(\mathbf{U}_\infty + U_{body}) + \sum_{k=2}^M \sum_{j=1}^N \Gamma_j^{n-k+1} \mathbf{w}_{ikj} \right] \times \mathbf{d}_i \right\} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{t}}_i \quad (81)$$

$$\frac{\partial E_i}{\partial \Gamma_j^n} = \frac{\left(C_i + \sum_{j=1}^N \Gamma_j^n (\mathbf{w}_{ij} \times \mathbf{d}_i) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i \right) (\mathbf{w}_{ij} \times \mathbf{d}_i) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i + \left(D_i + \sum_{j=1}^N \Gamma_j^n (\mathbf{w}_{ij} \times \mathbf{d}_i) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{t}}_i \right) (\mathbf{w}_{ij} \times \mathbf{d}_i) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{t}}_i}{\sqrt{\left(C_i + \sum_{j=1}^N \Gamma_j^n (\mathbf{w}_{ij} \times \mathbf{d}_i) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i \right)^2 + \left(D_i + \sum_{j=1}^N \Gamma_j^n (\mathbf{w}_{ij} \times \mathbf{d}_i) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{t}}_i \right)^2}} \quad (82)$$

$$F_i(\Gamma^n) = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(A_i + \sum_{j=1}^N \Gamma_j^n \mathbf{w}_{ij} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i \right)^2 + \left(B_i + \sum_{j=1}^N \Gamma_j^n \mathbf{w}_{ij} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{t}}_i \right)^2 \right] dA_i \sqrt{C_{l_i}^2 + C_{d_i}^2} \quad (83)$$

$$A_i = \left[-(\mathbf{U}_\infty + U_{body}) + \sum_{k=2}^M \sum_{j=1}^N \Gamma_j^{n-k+1} \mathbf{w}_{ikj} \right] \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i \quad (84)$$

$$B_i = \left[-(\mathbf{U}_\infty + U_{body}) + \sum_{k=2}^M \sum_{j=1}^N \Gamma_j^{n-k+1} \mathbf{w}_{ikj} \right] \cdot \hat{\mathbf{t}}_i \quad (85)$$

$$\frac{\partial F_i}{\partial \Gamma_j^n} = \left[\left(A_i + \sum_{j=1}^N \Gamma_j^n \mathbf{w}_{ij} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i \right) \cdot (\mathbf{w}_{ij} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i) + \left(B_i + \sum_{j=1}^N \Gamma_j^n \mathbf{w}_{ij} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{t}}_i \right) \cdot (\mathbf{w}_{ij} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{t}}_i) \right] dA_i \sqrt{C_{l_i}^2 + C_{d_i}^2} \quad (86)$$

For the solution we employ the Newton method:

$$\Gamma^0 = \Gamma^{n-1} \quad (87)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial R_i}{\partial \Gamma_j} \right] \Big|_{\Gamma^k} \Delta \Gamma = -[R_i(\Gamma^k)] \quad (88)$$

$$\Gamma^{k+1} = \Gamma^k + \Delta \Gamma \quad (89)$$

Evaluation of force and moments:

$$\mathbf{F}^n = \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\rho \Gamma_i^n \mathbf{V}_i \times \mathbf{dl}_i + \rho c_i \frac{\Gamma_i - \Gamma_i^{n-1}}{\Delta t} \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i + \rho c_i \Gamma_i^n \frac{d\hat{\mathbf{n}}_i}{dt} \right) \quad (90)$$

$$\mathbf{M}^n = \sum_{i=1}^N \left[\mathbf{r}_i \times \left(\rho \Gamma_i^n \mathbf{V}_i \times \mathbf{dl}_i + \rho c_i \frac{\Gamma_i - \Gamma_i^{n-1}}{\Delta t} \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i + \rho c_i \Gamma_i^n \frac{d\hat{\mathbf{n}}_i}{dt} \right) - \frac{1}{2} \rho |\mathbf{V}_i|^2 dA_i c_i C_{m_i} (\mathbf{c}_i \times \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i) \right] \quad (91)$$

As initial guess we can make the following approximation:

$$\mathbf{V}_i \times \mathbf{dl}_i = -(U_\infty + U_{body}) \times \mathbf{dl}_i \quad (92)$$

$$\mathbf{V}_i \times \hat{\mathbf{t}}_i \approx -(U_\infty + U_{body}) \times \mathbf{dl}_i \quad (93)$$

$$(\mathbf{V}_i \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i)^2 + (\mathbf{V}_i \cdot \hat{\mathbf{t}}_i)^2 \approx V_0^2 \quad (94)$$

$$\alpha_i = \arctan \left(\frac{\mathbf{V}_i \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i}{\mathbf{V}_i \cdot \hat{\mathbf{t}}_i} \right) \approx \frac{\mathbf{V}_i \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i}{(U_\infty + U_{body})} \quad (95)$$

$$C_{l_{\alpha_i}} = \frac{C_{l_i} - C_{l_0}}{\alpha_i - \alpha_{0_i}} \quad (96)$$

3.6.2 Implementation: initial guess

At time $t = 0$ we solve the linear system:

$$\Gamma_i^0 \sqrt{[[-(\mathbf{U}_\infty + \mathbf{U}_{body}) \times \mathbf{dl}_i] \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i]^2 + [[-(\mathbf{U}_\infty + \mathbf{U}_{body}) \times \mathbf{dl}_i] \cdot \hat{\mathbf{t}}_i]^2} \quad (97)$$

$$- \frac{1}{2} (U_\infty + U_{body})^2 dA_i C_{l_{\alpha_i}} \sum_{j=1}^N \Gamma_j^0 \mathbf{w}_{ij} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i = \quad (98)$$

$$\sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{2} \rho (U_\infty + U_{body})^2 dA_i C_{l_i} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{1}{2} \rho (U_\infty + U_{body})^2 dA_i C_{d_i} \right)^2} \quad (99)$$

3.7 Aerodynamic influence coefficients

3.7.1 Line vortices

Induced velocity. The velocity induced in \mathbf{r}_i by the vortex-ring ℓ , whose intensity is Γ , is computed by means of Biot-Savart law,

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r}_i) = -\frac{\Gamma}{4\pi} \oint_{\ell} \frac{\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}}{|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}|^3} \times \hat{\mathbf{t}}. \quad (100)$$

For vortex ring, whose sides are straight lines, a simple analytical expression of the previous integral can be found. After dividing the vortex ring ℓ in segments ℓ_k , the induced velocity reads

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r}_i) = -\frac{\Gamma}{4\pi} \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{\ell_k} \frac{\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}}{|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}|^3} \times \hat{\mathbf{t}}_k = \frac{\Gamma}{4\pi} \mathbf{I}_k, \quad (101)$$

having introduced the definition of \mathbf{I}_k as the velocity induced by the k -th side with intensity -4π . It is possible to prove that \mathbf{I}_k can be computed as

$$\mathbf{I}_k = \frac{\mathbf{R}_k \times \mathbf{R}_{k+1}(R_k + R_{k+1})}{R_k R_{k+1}(R_k R_{k+1} + \mathbf{R}_k \cdot \mathbf{R}_{k+1})}, \quad (102)$$

being $\mathbf{R}_k = \mathbf{r} - \mathbf{P}_k$ the vector “connecting” the k -th vertex of the element with the passive point \mathbf{r}_i .

Induced velocity gradient. The velocity gradient is directly computed in the base coordinate system. Direct differentiation of (323) reads

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{I}}{\partial x_i} = & \frac{1}{AB(AB + \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b})} \left\{ \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}}{\partial x_i} \times \mathbf{b}(A + B) + \mathbf{a} \times \frac{\partial \mathbf{b}}{\partial x_i}(A + B) + \mathbf{a} \times \mathbf{b} \left(\frac{\partial A}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial B}{\partial x_i} \right) \right\} + \\ & - \frac{\mathbf{a} \times \mathbf{b}(A + B)}{B[AB + \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b}]^2} \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial A}{\partial x_i} B + A \frac{\partial B}{\partial x_i} \right) (AB + \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b}) + AB \left(\frac{\partial A}{\partial x_i} B + A \frac{\partial B}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}}{\partial x_i} \cdot \mathbf{b} + \mathbf{a} \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{b}}{\partial x_i} \right) \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (103)$$

having defined $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{R}_k$, $\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{R}_{k+1}$, $A = |\mathbf{a}|$, $B = |\mathbf{b}|$. The derivatives in eq.(323) are easily obtained as

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{a}}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{b}}{\partial x_i} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i, \quad \frac{\partial A}{\partial x_i} = \frac{x_i}{A}, \quad \frac{\partial B}{\partial x_i} = \frac{x_i}{B}. \quad (104)$$

3.7.2 Surface doublets

Equivalence doublet surface-vortex ring. Following [Katz and Plotkin \(2001\)](#) (p.250, §10.4.3) a constant-strength flat panel with intensity μ is equivalent to a vortex ring on the boundary of the panel with intensity $\Gamma = \mu$.

Kinetic potential, D The potential induced in \mathbf{r}_i (passive point) by the unit-strength intensity surface doublet S_k (active surface) is

$$D_{ik} = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{S_k} \frac{\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot (\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r})}{|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}|^3}. \quad (105)$$

Following [Newman \(1986\)](#), $\Phi = -4\pi D_{ik}$ is recognised to be the solid angle of the panel S_k , as seen from the passive point \mathbf{r}_i . From the Gauss-Bonnet theorem, the solid angle Φ is equal to

$$\Phi = \sum_{\ell=1}^{N_e} \beta_\ell - (N_e - 2)\pi, \quad (106)$$

i.e. the sum of the angles β_ℓ of the projection of the N_e edges of the element on the unit sphere, centered in \mathbf{r}_i .

For each element Φ can be computed with a loop over the vertices of a element, as follows

- the unit vector aligned with the vector from the passive point P_0 to the vertex of the element is computed: $\mathbf{e}_i = (\mathbf{P}_i - \mathbf{P}_0)/|\mathbf{P}_i - \mathbf{P}_0|$

- normal projection of the edges $\boldsymbol{\ell}_i = P_{i+1} - P_i$, $\boldsymbol{\ell}_{i-1} = P_i - P_{i-1}$ w.r.t. \mathbf{e}_i is computed

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{a}_i = \boldsymbol{\ell}_i - \boldsymbol{\ell}_i \cdot \hat{\mathbf{e}}_i \hat{\mathbf{e}}_i \\ \mathbf{a}_{i-1} = -(\boldsymbol{\ell}_{i-1} - \boldsymbol{\ell}_{i-1} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{e}}_i \hat{\mathbf{e}}_i) \end{cases} \quad (107)$$

- the desired angle β_i , is the angle included between \mathbf{a}_i and \mathbf{a}_{i-1}

$$\begin{cases} \sin \beta_i = \frac{\mathbf{a}_i \times \mathbf{a}_{i-1} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{e}}_i}{|\mathbf{a}_i| |\mathbf{a}_{i-1}|} \\ \cos \beta_i = \frac{\mathbf{a}_i \cdot \mathbf{a}_{i-1}}{|\mathbf{a}_i| |\mathbf{a}_{i-1}|} \end{cases} \quad (108)$$

and can be computed with `atan2` function, providing only the numerators of the ratios appearing in $\sin \beta_i$ and $\cos \beta_i$.

Velocity, U . The induced velocity of a constant-strength doublet surface distribution is computed exploiting the doublet-vortex ring equivalence and the Biot-Savart law, see Sec. §3.7.1.

Velocity gradient. The velocity gradient induced by a constant-strength doublet surface distribution is obtained exploiting the results for the vortex line, see Sec. §3.7.1.

3.7.3 Surface sources

Kinetic potential, S . The potential induced in \mathbf{r}_i (passive point) by the unit-strength intensity surface source S_k (active surface) is

$$S_{ik} = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{S_k} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}|} . \quad (109)$$

The computation of the velocity potential of a constant-strength source surface distribution exploits the expression of the Φ term appeared in the computation of the doublet potential, see Sec. §8.2.1. Following Newman (1986), the integral $\Psi = -4\pi S$ is defined as the potential of a surface doublet of intensity -4π . It is possible to show

$$\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \zeta} = -\Phi \quad \text{and thus} \quad \Psi = -\int_{\zeta}^{\infty} \zeta' d\Phi - \zeta \Phi . \quad (110)$$

Proof. If $\Psi(\mathbf{r}_0)$ represents the potential induced in \mathbf{r}_0 by the surface source S ,

$$\Psi(\mathbf{r}_0) = \Psi(\xi_0, \eta_0, \zeta_0) = \int_S \frac{1}{|\mathbf{r}_0 - \mathbf{r}|} , \quad (111)$$

its derivative w.r.t. the ζ coordinate of the passive point reads

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \zeta}(\xi_0, \eta_0, \zeta_0) &= -\int_S \frac{\zeta_0}{((\xi_0 - \xi)^2 + (\eta_0 - \eta)^2 + \zeta_0^2)^{3/2}} = \\ &= -\int_S \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{r}_0 - \mathbf{r}}{|\mathbf{r}_0 - \mathbf{r}|^3} , \end{aligned} \quad (112)$$

being ζ the coordinate along the direction normal to the flat element, living in the plane $\zeta = 0$.

Exploiting the integration by part in the integration of the first equation of eqs.(298),

$$\underbrace{\Psi(\xi, \eta, \zeta_\infty)}_{=0} - \Psi(\xi, \eta, \zeta) = \int_\zeta^\infty \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \zeta} = - \int_\zeta^\infty \Phi d\zeta = (I \times P) = - [\zeta \Phi] \Big|_\zeta^\infty + \int_\zeta^\infty \zeta d\Phi . \quad (113)$$

Exploiting $\zeta \Phi \rightarrow 0$ as $\zeta \rightarrow \infty$, the desired second equation in (298) is obtained. \square

Following Newman (1986), the term Ψ for a flat N-edge panel becomes

$$\Psi(\xi, \eta, \zeta) = -\zeta \Phi(\xi, \eta, \zeta) + \sum_{k=1}^N v_k Q_k , \quad (114)$$

where v_k is the distance of the projection Q_0 of P_0 on the panel from the edge $P_k P_{k+1}$ and

$$Q_k = \ln \frac{R_k + R_{k+1} + s_k}{R_k + R_{k+1} - s_k} . \quad (115)$$

Velocity, V . The velocity induced in \mathbf{r}_i (passive point) by the unit-strength intensity surface source S_k (active surface) is

$$\mathbf{u}^d(\mathbf{r}_i) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{S_k} \frac{\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}}{|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}|^3} . \quad (116)$$

This integral is computed exploiting the local orthogonal reference frame of the element $(\hat{\xi}, \hat{\eta}, \hat{\zeta})$

$$4\pi \mathbf{u}^d(\mathbf{r}_i) = \int_{S_k} \frac{\xi}{\rho^3} \hat{\xi} + \int_{S_k} \frac{\eta}{\rho^3} \hat{\eta} + \int_{S_k} \frac{\zeta}{\rho^3} \hat{\zeta} , \quad (117)$$

where $\rho^2 = |\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}|^2 = \xi^2 + \eta^2 + \zeta^2$ is the distance between the active point on the panel surface \mathbf{r} and the passive point \mathbf{r}_i . Given the local orthogonal reference system, see Sec.§. . . , the relative coordinates read

$$\xi = (\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}) \cdot \hat{\xi} \quad , \quad \eta = (\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}) \cdot \hat{\eta} \quad , \quad \zeta = (\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}) \cdot \hat{\zeta} . \quad (118)$$

Since the unit vector $\hat{\zeta}$ coincides with the unit normal vector $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$, the coordinate ζ in the third integral is constant and this integral is equal to Φ , computed in Sec.§8.2.1. Following Newman (1986), the first two integrals are computed exploiting Green's lemma: surface integrals are transformed in a contour integrals

$$I_\xi = \int_S \frac{\xi}{\rho^3} = - \int_S \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} \frac{1}{\rho} = \oint_{\partial S} \frac{1}{\rho} d\eta = \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{\ell_k} \frac{1}{\rho} d\eta$$

$$I_\eta = \int_S \frac{\eta}{\rho^3} = - \int_S \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta} \frac{1}{\rho} = - \oint_{\partial S} \frac{1}{\rho} d\xi = - \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{\ell_k} \frac{1}{\rho} d\xi$$

(119)

Figure 2: Local reference system.

that are computed as sums of the contributions from all the sides of the element. For the k -th side, the elementary elements

$$d\xi = ds \cos \theta_k \quad , \quad d\eta = ds \sin \theta_k \quad , \quad (120)$$

the computation integrals I_ξ , I_η only involves the computation of line integrals of the form

$$Q_k = \int_{\ell_k} \frac{1}{\rho} ds \quad . \quad (121)$$

so that

$$I_\xi = \sum_{k=1}^N Q_k \sin \theta_k \quad , \quad I_\eta = - \sum_{k=1}^N Q_k \cos \theta_k \quad . \quad (122)$$

Keep following Newman (1986), with reference to Fig.4, the integral Q_k on the k -th side reads

$$Q_k = \ln \frac{R_k + R_{k+1} + s_k}{R_k + R_{k+1} - s_k} \quad , \quad (123)$$

so that the expression (305) of the velocity induced by a constant-strength flat source panel S reads

$$4\pi \mathbf{u}^d = \sum_{k=1}^N Q_k(\xi, \eta, \zeta) \sin \theta_k \hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}} - \sum_{k=1}^N Q_k(\xi, \eta, \zeta) \cos \theta_k \hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}} + \Phi(\xi, \eta, \zeta) \hat{\boldsymbol{\zeta}} \quad , \quad (124)$$

where all the dependences on the space coordinates have been explicitly written.

Velocity gradient. In the previous section, the velocity induced by a source surface has been written with the coordinates (ξ, η, ζ) of the local reference system. First the components in the local reference frame of the velocity gradient will be computed; then the transformation rule for the components of tensors is used to obtain the components in the base reference frame, to be used in the dynamical equation of the vorticity.

First the transformation rule for tensor in orthogonal coordinate systems is derived. Then the computation of the spatial derivatives of the velocity field w.r.t. the local coordinates follows. Given the unit vectors $\hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_i$ of the local reference system and the unit vectors $\hat{\boldsymbol{x}}_k$ of the base reference system, the transformation rule between these vectors reads

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_i = \hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_i \cdot \hat{\boldsymbol{x}}_k \hat{\boldsymbol{x}}_k = T_{ik} \hat{\boldsymbol{x}}_k \quad , \quad (125)$$

having introduced the definition $T_{ik} = \hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_i \cdot \hat{\boldsymbol{x}}_k$. If the geometry and the orientation of the element is known, **the coefficients T_{ik} are known** as well. A vector field \mathbf{u} can be expressed in these two coordinate system as

$$\mathbf{u} = u^k \hat{\boldsymbol{x}}_k = v^k \hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_k \quad , \quad (126)$$

where u^k are the components of the vector in the base reference system $\{\hat{\boldsymbol{x}}_i\}$ and v^k the coordinates in the local reference system $\{\hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_i\}$. The definition of the gradient of a vector field reads

$$\nabla \mathbf{u} = \frac{\partial v^k}{\partial \xi_i} \hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_i \otimes \hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_k = \frac{\partial u^k}{\partial x_i} \hat{\boldsymbol{x}}_i \otimes \hat{\boldsymbol{x}}_k \quad . \quad (127)$$

Introducing the transformation rule for the vectors of the base,

$$\nabla \mathbf{u} = \frac{\partial v^k}{\partial \xi_i} T_{il} T_{km} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_\ell \otimes \hat{\mathbf{x}}_m \quad \rightarrow \quad \frac{\partial u^m}{\partial x_\ell} = \frac{\partial v^k}{\partial \xi_i} T_{il} T_{km} \quad , \quad [\nabla \mathbf{u}]_x = \underline{\underline{T}}^T [\nabla \mathbf{u}]_\xi \underline{\underline{T}} \quad , \quad (128)$$

where the components of the gradient of vector field are organised in the array as follows

$$[\nabla \mathbf{u}]_x = \begin{bmatrix} \partial_x u_x & \partial_x u_y & \partial_x u_z \\ \partial_y u_x & \partial_y u_y & \partial_y u_z \\ \partial_z u_x & \partial_z u_y & \partial_z u_z \end{bmatrix} . \quad (129)$$

Explicitly writing all the functions of the space coordinates in expression (312)

$$4\pi \mathbf{u}^d = \sum_{k=1}^N Q_k(\xi, \eta, \zeta) \sin \theta_k \hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}} - \sum_{k=1}^N Q_k(\xi, \eta, \zeta) \cos \theta_k \hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}} + \Phi(\xi, \eta, \zeta) \hat{\boldsymbol{\zeta}} \quad , \quad (130)$$

it is possible to figure out the terms to be differentiated in order to compute the gradient of the velocity field: it is clear that only the derivatives of the terms $Q_k(\xi, \eta, \zeta)$ and $\Phi(\xi, \eta, \zeta)$ are required. Since the length s_k of the k -th side is independent from the spatial coordinates, the derivatives of $Q_k(\xi, \eta, \zeta)$ reads

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial Q_k}{\partial \xi_i} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_i} \frac{R_k + R_{k+1} + s_k}{R_k + R_{k+1} - s_k} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_i} \frac{N_k}{D_k} = \\ &= \frac{R_k + R_{k+1} - s_k}{R_k + R_{k+1} + s_k} \cdot \frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_i} (R_k + R_{k+1}) (R_k + R_{k+1} - s_k) - \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_i} (R_k + R_{k+1}) (R_k + R_{k+1} + s_k)}{(R_k + R_{k+1} - s_k)^2} = \\ &= - \frac{2 s_k}{(R_k + R_{k+1} + s_k)(R_k + R_{k+1} - s_k)} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_i} (R_k + R_{k+1}) = - \frac{2 s_k}{N_k D_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_i} (R_k + R_{k+1}), \end{aligned} \quad (131)$$

being $R_k = |\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{P}_k| = \sqrt{(\xi - \xi^{(k)})^2 + (\eta - \eta^{(k)})^2 + \zeta^2}$ the distance between the passive point \mathbf{r} and the node \mathbf{P}_k of the surface element S . Differentiating the definition of R_k , the last missing term needed for $\partial Q_k / \partial \xi_i$ is computed as

$$\frac{\partial R_k}{\partial \xi_i} = \frac{\xi_i - \xi_i^{(k)}}{R_k} . \quad (132)$$

The spatial derivatives of Φ are computed starting from the expression of Φ .

4 Rotational velocity

The mathematical formulation of the solver implemented in **DUST** relies on the decomposition of the velocity field as the sum of the potential contribution, induced by the surface elements presented in Sec. §3, and the rotational contribution described in this section.

The computation of the rotational contribution \mathbf{u}_ψ relies on a vortex particle method (VPM) to provide a Lagrangian grid-free description of the velocity-vorticity formulation of the governing equations of the fluid, as an alternative to classical Eulerian grid methods. This numerical method is particularly suited for these flows where vorticity is confined only to a small fraction of the volume domain, as many aeronautical flows of interest. The vorticity field is represented as the sum of the elementary contributions associated with the vortex particles, material particles moving with the local fluid velocity. Thus, the evolution of the vorticity field is governed by the Lagrangian form of the vorticity equation and the kinematic equation of the material particles,

$$\begin{cases} \frac{D\boldsymbol{\omega}}{Dt} = (\boldsymbol{\omega} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{u} - \nu\Delta\boldsymbol{\omega} \\ \frac{D\mathbf{r}(t)}{Dt} = \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r}(t), t) . \end{cases} \quad (133)$$

The evolution of the vorticity of a material particle is influenced by vortex stretching/tilting and viscous effects. In the VPM method these terms are computed for each particle at each time step as the sum of the elementary interaction with all the other particles and potential elements. Since this is a $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ operation and the number of the vortex particles increases as the simulation advances in time, the computation of these interactions is accelerated by a Cartesian Fast Multiple Method (FMM), targeting the theoretical $\mathcal{O}(N)$ computational cost, as described in Chap. §5.

4.1 Poisson's equation for the vector potential

Following Helmholtz's decomposition of the velocity field, the rotational component of the velocity field is defined as the curl of the vector potential, $\mathbf{u}_\psi(\mathbf{r}, t) = \nabla \times \boldsymbol{\psi}(\mathbf{r}, t)$, and the vorticity field corresponds to the curl of the rotational component of the velocity, $\boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \nabla \times \mathbf{u}_\psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$. Using these two relations, a Poisson's equation for the vector potential $\boldsymbol{\psi}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ where the vorticity field $\boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ acts as the volume forcing,

$$-\Delta\boldsymbol{\psi} = \boldsymbol{\omega} , \quad (134)$$

is obtained, given the vector identity $\Delta\boldsymbol{\psi} = \nabla(\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\psi}) - \nabla \times \nabla \times \boldsymbol{\psi}$ and the gauge condition $\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\psi} = 0$. The potential vector field $\boldsymbol{\psi}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is computed as the solution of the Poisson's equation by means of the Green's function method, namely

$$\boldsymbol{\psi}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \int_{V_0} \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0)\boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r}_0, t)dV_0 = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{V_0} \frac{\boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r}_0, t)}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0|}dV_0 , \quad (135)$$

if the boundary contributions vanish, as in the case of unbounded aerodynamic flows. In a homogeneous and isotropic space, the kinetic potential can be interpreted as the convolution of the Green's function $\tilde{\mathcal{G}}(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0) = \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0)$ and the vorticity field $\boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r}, t)$,

$$\boldsymbol{\psi}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \int_{V_0} \tilde{\mathcal{G}}(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0)\boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r}_0, t)dV_0 = (\tilde{\mathcal{G}} * \boldsymbol{\omega})(\mathbf{r}, t) . \quad (136)$$

The rotational part of the velocity field \mathbf{u}_ψ is evaluated taking the curl of the vector potential field (135),

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{u}_\psi(\mathbf{r},t) &= \nabla \times \boldsymbol{\psi}(\mathbf{r},t) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \nabla \times \int_{V_0} \frac{\boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r}_0,t)}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0|} dV_0 = \\ &= -\frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{V_0} \frac{\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0|^3} \times \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r}_0,t) dV_0 =\end{aligned}\quad (137)$$

and it can be interpreted as the convolution of the Biot–Savart kernel, $\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}) = \nabla \tilde{\mathcal{G}}(\mathbf{x}) = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{\mathbf{x}}{|\mathbf{x}|^3}$, with the vorticity field,

$$\mathbf{u}_\psi(\mathbf{r},t) = \int_{V_0} \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0) \times \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r}_0,t) dV_0 = (\mathbf{K} * \boldsymbol{\omega})(\mathbf{r},t) . \quad (138)$$

4.2 Vortex particle method: vorticity approximation

Vortex particle methods introduce a finite-dimensional approximation of the vorticity field $\boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r},t)$ in the expression (138) of the rotational part of the velocity. First, the singular vortex particle method is introduced in Sec. §4.2.1, then regular methods are outlined in Sec. §4.2.2. The treatment of the vortex stretching/tilting and viscous terms follow in Sec. §4.3.1 and §4.3.2 respectively.

4.2.1 Vortex particles: singular model

The vortex particle method assumes the following form of the vorticity field

$$\boldsymbol{\omega}^h(\mathbf{r},t) = \sum_{p=1}^{N_p} \boldsymbol{\alpha}^p(t) \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_p(t)) , \quad (139)$$

where $\mathbf{r}^p(t)$ denotes the coordinate of the p^{th} vortex particle. Introducing the approximation (139) of the vorticity field in the expression (135), the approximation of vector potential field $\boldsymbol{\psi}(\mathbf{r},t)$ becomes,

$$\begin{aligned}\boldsymbol{\psi}^h(\mathbf{r},t) &= \frac{1}{4\pi} \sum_{p=1}^{N_p} \boldsymbol{\alpha}^p(t) \int_{V_0} \frac{\delta(\mathbf{r}_0 - \mathbf{r}^p(t))}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0|} dV_0 = \\ &= \frac{1}{4\pi} \sum_{p=1}^{N_p} \frac{\boldsymbol{\alpha}^p(t)}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_p(t)|} ,\end{aligned}\quad (140)$$

and the rotational part of the velocity fields follows,

$$\mathbf{u}_\varepsilon^h(\mathbf{r},t) = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \sum_{p=1}^{N_p} \frac{\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_p}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_p|^3} \times \boldsymbol{\alpha}^p(t) . \quad (141)$$

Both the vector potential and the rotational velocity (and its space derivatives) are singular at the location of the vortex particles. Regularised models are introduced in order to avoid infinite intensity interactions between particles.

4.2.2 Vortex particles: regular(ised) model

In order to avoid singularities, the vortex particle method assumes the following form of the vorticity field

$$\boldsymbol{\omega}_\varepsilon^h(\mathbf{r}, t) = \sum_{p=1}^{N_p} \boldsymbol{\alpha}^p \zeta_\varepsilon(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}^p(t)) , \quad (142)$$

where $\mathbf{r}^p(t)$ denotes the coordinate of the p^{th} vortex particle and the regular *cut-off* function $\zeta_\varepsilon(\mathbf{x})$ replaces the Dirac's delta of the singular model. The regular expression (142) is equal to the convolution of the singular vorticity field (139) with the *cut-off* function $\zeta_\varepsilon(\mathbf{r})$,

$$\begin{aligned} (\zeta_\varepsilon * \boldsymbol{\omega}^h)(\mathbf{r}, t) &= \int_{V_0} \zeta_\varepsilon(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0) \boldsymbol{\omega}^h(\mathbf{r}_0, t) dV_0 = \\ &= \int_{V_0} \zeta_\varepsilon(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0) \sum_{p=1}^{N_p} \boldsymbol{\alpha}^p(t) \delta(\mathbf{r}_0 - \mathbf{r}_p(t)) dV_0 = \\ &= \sum_{p=1}^{N_p} \boldsymbol{\alpha}^p(t) \zeta_\varepsilon(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_p(t)) = \boldsymbol{\omega}_\varepsilon^h(\mathbf{r}, t) . \end{aligned} \quad (143)$$

Replacing the Dirac's delta in the Poisson's equation for the Green's function with the cut-off function ζ_ε , the mollified Poisson's problem for the regularized Green's function \mathcal{G}_ε reads,

$$-\Delta \mathcal{G}_\varepsilon(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) = \zeta_\varepsilon(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0) , \quad (144)$$

whose solution is computed from the convolution of the Green's function \mathcal{G} with the cut-off function ζ_ε , $\mathcal{G}_\varepsilon(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) = (\mathcal{G} * \zeta_\varepsilon)(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0)$, namely

$$\mathcal{G}_\varepsilon(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) = \int_{V_c} \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_c) \zeta_\varepsilon(\mathbf{r}_c - \mathbf{r}_0) , \quad (145)$$

where the integration is performed on the \mathbf{r}_c variable. Using this relation and introducing the regular approximation (142) of the vorticity field in the expression (135) of the vector potential, its approximation reads,

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\psi}_\varepsilon^h(\mathbf{r}, t) &= \int_{V_0} \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) \boldsymbol{\omega}_\varepsilon^h(\mathbf{r}_0, t) = \\ &= \int_{V_0} \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) \sum_{p=1}^{N_p} \boldsymbol{\alpha}^p(t) \zeta_\varepsilon(\mathbf{r}_0 - \mathbf{r}^p(t)) = \\ &= \sum_{p=1}^{N_p} \boldsymbol{\alpha}^p(t) \mathcal{G}_\varepsilon(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_p(t)) = \sum_{p=1}^{N_p} \boldsymbol{\alpha}^p(t) \tilde{\mathcal{G}}_\varepsilon(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_p(t)) , \end{aligned} \quad (146)$$

and the regular velocity field $\mathbf{u}_\varepsilon^h(\mathbf{r}, t)$ reads,

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{u}_\varepsilon^h(\mathbf{r}, t) &= \nabla \times \boldsymbol{\psi}_\varepsilon^h(\mathbf{r}, t) = \\ &= \nabla \times \sum_{p=1}^{N_p} \boldsymbol{\alpha}^p(t) \tilde{\mathcal{G}}_\varepsilon(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_p(t)) = \\ &= \sum_{p=1}^{N_p} \nabla \tilde{\mathcal{G}}_\varepsilon(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_p(t)) \times \boldsymbol{\alpha}^p(t) = \sum_{p=1}^{N_p} \mathbf{K}_\varepsilon(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_p(t)) \times \boldsymbol{\alpha}^p(t) ,\end{aligned}\tag{147}$$

where the regular Biot–Savart kernel $\mathbf{K}_\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}) = \nabla \tilde{\mathcal{G}}_\varepsilon(\mathbf{x})$ has been defined. Several regularized Green’s function are available in literature with their respective regular Biot–Savart kernel (cite). In DUST, the Rosenhead kernel is implemented as the resularised version of the Biot–Savart kernel,

$$\mathbf{K}_\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}}{(|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|^2 + \delta^2)^{3/2}} ,\tag{148}$$

defined as the gradient of the Plummer’s potential,

$$\mathcal{G}_\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \frac{1}{4\pi(|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|^2 + \delta^2)^{1/2}} ,\tag{149}$$

where the regularization parameter δ is proportional to the radius of the vortex particles.

4.3 Vortex particle method: dynamical equations

A Lagrangian description of the rotational velocity and the vorticity fields is provided by the kinematic equation of the trajectory of the material particles and the vorticity equation,

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d\mathbf{r}_p(t)}{dt} = \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{r}_p(t), t) \\ \frac{D\boldsymbol{\omega}}{Dt} = (\boldsymbol{\omega} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{U} + \nu \nabla^2 \boldsymbol{\omega} , \end{cases}\tag{150}$$

where $\mathbf{r}_p(t)$ is the position of the p^{th} material particles and D/Dt is the material derivative, describing the time rate of change of a physical quantity of a material particle. These equations must be supplemented with appropriate initial conditions, and directly related to the wake shedding criterion from solid bodies in the simulations of flows of aeronautical interest. The discrete counterpart of the dynamical equations (150) reads,

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d\mathbf{r}_p(t)}{dt} = \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r}_p(t), t) \\ \frac{d\boldsymbol{\alpha}^p}{dt} = (\boldsymbol{\alpha}^p \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r}_p(t), t) + \nu \text{“}\nabla^2 \boldsymbol{\alpha}^p\text{”} , \end{cases}\tag{151}$$

where the $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{U}_\infty + \mathbf{u}_\varphi + \mathbf{u}_\psi$ is the complete velocity field and the operator $\nu \text{“}\nabla^2 \boldsymbol{\alpha}^p\text{”}$ represents the viscous term acting on the p -th particle,

$$\nu \text{“}\nabla^2 \boldsymbol{\alpha}^p\text{”} = \nu \int_{V_p} \nabla^2 \boldsymbol{\omega} ,\tag{152}$$

that is approximated in DUST by means of the *Particle-Strength Exchange* (PSE) method, described below.

4.3.1 Vortex stretching/tilting term

For incompressible flows, three different equivalent expressions of the vortex stretching and tilting term are available,

$$\begin{aligned}
(\boldsymbol{\omega} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} & \quad \text{(direct scheme)} \\
(\boldsymbol{\omega} \cdot \nabla^T) \mathbf{u} & \quad \text{(adjoint scheme)} \\
\frac{1}{2} [(\boldsymbol{\omega} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} + (\boldsymbol{\omega} \cdot \nabla^T) \mathbf{u}] & \quad \text{(symmetric scheme)}
\end{aligned} \tag{153}$$

The equivalence between the direct and the adjoint scheme is readily verified, writing their cartesian components, indicated with the ordered indices $\{i, j, k\}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
\{(\boldsymbol{\omega} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u}\}_i &= \sum_j \omega_j \partial_j u_i = \omega_i \partial_i u_i + \omega_j \partial_j u_i + \omega_k \partial_k u_i \\
\{(\boldsymbol{\omega} \cdot \nabla^T) \mathbf{u}\}_i &= \sum_j \omega_j \partial_i u_j = \omega_i \partial_i u_i + \omega_j \partial_i u_j + \omega_k \partial_i u_k,
\end{aligned} \tag{154}$$

and subtracting one from the other,

$$\begin{aligned}
\{(\boldsymbol{\omega} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} (\boldsymbol{\omega} \cdot \nabla^T) \mathbf{u}\}_i &= 0 + \omega_j (\partial_j u_i - \partial_i u_j) + \omega_k (\partial_k u_i - \partial_i u_k) = \\
&= -\omega_j \omega_k + \omega_k \omega_j = 0.
\end{aligned} \tag{155}$$

While these schemes are equivalent in the continuous framework, their discrete counterparts are not. In the following, only the discrete version of the transpose scheme of the near-field particle-to-particle direct interactions implemented in **DUST** is detailed. Direct scheme can be easily derived following the same procedure. The computation of panel-to-particle interactions require the expression of the velocity gradient (or its transpose) provided in Sec. §3, while the far-field interactions are accelerated with the Cartesian FMM, described in Sec. §5.

Transpose scheme. The transpose scheme for inviscid flows reads

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d\mathbf{r}^p(t)}{dt} = \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r}^p(t), t) \\ \frac{d\boldsymbol{\alpha}^p}{dt} = (\boldsymbol{\alpha}^p \cdot \nabla^T) \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r}^p(t), t), \end{cases} \tag{156}$$

where the index expression of the vortex stretching/tilting term reads,

$$(\boldsymbol{\alpha}^p \cdot \nabla^T) \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r}^p(t), t)_i = \alpha_k^p \partial_i u_k(\mathbf{r}^p(t), t). \tag{157}$$

This term is evaluated using the Rosenhead kernel (148). The influence on the particle p of all the particles $q = 1 : N$ but the particle p itself, is computed as

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{da_i^p}{dt} &= \alpha_k^p \partial_i u_k(\mathbf{r}^p(t), t) = \\
&= \alpha_k^p \partial_i \left[-\frac{1}{4\pi} \sum_q \varepsilon_{klm} \frac{r_\ell^p - r_\ell^q}{R^3} \alpha_m^q \right] = \\
&= -\frac{1}{4\pi} \sum_q \left[\alpha_k^p \varepsilon_{klm} \left(\frac{\delta_{i\ell}}{R^3} - 3 \frac{(r_i^p - r_i^q)(r_\ell^p - r_\ell^q)}{R^5} \right) \alpha_m^q \right] = \\
&= -\frac{1}{4\pi} \sum_q \left[\frac{1}{R^3} \varepsilon_{kim} \alpha_k^p \alpha_m^q - \frac{3}{R^5} (r_i^p - r_i^q)(r_\ell^p - r_\ell^q) \alpha_k^p \alpha_m^q \right],
\end{aligned} \tag{158}$$

or equivalently, in vector form,

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d\boldsymbol{\alpha}^p}{dt} &= -\frac{1}{4\pi} \sum_q \left[\frac{1}{R^3} \boldsymbol{\alpha}^q \times \boldsymbol{\alpha}^p - \frac{3}{R^5} \Delta \mathbf{r}^{pq} (\boldsymbol{\alpha}^q \cdot \boldsymbol{\alpha}^p \times \Delta \mathbf{r}^{pq}) \right] = \\
&= -\frac{1}{4\pi} \sum_q \left[\frac{1}{R^3} \boldsymbol{\alpha}^q \times \boldsymbol{\alpha}^p - \frac{3}{R^5} \Delta \mathbf{r}^{pq} (\Delta \mathbf{r}^{pq} \cdot \boldsymbol{\alpha}^q \times \boldsymbol{\alpha}^p) \right],
\end{aligned} \tag{159}$$

where $R = (|\Delta \mathbf{r}^{pq}|^2 + \delta^2)^{1/2}$ and $\Delta \mathbf{r}^{pq} = \mathbf{r}^p - \mathbf{r}^q$.

4.3.2 Viscous term: Particle Strength Exchange (PSE) method

The viscous term in the vorticity equation is modelled with the PSE method, whose idea is to replace the differential Laplacian operator by an integral one. It is possible to prove (see the paragraph at the end of this section) that the integral operator

$$\Delta_\epsilon \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{x}) = \epsilon^{-2} \int_V [\boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{y}) - \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{x})] \eta_\epsilon(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}) dV_{\mathbf{y}}, \tag{160}$$

is a good approximation of the differential Laplacian operator, i.e. $\Delta_\epsilon \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{x}) \sim \Delta \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{x})$, if the kernel function is defined as $\eta_\epsilon(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{\epsilon^3} \eta\left(\frac{\mathbf{x}}{\epsilon}\right)$ and $\eta(\mathbf{x})$ satisfies the following conditions

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_V x_i x_j \eta(\mathbf{x}) dV &= 2\delta_{ij} \quad , \quad \text{for } i, j = 1, 2, 3 \\
\int_V x_1^{i_1} x_2^{i_2} x_3^{i_3} \eta(\mathbf{x}) dV &= 0 \quad , \quad \text{if } i_1 + i_2 + i_3 = 1 \text{ or } 3 \leq i_1 + i_2 + i_3 \leq r + 1 \\
\int_V |\mathbf{x}|^{r+2} |\eta(\mathbf{x})| &< \infty .
\end{aligned} \tag{161}$$

For vortex particle methods, the integral (160) can be approximated as the summation over all the particles in the domain,

$$\Delta_\epsilon \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{x}) \simeq \epsilon^{-2} \sum_q V_q [\boldsymbol{\omega}_q - \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{x})] \eta_\epsilon(\mathbf{r}_q - \mathbf{x}), \tag{162}$$

where V_q is the volume of the q^{th} vortex particle. Thus, the integral PSE approximation of the viscous term “ $\nabla^2 \boldsymbol{\alpha}^p$ ” = $\int_{V_p} \Delta_\varepsilon \boldsymbol{\omega}$ reads

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{“}\nabla^2 \boldsymbol{\alpha}^p\text{”} &= \varepsilon^{-2} \int_{V_p} \sum_q V_q [\boldsymbol{\omega}_q - \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{x})] \eta_\varepsilon(\mathbf{r}_q - \mathbf{x}) \\
&= \varepsilon^{-2} V_p \sum_q V_q [\boldsymbol{\omega}_q - \boldsymbol{\omega}_p] \eta_\varepsilon(\mathbf{r}_q - \mathbf{r}_p) = \\
&= \varepsilon^{-2} \sum_q [V_p \boldsymbol{\alpha}_q - V_q \boldsymbol{\alpha}_p] \eta_\varepsilon(\mathbf{r}_q - \mathbf{r}_p) .
\end{aligned} \tag{163}$$

Winkelmans provides some examples of kernel functions with spherical symmetry, $\tilde{\eta}(r) = \eta(r)$, with $r = |\mathbf{r}|$. Some of them are listed here, with the respective regularisation function $\tilde{\zeta}(r)$, that must satisfy $\tilde{\eta}(r) = -\frac{\tilde{\zeta}'(r)}{r}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{\zeta}(r) = \frac{e^{-r^2/2}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} &\rightarrow \tilde{\eta}(r) = \frac{e^{-r^2/2}}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} = \tilde{\zeta}(r) && \text{(Gaussian)} \\
\tilde{\zeta}(r) = \frac{3}{4\pi} \frac{1}{(1+r^2)^{5/2}} &\rightarrow \tilde{\eta}(r) = \frac{15}{4\pi} \frac{1}{(1+r^2)^{7/2}} && \text{(Low-order algebraic)} \\
\tilde{\zeta}(r) = \frac{15}{8\pi} \frac{1}{(1+r^2)^{7/2}} &\rightarrow \tilde{\eta}(r) = \frac{105}{8\pi} \frac{1}{(1+r^2)^{9/2}} && \text{(High-order algebraic)}
\end{aligned} \tag{164}$$

The high-order algebraic kernel function is currently used in the PSE method implemented in DUST.

From differential to integral operator. Using multi-indices notation, the Taylor series of the vorticity field reads

$$\boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{y}) = \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}) = \sum_{|\mathbf{m}|=0}^{\infty} \frac{D^{\mathbf{m}} \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{x})}{\mathbf{m}!} (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x})^{\mathbf{m}} = \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{x}) + \sum_{|\mathbf{m}|=1}^{\infty} \frac{D^{\mathbf{m}} \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{x})}{\mathbf{m}!} (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x})^{\mathbf{m}} . \tag{165}$$

Inserting the approximation of the difference $\boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{y}) - \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{x})$ in the expression (160),

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta_\epsilon \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{x}) &= \epsilon^{-2} \int_V [\boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{y}) - \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{x})] \eta_\epsilon(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}) dV_{\mathbf{y}} = \\
&= \epsilon^{-2} \sum_{|m|=1}^{\infty} \frac{D^m \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{x})}{m!} \int_V (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x})^m \eta_\epsilon(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}) dV_{\mathbf{y}} = \\
&\simeq \epsilon^{-2} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \boldsymbol{\omega}}{\partial x_1^2}(\mathbf{x}) \underbrace{\int_V (y_1 - x_1)^2 \eta_\epsilon(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}) dV_{\mathbf{y}}}_{=2\epsilon^2} + \right. \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \boldsymbol{\omega}}{\partial x_2^2}(\mathbf{x}) \underbrace{\int_V (y_2 - x_2)^2 \eta_\epsilon(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}) dV_{\mathbf{y}}}_{=2\epsilon^2} \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \boldsymbol{\omega}}{\partial x_3^2}(\mathbf{x}) \underbrace{\int_V (y_3 - x_3)^2 \eta_\epsilon(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x}) dV_{\mathbf{y}}}_{=2\epsilon^2} \right\} = \Delta \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{x}) .
\end{aligned} \tag{166}$$

4.4 Generation of the vortex particles

The vortex particles are generated from the wake vortex lattices. At each timestep the wake panels are advected downstream and another panels is generated, after a prescribed n_{wp} number of time steps of existence of a panel the panel is converted into a particle, generating after the initial transient a wake with n_{wp} rows of panels attached to the trailing edges followed by a particles wake. It is possible to obtain a full particles wake by prescribing $n_{wp} = 1$, which leaves only the first row of implicit panels, necessary to enforce the Kutta condition.

When converting each panel into a particle the intensity comes from the integration of the vorticity contribution from the sides of the vortex lattice element. However since each vortex ring panel has a constant intensity and represents a closed path, the simple integration of its sides would lead to a zero value. For this reason the actual intensity of each side due to the superimposition of the neighbouring panels sides is considered, and the contribution of each side is distributed to the neighbouring particles which are about to be generated, see Fig. 3 for a detailed scheme. While the neighbouring elements in the direction normal to the flow are converted simultaneously and their contribution is shared with the respective particles, the previous panel in the streamwise direction was already converted the previous timestep. For this reason each particles if formed with the contribution of the two lateral sides of the panel, the rearmost side and a line vortex left by the previous panel, while the present panel leaves the foremost side as a line vortex attached to the following panel. The contribution from each lateral side can be defined as

$$\mathbf{J}_s = \begin{cases} \int_s \frac{1}{2} (\mu_{w,i} - \mu_{w,i_n}) dl & \text{if neighbour } i_n \text{ present} \\ \int_s \mu_{w,i} dl & \text{if neighbour } i_n \text{ absent} \end{cases}, \tag{167}$$

where s is one side and the contribution is the whole vorticity of the side if no neighbour is present or half of the net contribution of the side. The other half will be assigned to the neighbouring particle. The end side contribution is

$$\mathbf{J}_E = \int_s (\mu_{w,i} - \mu_{i_{end}}) d\mathbf{l} \quad (168)$$

where $\mu_{i_{end}}$ is the intensity of the corresponding end line vortex, and thus defining $\mathbf{J}_L, \mathbf{J}_R$ the contribution from the two lateral sides, the intensity of the generated particle is:

$$\alpha_{i_p} = \mathbf{J}_L + \mathbf{J}_R + \mathbf{J}_E. \quad (169)$$

Figure 3: Schematics of an example of conversion from panels to particles: the panel i is converted into the particle i_p , the intensity of the particle is obtained considering the contribution of three sides. The left side L contribution is full since there are no neighbours. The contribution of the end side E is the difference between the panel intensity and the line vortex intensity. The contribution of the right side R is due to the difference between element i and the neighbouring element i_n , however the contribution is split in half between particle i_p and the particle generated by the neighbouring panel.

The newly generated particle is positioned at the centre of the previous panel, and then starts evolving according to (150). Both the computation of the intensity and the initial placement are approximations, however they do not introduce a significant error, while using more complex distribution of particles to describe a converted panel do not lead to a noticeable increase of accuracy.

5 Fast Multiple Method

In vortex particle simulations, the direct evaluation of the particle-to-particle interactions in a N -particle problem has a $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ computational cost. Usually, as the number of the vortex particles increases during a numerical simulation using a panel-particle solver like DUST, the evaluation of particle-to-particle interactions becomes the most expensive task. Fast Multipole Methods (FMM) have been developed in order to reduce the computational cost of particle-to-particle interactions in N -body problems, aiming at the theoretical $\mathcal{O}(N)$ computational cost. The Cartesian FMM, presented by [Lindsay and Krasny \(2001\)](#) and used by [Brown and Line \(2005\)](#), is implemented in DUST is detailed here. This method is presented for the regular Rosenhead–Moore kernel,

$$\mathbf{K}_\delta(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}}{(|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|^2 + \delta^2)^{3/2}}, \quad (170)$$

the gradient of the Plummer potential,

$$\phi_\delta(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{1}{(|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|^2 + \delta^2)^{1/2}}. \quad (171)$$

From Sec. §4, the rotational velocity \mathbf{u}_i induced in the point \mathbf{x}_i by all the vortex particles reads

$$\mathbf{u}_i = \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_i) = \sum_{j=1}^N \mathbf{K}_\delta(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{y}_j) \times \boldsymbol{\alpha}_j, \quad (172)$$

where \mathbf{y}_j and $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_j$ are the position and the intensity of the j^{th} vortex particle. Fast Multipole Methods rely on the Taylor series expansion of the equation (172) around the position of both the source and the target particles, in order to compute far-field interactions between well-separated clusters of particles and use direct computation only for near-field interactions.

In this chapter, first some properties of the potential functions and the compact multi-index notation is presented in Sec. §5.1. The Cartesian FMM follows in Sec. §5.2. Then, some properties of the Plummer potential and the Rosenhead kernel are presented in Sec. §5.3, along with the recursive relations used for the actual evaluation of the derivatives of the kernel appearing in the Taylor series of equation (172) involved in the FMM. Eventually, some details of the actual management of the Octree structure underlying the Cartesian FMM and its implementation in DUST are provided in Sec §5.4.

5.1 Properties of the kernel functions and multi-index notation

Spherically symmetrical potential functions depend only on the distance between the interacting points and are well suited for interactions in isotropic space. The symmetry properties of a spherically symmetrical potential function, like the Plummer potential, and its spatial derivatives are discussed here. The potential and its derivatives are function of two spatial locations, those of the passive point \mathbf{x} and the active point \mathbf{y} , assumed to be the first and the second argument of these functions respectively.

Symmetries of Plummer potential and Rosenhead kernel (I): first order derivatives. The Rosenhead kernel can be obtained as the gradient of the Plummer potential,

$$\phi_\delta(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{1}{(|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|^2 + \delta^2)^{1/2}}, \quad (173)$$

i.e.

$$\mathbf{K}_\delta = \nabla_{\mathbf{x}}\phi = -\nabla_{\mathbf{y}}\phi. \quad (174)$$

Since the Plummer potential and the Rosenhead kernel could be defined as functions of the vector radius $\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}$, going from the source particle to the target particle, the following property holds

$$\frac{\partial\phi_\delta}{\partial x_i} = -\frac{\partial\phi_\delta}{\partial y_i}, \quad \frac{\partial K_j}{\partial x_i} = -\frac{\partial K_j}{\partial y_i}. \quad (175)$$

Multi-index compact notation. The multi-index \mathbf{m} will be used to obtain a compact expression of the Taylor series of a function in a multi-dimensional space. The following properties/definitions of the multi-index $\mathbf{m} = (m_x, m_y, m_z)$ hold

$$|\mathbf{m}| = m_x + m_y + m_z, \quad \mathbf{m}! = m_x! m_y! m_z!, \quad \mathbf{a}^{\mathbf{m}} = a_x^{m_x} a_y^{m_y} a_z^{m_z}. \quad (176)$$

The symbol $D_{\mathbf{y}}^{\mathbf{m}}$ will be introduced to represent the mixed partial derivative of order $m = |\mathbf{m}|$ with respect to the second argument of the functions $\phi_\delta(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$, $\mathbf{K}_\delta(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$, \dots

$$D_{\mathbf{y}}^{\mathbf{m}} = \frac{\partial^{m_x}}{\partial y_x^{m_x}} \frac{\partial^{m_y}}{\partial y_y^{m_y}} \frac{\partial^{m_z}}{\partial y_z^{m_z}}. \quad (177)$$

Symmetries of Plummer potential and Rosenhead kernel (II): higher order derivatives. It is possible to get the symmetry properties of the Plummer potential and the Rosenhead kernel for higher order derivatives, using the multi-index compact notation introduced above. The following property readily follows

$$D_{\mathbf{y}}^{\mathbf{m}} \text{---} = (-1)^{|\mathbf{m}|} D_{\mathbf{x}}^{\mathbf{m}} \text{---}, \quad (178)$$

5.2 Cartesian Fast Multiple Method (FMM)

In this section, the FMM method is briefly outlined and some steps of the algorithm are detailed to obtain the expressions that are implemented in DUST. Fast Multipole Methods are fast algorithms to compute N -body interactions and solving some families of differential equations, after recasting them into integral problems. These algorithms rely on the subdivision of the domain into subdomains (boxes), identifying clusters of close particles separated from the other particles. The particles belonging to a each box are grouped in *clusters*, used in the evaluation of the far-field interactions. The domain is divided using an Octree structure. As an example, a cubic domain is first divided in 8 boxes at the first level of the Octree. Each of these 8 boxes is divided again in 8 boxes, belonging to the second level of the Octree. The division of the domain proceeds forward to the lowest level of the Octree, as set by the user or required by the particle distribution in the domain. An adaptive non-uniform domain Octree structure

is implemented in DUST, but not considered in this description of the basic steps of the FMM.

A parent-child relationship is established between a cell and its subcells. A neighboring relationship is established between the cells at the same level of the Octree. The *neighbors* of a cell are the cells sharing a face with it, otherwise they are *well-separated* from it. An *interaction list* is defined for the cell i at each level ℓ of the Octree, as the children of the neighbors of i 's parent that are well separated from cell i itself.

The steps of a FMM method run across the Octree twice, first from the lowest (the most refined) to the highest level and then back again to the leaves of the Octree. At the lowest level, the multipole expansion of all the leaf clusters is computed. Then, the coefficients of the children multipole expansions are combined to obtain the multipole coefficients of their parents up to the highest level of the Octree, in the *translation of multipole expansions* (M2M). Starting from the highest level, each cell interacts only with the cells in its interaction list. The coefficients of multipole expansions are converted into the coefficients of local expansions (M2L). The interactions with cells in the far-field (not in the near-field nor in the interaction list) is inherited from the parent cells, in the *translation of local expansions* (L2L), from the highestdown to the lowest level of the Octree. Eventually, the direct interactions between near-field particles are evaluated and added to the far-field interaction computed with the previous steps of the FMM.

5.2.1 Multipole expansion

An approximation of the influence of a cluster of particles \mathbf{y}_j , $j \in T$, on the target particle \mathbf{x}_i is obtained expanding the kernel of equation (172) in a Taylor series with respect to the second argument of the function $\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$, indicating the position of the sources \mathbf{y}_j , about the cell center \mathbf{y}^* . This expansion reads

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{y}_j) &= \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{y}^* + (\mathbf{y}_j - \mathbf{y}^*)) = \\ &= \sum_{|\mathbf{m}|=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\mathbf{m}!} D_{\mathbf{y}}^{\mathbf{m}} \mathbf{K}_{\delta}(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{y}^*) (\mathbf{y}_j - \mathbf{y}^*)^{\mathbf{m}} . \end{aligned} \quad (179)$$

Taylor series (179) is truncated at order p and introduced in equation (172) to get

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}_i &= \sum_{j \in T} \sum_{|\mathbf{m}|=0}^p \frac{1}{\mathbf{m}!} D_{\mathbf{y}}^{\mathbf{m}} \mathbf{K}_{\delta}(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{y}_T^*) (\mathbf{y}_j - \mathbf{y}_T^*)^{\mathbf{m}} \times \alpha_j = \\ &= \sum_{|\mathbf{m}|=0}^p \frac{1}{\mathbf{m}!} D_{\mathbf{y}}^{\mathbf{m}} \mathbf{K}_{\delta}(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{y}_T^*) \times \sum_{j \in T} \alpha_j (\mathbf{y}_j - \mathbf{y}_T^*)^{\mathbf{m}} = \\ &= \sum_{|\mathbf{m}|=0}^p \frac{1}{\mathbf{m}!} D_{\mathbf{y}}^{\mathbf{m}} \mathbf{K}_{\delta}(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{y}_T^*) \times \mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{m}, T} , \end{aligned} \quad (180)$$

where $\mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{m}, T} = \sum_{j \in T} \alpha_j (\mathbf{y}_j - \mathbf{y}_T^*)^{\mathbf{m}}$ is the \mathbf{m} -th moment of the cluster T , independent from the target particle \mathbf{x}_i .

5.2.2 Translation of multipole expansions - M2M

In FMM, the coefficients $\underline{\mathbf{a}}_{\ell,k}$ of multipole expansions are directly computed only at the finest level $\ell = J$ of the domain subdivision. Then, these coefficients are translated to the coefficients of cells belonging to higher levels of the tree, $\ell = J - 1 : -1 : 0$. The \mathbf{m} -th moment $\mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{m},\ell-1,k} = \sum_{j \in (\ell-1,k)} \alpha_j (\mathbf{y}_j - \mathbf{y}_{\ell-1,k}^*)^{\mathbf{m}}$ of the cell $\ell - 1, k$ can be written as the sum of the contributions from the son-cells of (ℓ, k) ,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{m},\ell-1,k} &= \sum_{j \in (\ell-1,k)} \alpha_j (\mathbf{y}_j - \mathbf{y}_{\ell-1,k}^*)^{\mathbf{m}} = \\ &= \sum_{c=1}^{2^d} \sum_{j \in (\ell, \text{son}((\ell-1,k), c))} \alpha_j (\mathbf{y}_j - \mathbf{y}_{\ell-1,k}^*)^{\mathbf{m}}, \end{aligned} \quad (181)$$

where d is the spatial dimension of the problem, 2^d is the number of sons of each cell and $\text{son}((\ell-1,k), c)$ is the c -th son (at level ℓ) of the cell $(\ell-1, k)$. Using the binomial expansion, the term $(\mathbf{y}_j - \mathbf{y}_{\ell-1,k}^*)^{\mathbf{m}}$ can be manipulated to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{y}_j - \mathbf{y}_{\ell-1,k}^*)^{\mathbf{m}} &= (\mathbf{y}_j - \mathbf{y}_{\ell, \text{son}((\ell-1,k), c)}^* + \mathbf{y}_{\ell, \text{son}((\ell-1,k), c)}^* - \mathbf{y}_{\ell-1,k}^*)^{\mathbf{m}} = \\ &= \sum_{\mathbf{s}=0}^{\mathbf{m}} \binom{\mathbf{m}}{\mathbf{s}} (\mathbf{y}_{\ell, \text{son}((\ell-1,k), c)}^* - \mathbf{y}_{\ell-1,k}^*)^{\mathbf{m}-\mathbf{s}} (\mathbf{y}_j - \mathbf{y}_{\ell, \text{son}((\ell-1,k), c)}^*)^{\mathbf{s}} = \\ &= \sum_{\mathbf{s}=0}^{\mathbf{m}} \binom{\mathbf{m}}{\mathbf{s}} (\mathbf{y}_{\ell, \text{son}((\ell-1,k), c)}^* - \mathbf{y}_{\ell-1,k}^*)^{\mathbf{m}-\mathbf{s}} (\mathbf{y}_j - \mathbf{y}_{\ell, \text{son}((\ell-1,k), c)}^*)^{\mathbf{s}} = \\ &= \sum_{\mathbf{s}=0}^{\mathbf{m}} \binom{\mathbf{m}}{\mathbf{s}} \left(\frac{\mathbf{h}_{\ell}^{(c)}}{2} \right)^{\mathbf{m}-\mathbf{s}} (\mathbf{y}_j - \mathbf{y}_{\ell, \text{son}((\ell-1,k), c)}^*)^{\mathbf{s}}, \end{aligned} \quad (182)$$

where the vector $\mathbf{h}_{\ell}^{(c)}/2$ represents the difference between the center of the c -th son of cell $(\ell-1, k)$ and the center of cell $(\ell-1, k)$ itself. The components of these vectors are equal to $\pm h_{\ell}/2$, where h_{ℓ} is the dimension of the cells at level ℓ . The binomial coefficient of the multi-indices \mathbf{m}, \mathbf{s} indicates the product of the binomial coefficients of each single component of the multi-indices, i.e.

$$\binom{\mathbf{m}}{\mathbf{s}} = \binom{m_x}{s_x} \binom{m_y}{s_y} \binom{m_z}{s_z}. \quad (183)$$

Inserting the binomial expansion (182) in the expression (181) of $\mathbf{a}_{m,\ell-1,k}$, the translation rule for multipole coefficients follows,

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{a}_{m,\ell-1,k} &= \sum_{j \in (\ell-1,k)} \alpha_j (\mathbf{y}_j - \mathbf{y}_{\ell-1,k}^*)^m = \\
&= \sum_{c=1}^{2^d} \sum_{j \in (\ell, \text{son}((\ell-1,k),c))} \alpha_j (\mathbf{y}_j - \mathbf{y}_{\ell-1,k}^*)^m = \\
&= \sum_{c=1}^{2^d} \sum_{j \in (\ell, \text{son}((\ell-1,k),c))} \alpha_j \sum_{s=0}^m \binom{m}{s} \left(\frac{\mathbf{h}_\ell^{(c)}}{2} \right)^{m-s} (\mathbf{y}_j - \mathbf{y}_{\ell, \text{son}((\ell-1,k),c)}^*)^s = \quad (184) \\
&= \sum_{c=1}^{2^d} \sum_{s=0}^m \binom{m}{s} \left(\frac{\mathbf{h}_\ell^{(c)}}{2} \right)^{m-s} \sum_{j \in (\ell, \text{son}((\ell-1,k),c))} \alpha_j (\mathbf{y}_j - \mathbf{y}_{\ell, \text{son}((\ell-1,k),c)}^*)^s = \\
&= \sum_{c=1}^{2^d} \sum_{s=0}^m \binom{m}{s} \left(\frac{\mathbf{h}_\ell^{(c)}}{2} \right)^{m-s} \mathbf{a}_{s,\ell, \text{son}((\ell-1,k),c)} .
\end{aligned}$$

5.2.3 From multipole to local expansion - M2L

In FMM, each cell directly interacts only with cells at the same level. At level ℓ , the influence on the cell (ℓ,k) from all the cells in its interaction list $(\ell,s) \in I(\ell,k)$ is obtained as the sum of the respective multipole approximation. The sum of these terms must be transformed in a local expansion with respect to the first argument of the kernel, i.e. the position of the target particle $i \in T_{\ell,k}$, about the center $\mathbf{x}_{\ell,k}^*$ of the cell $T_{\ell,k}$ itself. The multipole expansion,

$$\Phi(\mathbf{x}_i; \mathbf{x}_{\ell,s}^*, \underline{\mathbf{a}}_{\ell,s}) = \sum_{|\mathbf{m}|=0}^p \frac{1}{\mathbf{m}!} D_{\mathbf{y}}^{\mathbf{m}} \mathbf{K}_\delta(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_{\ell,s}^*) \times \mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{m},\ell,s} , \quad (185)$$

represents a p -order approximation of the influence of cell (ℓ,s) on the particle $i \in T_{\ell,k}$. The local expansion of order p in the cell (ℓ,k) is the polynomial expansion about its cell-center $\mathbf{x}_{\ell,k}^*$,

$$\Psi(\mathbf{x}_i; \mathbf{x}_{\ell,k}^*, \underline{\mathbf{b}}_{\ell,k}) = \sum_{|\mathbf{m}|=0}^p \mathbf{b}_{\mathbf{m},\ell,k} (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_{\ell,k}^*)^{\mathbf{m}} . \quad (186)$$

and it locally collects the effects of all the source cells (ℓ,s) in the interaction list $I(\ell,k)$ of the target cell (ℓ,k) . Once the coefficients $\underline{\mathbf{a}}_{\ell,s}$ are known, the coefficients $\underline{\mathbf{b}}_{\ell,k}$ are computed by equating the expression of the local and the multipole expansions. Taylor series w.r.t its first argument of the kernel function is computed about the center $\mathbf{x}_{\ell,k}^*$ of the cell (ℓ,k) ,

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{1}{\mathbf{m}!} D_{\mathbf{y}}^{\mathbf{m}} \mathbf{K}_\delta(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{y}_{\ell,s}^*) &= \frac{1}{\mathbf{m}!} D_{\mathbf{y}}^{\mathbf{m}} \mathbf{K}_\delta(\mathbf{x}_{\ell,k}^* + (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_{\ell,k}^*), \mathbf{y}_{\ell,s}^*) = \\
&= \sum_{|\mathbf{n}|=0}^p \frac{1}{\mathbf{n}!} \frac{1}{\mathbf{m}!} D_{\mathbf{x}}^{\mathbf{n}} D_{\mathbf{y}}^{\mathbf{m}} \mathbf{K}_\delta(\mathbf{x}_{\ell,k}^*, \mathbf{y}_{\ell,s}^*) (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_{\ell,k}^*)^{\mathbf{n}} , \quad (187)
\end{aligned}$$

and it is introduced in the multipole expansion (185). The polynomial expansion obtained from the the multipole expansion of the interacting cells (ℓ, s) is then compared with the local expansion (186) of the cell (ℓ, k) ,

$$\begin{aligned}
\Psi(\mathbf{x}_i; \mathbf{x}_{\ell, k}^*, \underline{\mathbf{b}}_{\ell, k}) &= \sum_{(\ell, s) \in I(\ell, k)} \Phi(\mathbf{x}_i; \mathbf{y}_{\ell, s}^*, \underline{\mathbf{a}}_{\ell, s}) \\
&\downarrow \\
\sum_{|\mathbf{m}|=0}^p \mathbf{b}_{\mathbf{m}, \ell, k} (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_{\ell, k}^*)^{\mathbf{m}} &= \sum_{(\ell, s) \in I(\ell, k)} \sum_{|\mathbf{m}|=0}^p \sum_{|\mathbf{n}|=0}^p \frac{1}{\mathbf{n}!} \frac{1}{\mathbf{m}!} D_{\mathbf{x}}^{\mathbf{n}} D_{\mathbf{y}}^{\mathbf{m}} \mathbf{K}_{\delta}(\mathbf{x}_{\ell, k}^*, \mathbf{y}_{\ell, s}^*) \times \mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{m}, \ell, s} (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_{\ell, k}^*)^{\mathbf{n}} = \\
&= \sum_{|\mathbf{m}|=0}^p \left\{ \sum_{(\ell, s) \in I(\ell, k)} \sum_{|\mathbf{n}|=0}^p \frac{1}{\mathbf{m}!} \frac{1}{\mathbf{n}!} D_{\mathbf{x}}^{\mathbf{m}} D_{\mathbf{y}}^{\mathbf{n}} \mathbf{K}_{\delta}(\mathbf{x}_{\ell, k}^*, \mathbf{y}_{\ell, s}^*) \times \mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{n}, \ell, s} \right\} (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_{\ell, k}^*)^{\mathbf{m}}, \tag{188}
\end{aligned}$$

so that the curly braces contain the expressions of the coefficients $\underline{\mathbf{b}}_{\ell, k}$ appearing in the local expansion,

$$\mathbf{b}_{\mathbf{m}, \ell, k} = \sum_{(\ell, s) \in I(\ell, k)} \sum_{|\mathbf{n}|=0}^p \frac{1}{\mathbf{m}!} \frac{1}{\mathbf{n}!} D_{\mathbf{x}}^{\mathbf{m}} D_{\mathbf{y}}^{\mathbf{n}} \mathbf{K}_{\delta}(\mathbf{x}_{\ell, k}^*, \mathbf{y}_{\ell, s}^*) \times \mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{n}, \ell, s}. \tag{189}$$

5.2.4 Translation of local expansions - L2L

In FMM, the interactions with cells in the far-field (cells that are not in the near-field nor in the interaction list) is not directly computed, but it is inherited from the parent cells. The translation of the local expansion from cell (ℓ, k) to cell $(\ell, \text{son}((\ell - 1, k), c))$ is obtained by equating

$$\begin{aligned}
\Psi(\mathbf{x}_i; \mathbf{x}_{\ell, \text{son}((\ell-1, k), c)}^*, \underline{\mathbf{b}}_{\ell, \text{son}((\ell-1, k), c)}) &= \Psi(\mathbf{x}_i; \mathbf{x}_{\ell-1, k}^*, \underline{\mathbf{b}}_{\ell-1, k}) \\
\sum_{|\mathbf{m}|=0}^p \mathbf{b}_{\mathbf{m}, \ell, \text{son}((\ell-1, k), c)} (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_{\ell, \text{son}((\ell-1, k), c)}^*)^{\mathbf{m}} &= \sum_{|\mathbf{m}|=0}^p \mathbf{b}_{\mathbf{m}, \ell-1, k} (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_{\ell-1, k}^*)^{\mathbf{m}} \tag{190}
\end{aligned}$$

for $\mathbf{x}_i \in (\ell, \text{son}((\ell - 1, k), c)) =: (\ell, \tilde{c})$. Using the binomial expansion, the term $(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_{\ell-1, k}^*)^{\mathbf{m}}$ can be manipulated to obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_{\ell-1, k}^*)^{\mathbf{m}} &= (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_{\ell, \tilde{c}}^* + \mathbf{x}_{\ell, \tilde{c}}^* - \mathbf{x}_{\ell-1, k}^*)^{\mathbf{m}} = \\
&= \sum_{s=0}^{\mathbf{m}} \binom{\mathbf{m}}{s} (\mathbf{x}_{\ell, \tilde{c}}^* - \mathbf{x}_{\ell-1, k}^*)^{\mathbf{m}-s} (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_{\ell, \tilde{c}}^*)^s = \\
&= \sum_{s=0}^{\mathbf{m}} \binom{\mathbf{m}}{s} (\mathbf{x}_{\ell, \tilde{c}}^* - \mathbf{x}_{\ell-1, k}^*)^{\mathbf{m}-s} (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_{\ell, \tilde{c}}^*)^s = \\
&= \sum_{s=0}^{\mathbf{m}} \binom{\mathbf{m}}{s} \left(\frac{\mathbf{h}_{\ell}^{(c)}}{2} \right)^{\mathbf{m}-s} (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_{\ell, \tilde{c}}^*)^s. \tag{191}
\end{aligned}$$

Introducing the expansion (191) in the equation (190), the translation rule for local coefficients is obtained,

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{|\mathbf{m}|=0}^p \mathbf{b}_{\mathbf{m},\ell-1,k} (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_{\ell-1,k}^*)^{\mathbf{m}} &= \sum_{|\mathbf{m}|=0}^p \mathbf{b}_{\mathbf{m},\ell-1,k} \sum_{\mathbf{s}=0}^{\mathbf{m}} \binom{\mathbf{m}}{\mathbf{s}} \left(\frac{\mathbf{h}_\ell^{(c)}}{2} \right)^{\mathbf{m}-\mathbf{s}} (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_{\ell,\tilde{c}}^*)^{\mathbf{s}} = \\
&= \sum_{|\mathbf{s}|=0}^p \mathbf{b}_{\mathbf{s},\ell-1,k} \sum_{\mathbf{m}=0}^{\mathbf{s}} \binom{\mathbf{s}}{\mathbf{m}} \left(\frac{\mathbf{h}_\ell^{(c)}}{2} \right)^{\mathbf{s}-\mathbf{m}} (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_{\ell,\tilde{c}}^*)^{\mathbf{m}} = \\
&= \sum_{\mathbf{m}=0}^p \sum_{\mathbf{s}=\mathbf{m}}^p \mathbf{b}_{\mathbf{s},\ell-1,k} \binom{\mathbf{s}}{\mathbf{m}} \left(\frac{\mathbf{h}_\ell^{(c)}}{2} \right)^{\mathbf{s}-\mathbf{m}} (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_{\ell,\tilde{c}}^*)^{\mathbf{m}} ,
\end{aligned} \tag{192}$$

where the limits of the summations over the multi-indexes \mathbf{m} , \mathbf{s} are consistent with the order of the summations themselves. Thus, the translation rule of the coefficients of the local expansions from higher to lower levels is

$$\mathbf{b}_{\mathbf{m},\ell,\tilde{c}} = \sum_{\mathbf{s}=\mathbf{m}}^p \mathbf{b}_{\mathbf{s},\ell-1,k} \binom{\mathbf{s}}{\mathbf{m}} \left(\frac{\mathbf{h}_\ell^{(c)}}{2} \right)^{\mathbf{s}-\mathbf{m}} . \tag{193}$$

5.3 Kernel derivatives

Lindsay and Krasny (2001) described a recurrence relation for the computation of the spatial derivatives of the kernel $\mathbf{K}_\delta(\mathbf{x},\mathbf{y})$ needed for the Taylor series appearing in the Fast Multipole Method for vortex particle simulations. The regularised Rosenhead–Moore kernel \mathbf{K}_δ is the gradient of the Plummer potential,

$$\phi_\delta(\mathbf{x},\mathbf{y}) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{1}{(|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|^2 + \delta^2)^{1/2}} = \frac{1}{4\pi R} , \tag{194}$$

being $R = (|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}|^2 + \delta^2)^{1/2}$. The derivatives of R^2 w.r.t. the i -th coordinate of \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} read

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} R^2(\mathbf{x},\mathbf{y}) &= 2R \frac{\partial R}{\partial x_i} = 2(x_i - y_i) \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial y_i} R^2(\mathbf{x},\mathbf{y}) &= 2R \frac{\partial R}{\partial y_i} = -2(x_i - y_i) ,
\end{aligned} \tag{195}$$

so that the derivatives $\partial R/\partial x_i$ and $\partial R/\partial y_i$ read

$$\frac{\partial R}{\partial x_i}(\mathbf{x},\mathbf{y}) = \frac{x_i - y_i}{R} , \quad \frac{\partial R}{\partial y_i}(\mathbf{x},\mathbf{y}) = -\frac{x_i - y_i}{R} . \tag{196}$$

The derivatives of the Plummer potential then become

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \phi_\delta(\mathbf{x},\mathbf{y}) &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{1}{4\pi R} = -\frac{1}{4\pi R^2} \frac{\partial R}{\partial x_i} = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{x_i - y_i}{R^3} \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial y_i} \phi_\delta(\mathbf{x},\mathbf{y}) &= \frac{\partial}{\partial y_i} \frac{1}{4\pi R} = -\frac{1}{4\pi R^2} \frac{\partial R}{\partial y_i} = \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{x_i - y_i}{R^3} .
\end{aligned} \tag{197}$$

Thus, the Rosenhead–Moore kernel can be written as the gradient of the Plummer potential as

$$\mathbf{K}_\delta(\mathbf{x},\mathbf{y}) = \nabla_{\mathbf{x}} \phi_\delta(\mathbf{x},\mathbf{y}) = -\nabla_{\mathbf{y}} \phi_\delta(\mathbf{x},\mathbf{y}) , \quad K_i = \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x_i} = -\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y_i} . \tag{198}$$

5.3.1 Taylor series of the Plummer potential, the Rosenhead kernel and its gradient.

The gradient of the Rosenhead kernel is the second-order tensor defined as

$$\mathbb{G}_\delta(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \nabla_{\mathbf{y}} \mathbf{K}_\delta(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = -\nabla_{\mathbf{y}} \mathbf{K}_\delta(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \quad , \quad G_{ij} = \frac{\partial K_i}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{\partial K_i}{\partial y_j} . \quad (199)$$

It is possible to expand the Plummer potential, the Rosenhead kernel and its gradient around $(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}^*)$ as Taylor series w.r.t. the argument \mathbf{y} as

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}) &= \sum_{|\mathbf{k}|=0}^{\infty} b_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}^*) (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}^*)^{\mathbf{k}} \\ \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}) &= \sum_{|\mathbf{k}|=0}^{\infty} \mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}^*) (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}^*)^{\mathbf{k}} \quad , \quad -\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y_i} = K_i = \sum_{|\mathbf{k}|=0}^{\infty} \{\mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{k}}\}_i (\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}^*) (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}^*)^{\mathbf{k}} \\ \mathbb{G}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}) &= \sum_{|\mathbf{k}|=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}^*) (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}^*)^{\mathbf{k}} \quad , \quad -\frac{\partial K_i}{\partial y_j} = G_{ij} = \sum_{|\mathbf{k}|=0}^{\infty} \{\mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{k}}\}_{ij} (\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}^*) (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}^*)^{\mathbf{k}} \end{aligned} \quad (200)$$

where the coefficients

$$\begin{aligned} b_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) &= \frac{1}{\mathbf{k}!} D_{\mathbf{y}}^{\mathbf{k}} \phi_\delta(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \\ \mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) &= \frac{1}{\mathbf{k}!} D_{\mathbf{y}}^{\mathbf{k}} \mathbf{K}_\delta(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \quad , \quad \{\mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{k}}\}_i(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \frac{1}{\mathbf{k}!} D_{\mathbf{y}}^{\mathbf{k}} \{\mathbf{K}_\delta\}_i(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \\ \mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) &= \frac{1}{\mathbf{k}!} D_{\mathbf{y}}^{\mathbf{k}} \mathbb{G}_\delta(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \quad , \quad \{\mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{k}}\}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \frac{1}{\mathbf{k}!} D_{\mathbf{y}}^{\mathbf{k}} \{\mathbb{G}_\delta\}_{ij}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \end{aligned} \quad (201)$$

are the \mathbf{k} -th coefficients of the Taylor expansion of the Plummer potential, the Rosenhead–Moore kernel and its gradient, respectively. From (198) it easily follows that

$$\mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{k}} = -\sum_{i=1}^d (k_i + 1) b_{\mathbf{k} + \hat{\mathbf{e}}_i} \hat{\mathbf{e}}_i \quad , \quad \{\mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{k}}\}_i = -(k_i + 1) \{b_{\mathbf{k} + \hat{\mathbf{e}}_i}\} \quad , \quad (202)$$

where d is the space dimension and $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_i$ is the i -th unit vector of a Cartesian basis. Similarly, from (199) it easily follows that

$$\mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{k}} = -\sum_{j=1}^d (k_j + 1) \mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{k} + \hat{\mathbf{e}}_j} \otimes \hat{\mathbf{e}}_j \quad , \quad \{\mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{k}}\}_{ij} = -(k_j + 1) \{\mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{k} + \hat{\mathbf{e}}_j}\}_i \quad . \quad (203)$$

Proof: from potential to kernel. The derivative of the Plummer potential w.r.t. the i -th component of the first argument is $\partial \phi / \partial y_i = -\{\mathbf{K}_\delta\}_i$. Taking the derivatives of the

Taylor series, the following relation holds

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial \phi_\delta}{\partial y_i}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}) &= \frac{\partial}{\partial y_i} \sum_{|\mathbf{k}|=0}^{\infty} b_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}^*) (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}^*)^{\mathbf{k}} = \\
&= \sum_{|\mathbf{k}|=0}^{\infty} k_i b_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}^*) (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}^*)^{\mathbf{k} - \hat{\mathbf{e}}_i} = \\
&= \sum_{|\mathbf{k}|=0}^{\infty} (k_i + 1) b_{\mathbf{k} + \hat{\mathbf{e}}_i}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}^*) (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}^*)^{\mathbf{k}} = \\
&= - \sum_{|\mathbf{k}|=0}^{\infty} \{\mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}^*)\}_i (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}^*)^{\mathbf{k}} = \\
&= - \{\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y})\}_i ,
\end{aligned} \tag{204}$$

so that i -th component of the desired formula is obtained,

$$\{\mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}^*)\}_i = -(k_i + 1) b_{\mathbf{k} + \hat{\mathbf{e}}_i}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}^*) , \tag{205}$$

and thus

$$\mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}^*) = - \sum_{i=1}^3 (k_i + 1) b_{\mathbf{k} + \hat{\mathbf{e}}_i}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}^*) \hat{\mathbf{e}}_i . \tag{206}$$

□

Proof: from kernel to gradient. Since $\partial K_i / \partial y_j = -C_{ij}$, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial K_i}{\partial y_j}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}) &= \frac{\partial}{\partial y_j} \sum_{|\mathbf{k}|=0}^{\infty} \{\mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}^*)\}_i (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}^*)^{\mathbf{k}} = \\
&= \sum_{|\mathbf{k}|=0}^{\infty} k_j \{\mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}^*)\}_i (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}^*)^{\mathbf{k} - \hat{\mathbf{e}}_j} = \\
&= \sum_{|\mathbf{k}|=0}^{\infty} (k_j + 1) \{\mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{k} + \hat{\mathbf{e}}_j}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}^*)\}_i (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}^*)^{\mathbf{k}} = \\
&= - \sum_{|\mathbf{k}|=0}^{\infty} \{\mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}^*)\}_{ij} (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{y}^*)^{\mathbf{k}} = \\
&= - \{\mathbb{G}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y})\}_{ij} ,
\end{aligned} \tag{207}$$

so that the desired formula is obtained,

$$\{\mathbb{C}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}^*)\}_{ij} = -(k_j + 1) \{\mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{k} + \hat{\mathbf{e}}_j}(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{y}^*)\}_i . \tag{208}$$

□

5.3.2 Recurrence relation for the Plummer potential

The coefficients $b_{\mathbf{k}}$ of the Plummer potential satisfy the following recurrence relation,

$$|\mathbf{k}|R^2b_{\mathbf{k}} - (2|\mathbf{k}| - 1) \sum_{i=1}^d (x_i - y_i)b_{\mathbf{k}-\hat{e}_i} + (|\mathbf{k}| - 1) \sum_{i=1}^d b_{\mathbf{k}-2\hat{e}_i} \quad , \text{ for } |\mathbf{k}| \geq 1 \quad , \quad (209)$$

where $b_{\mathbf{0}} = \phi_{\delta}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$ and $b_{\mathbf{k}} = 0$ if any $k_i < 0$.

Proof. The proof for $d = 3$ is divided in the following steps.

- The Plummer potential satisfies the equation

$$R^2 D_{y_1} \phi_{\delta} - (x_1 - y_1) \phi_{\delta} = 0 \quad . \quad (210)$$

Using the expression in (197) for $D_{y_1} \phi_{\delta} := \partial \phi_{\delta} / \partial y_1$, it readily follows,

$$R^2 \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{x_i - y_i}{R^2} - \frac{x_i - y_i}{R} = 0 \quad (211)$$

□

- Applying the operator $D_{y_1}^{k_1-1}$ to the identity (210) and using the Leibniz's rule for the differentiation of a product, leads to

$$R^2 D_{y_1}^{k_1} \phi_{\delta} - (2k_1 - 1)(x_1 - y_1) D_{y_1}^{k_1-1} \phi_{\delta} + (k_1 - 1)^2 D_{y_1}^{k_1-2} \phi_{\delta} = 0 \quad . \quad (212)$$

Indeed,

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= D_{y_1}^{k_1-1} (R^2 D_{y_1} \phi_{\delta} - (x_1 - y_1) \phi_{\delta}) = \\ &= \sum_{s=0}^{k_1-1} \binom{k_1-1}{s} D_{y_1}^{k_1-1-s} R^2 D_{y_1}^s D_{y_1} \phi_{\delta} - \sum_{s=0}^{k_1-1} \binom{k_1-1}{s} D_{y_1}^{k_1-1-s} (x_1 - y_1) D_{y_1}^s D_{y_1} \phi_{\delta} \quad . \end{aligned} \quad (213)$$

Since only the derivatives of R^2 up to the 2-nd order are different from zero

$$D_{y_1}^0 R^2 = R^2 \quad , \quad D_{y_1}^1 R^2 = 2(y_1 - x_1) \quad , \quad D_{y_1}^2 R^2 = 2 \quad , \quad (214)$$

and only the derivatives up to the 1-st order of $(x_i - y_i)$ are different from zero

$$D_{y_1}^0 (x_1 - y_1) = x_1 - y_1 \quad , \quad D_{y_1}^1 (x_1 - y_1) = -1 \quad , \quad (215)$$

only few terms are different from zero in equation (213). The terms with $s = k_1 - 3 : k_1 - 1$ are different from zero in the first summation, while the terms with $s = k_1 - 2 : k_1 - 1$ are different from zero in the second summation, so that

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \binom{k_1-1}{k_1-3} D_{y_1}^2 R^2 D_{y_1}^{k_1-2} \phi_{\delta} + \binom{k_1-1}{k_1-2} D_{y_1}^1 R^2 D_{y_1}^{k_1-1} \phi_{\delta} + \binom{k_1-1}{k_1-1} D_{y_1}^0 R^2 D_{y_1}^{k_1} \phi_{\delta} + \\ &\quad - \binom{k_1-1}{k_1-2} D_{y_1}^1 (x_1 - y_1) D_{y_1}^{k_1-1} \phi_{\delta} - \binom{k_1-1}{k_1-1} D_{y_1}^0 (x_1 - y_1) D_{y_1}^{k_1} \phi_{\delta} = \\ &= \frac{(k_1-1)(k_1-2)}{2} 2 D_{y_1}^{k_1-2} \phi_{\delta} + (k_1-1) 2 (y_1 - x_1) D_{y_1}^{k_1-1} \phi_{\delta} + R^2 D_{y_1}^{k_1} \phi_{\delta} + \\ &\quad - (k_1-1)(-1) D_{y_1}^{k_1-2} \phi_{\delta} - 1 (x_1 - y_1) D_{y_1}^{k_1-1} \phi_{\delta} = \\ &= R^2 D_{y_1}^{k_1} \phi_{\delta} - (2k_1 - 1)(x_1 - y_1) D_{y_1}^{k_1-1} \phi_{\delta} + (k_1 - 1)^2 D_{y_1}^{k_1-2} \phi_{\delta} \quad . \end{aligned} \quad (216)$$

□

- Applying the operator $D_{y_2}^{k_2} D_{y_3}^{k_3}$ to equation (212) leads to

$$k_1 R^2 b_{\mathbf{k}} - 2k_1 \sum_{i=1}^d (x_i - y_i) b_{\mathbf{k} - \hat{e}_i} + k_1 \sum_i i = 1^d b_{\mathbf{k} - 2\hat{e}_i} + (x_i - y_i) b_{\mathbf{k} - \hat{e}_i} - b_{\mathbf{k} - 2\hat{e}_1} = 0. \quad (217)$$

Since only the Plummer potential is a function of y_2 in the second and the third terms of equation (212) are independent from y_2 , applying $D_{y_2}^{k_2}$ gives

$$R^2 D_{y_2}^{k_2} D_{y_1}^{k_1} \phi_\delta + 2k_2 (y_2 - x_2) D_{y_2}^{k_2-1} D_{y_1}^{k_1} \phi_\delta + k_2 (k_2 - 1) D_{y_2}^{k_2-2} D_{y_1}^{k_1} \phi_\delta + \\ - (2k_1 - 1)(x_1 - y_1) D_{y_2}^{k_2} D_{y_1}^{k_1-1} \phi_\delta + (k_1 - 1)^2 D_{y_2}^{k_2} D_{y_1}^{k_1-2} \phi_\delta = 0, \quad (218)$$

where the Leibniz's rule and the expression of the partial derivatives $\partial R^2 / \partial y_2 = 2(y_2 - x_2)$, $\partial^2 R^2 / \partial y_2^2 = 2$ have been used to manipulate $D_{y_2}^{k_2} (R^2 D_{y_2}^{k_2} D_{y_1}^{k_1} \phi_\delta)$. Leibniz's rule is applied when the operator $D_{y_3}^{k_3}$ is applied to the first term of the last equation to obtain

$$R^2 D_{y_3}^{k_3} D_{y_2}^{k_2} D_{y_1}^{k_1} \phi_\delta + 2k_3 (y_3 - x_3) D_{y_3}^{k_3-1} D_{y_2}^{k_2} D_{y_1}^{k_1} \phi_\delta + k_3 (k_3 - 1) D_{y_3}^{k_3-2} D_{y_2}^{k_2} D_{y_1}^{k_1} \phi_\delta + \\ + 2k_2 (y_2 - x_2) D_{y_3}^{k_3} D_{y_2}^{k_2-1} D_{y_1}^{k_1} \phi_\delta + k_2 (k_2 - 1) D_{y_3}^{k_3} D_{y_2}^{k_2-2} D_{y_1}^{k_1} \phi_\delta + \\ - (2k_1 - 1)(x_1 - y_1) D_{y_3}^{k_3} D_{y_2}^{k_2} D_{y_1}^{k_1-1} \phi_\delta + (k_1 - 1)^2 D_{y_3}^{k_3} D_{y_2}^{k_2} D_{y_1}^{k_1-2} \phi_\delta = 0. \quad (219)$$

The terms in the last expression, divided by $\mathbf{k}!$, can be sorted as

$$R^2 \frac{D_{\mathbf{y}}^{\mathbf{k}} \phi_\delta}{\mathbf{k}!} - 2 \sum_{i=1}^3 k_i (x_i - y_i) \frac{D_{\mathbf{y}}^{\mathbf{k} - \hat{e}_i} \phi_\delta}{\mathbf{k}!} + \sum_{i=1}^3 k_i (k_i - 1) \frac{D_{\mathbf{y}}^{\mathbf{k} - 2\hat{e}_i} \phi_\delta}{\mathbf{k}!} + \\ + (x_1 - y_1) \frac{D_{\mathbf{y}}^{\mathbf{k} - \hat{e}_1} \phi_\delta}{\mathbf{k}!} - (k_1 - 1) \frac{D_{\mathbf{y}}^{\mathbf{k} - 2\hat{e}_1} \phi_\delta}{\mathbf{k}!} = 0. \quad (220)$$

Using the definition of the Taylor coefficients $b_{\mathbf{k}}$, the last expression becomes

$$R^2 b_{\mathbf{k}} - 2 \sum_{i=1}^3 (x_i - y_i) b_{\mathbf{k} - \hat{e}_i} + \sum_{i=1}^3 b_{\mathbf{k} - 2\hat{e}_i} + (x_1 - y_1) \frac{b_{\mathbf{k} - \hat{e}_1}}{k_1} - \frac{b_{\mathbf{k} - 2\hat{e}_1}}{k_1} = 0. \quad (221)$$

While this relation is focused on the index 1, similar equations can be obtained for indexes 2 and 3. The desired symmetric form is obtained summing these three equations (multiplied by the respective k_i),

$$|\mathbf{k}| R^2 b_{\mathbf{k}} - (2|\mathbf{k}| - 1) \sum_{i=1}^3 (x_i - y_i) b_{\mathbf{k} - \hat{e}_i} + (|\mathbf{k}| - 1) \sum_{i=1}^3 b_{\mathbf{k} - 2\hat{e}_i} = 0. \quad (222)$$

□

5.4 DUST implementation

In this section the actual implementation of the cartesian FMM is detailed. The description will follow the actual order of the operations performed in DUST.

5.4.1 Octree

First the octree is built. The octree is based upon one or more square blocks which should contain all the vortex particles during the computations. Then each cube block is divided into 8 cubes of half the size of the original block. And these are again divided into 8 smaller cubes in order to generate a prescribed number of layers n_l in which each subsequent layer is made by the subdivision of the previous one into cubic elements of half the size. Note that the layers are generally numbered from 1, the biggest one composed by the original block, to n_l which is the last with the smallest cells, however the term *higher* layer will be employed to refer to one with bigger cells (thus a smaller number) and *lower* layer will be used to refer to one with smaller cells and higher number. Each cell k in the layer l is assigned three cartesian indices $\mathbf{i}_{k,l}$ which denotes its position in the structured layer of cells.

Hereafter the relationships between the cells are established. Each cell in the layer l , except the ones in the first original layer, has a parent cell $P_{k,l}$ in the higher layer $l - 1$, and each cell except the ones in the smaller last layer n_l has eight children cells, indicated by the set $C_{k,l}$ generated by its subdivision in the layer $l + 1$. Then the neighbours are identified: given a cell k in layer l all the cells in the same layer that touch the cell even with a vertex, i.e. which have all the components of the cartesian index \mathbf{i}_l different no more than ± 1 from the k cell indices $\mathbf{i}_{k,l}$, are considered neighbours of the cell, denoted by $N_{k,l}$. All the interactions between each cell and its neighbours will be computed directly without employing the fast multipole expansion. Finally the interaction list $I_{k,l}$ is generated: the fast multipole interactions are computed, for each cell, only with the cells in the interaction list, since the contribution of cells which are farther away was already accounted for in the interactions of the parent cell which is inherited from each cell. The cells in the interaction list of the cell k in the layer l are all the cells that are child of the neighbour of

$$I_{k,l} = \{x \mid \forall y \in N_{P_{k,l},l-1}, x \in C_{y,l-1} \wedge x \notin N_{k,l}\} \quad (223)$$

5.4.2 Sorting

At each timestep before computing the multipole expansion it is necessary to sort all the particles and set the status of each cell. All the particles are sorted at the lowest level $l = n_l$, then each higher level inherits the particles of the children, in order to have a reference, at all cells k at each level l of which particles are contained in the volume of the cell.

Cells are then set as leaf cells, $k \in L$, branch cells, $k \in B$ or inactive cells, $k \in X$. Leaf cells are the ones in which close range interactions are computed, branch cells are the ones from which the leaves inherit the long range contributions and inactive cells are the ones which do not contain enough particles to be used to compute the multipole expansion. At the lowest levels if the cells contain enough particles ($npart_{k,l} \geq npart_{min}$) the cell is marked as leaf. Then from the lowest level, all higher levels $l > n_l$ are considered hierarchically, and in each cell k all the children $C_{k,l}$ are analysed. If at least one of the children is either a leaf or a branch, the current cell k is marked as branch, and all the other children which are not leaves nor branches are set as leaves. If none of the children are leaves nor branches, all the children are set as inactive, and the current cell is checked

to decide if it is a leaf.

5.4.3 Multipole expansions

The first step of the multipole procedure is to compute the multipole expansion of the particles inside each leaf cell

$$\forall k,l \in L \quad a_{k,l}(:, \mathbf{m}) = \sum_{p \in k} \alpha_p (\mathbf{r}_p - \mathbf{c}_{k,l})^{\mathbf{m}}, \quad (224)$$

where α_p and \mathbf{r}_p is the intensity and position of the particle p , $\mathbf{c}_{k,l}$ is the centre of the cell and \mathbf{m} is the multi-index of the degree of the multipole expansion.

The coefficient of the expansion a appears in a mixed notation, with the subscript indicating the cell at which belongs, but in the brackets it is not indicated the functional dependence but rather the array-like reference in a pseudo-code way, similar to Fortran or Matlab syntax. This is to better keep track of the different indices and dimensions involved, and will be used throughout this section.

5.4.4 Multipole to multipole

After the multipole coefficients have been computed in all the leaves, the coefficients are computed in all the branch cells inheriting the contributions from their children

$$\forall k,l \in B \quad a_{k,l}(:, \mathbf{m}) = \sum_{c \in C_{k,l}} \sum_{s=0}^{\mathbf{m}} \binom{\mathbf{m}}{\mathbf{s}} (\mathbf{c}_c - \mathbf{c}_{k,l})^{\mathbf{m}-\mathbf{s}} a_c(:, \mathbf{s}). \quad (225)$$

By operating from level $l = n_l - 1$ and computing the multipole to local in all the cells which are branches, all the cells should have the correct multipole coefficients a .

5.4.5 Kernel Derivatives

The derivatives of the kernel are used to compute the transfer from multipole to local expansions in each cell. Since they depend only on the relative distance between the interacting cells, and since the extension of the interaction list is limited and known, at each level the kernel derivatives are computed just once at the beginning of the simulation. The kernel derivative for the velocity is

$$Dk_{(i_{k,l}-i_{j,l})}(i, \mathbf{m}) = -(1 + m_i) bk_{(i_{k,l}-i_{j,l})}(\mathbf{m} + \mathbf{e}_i) \quad (226)$$

where i is the direction of the derivative, m_i is the component in the i direction of the multi index \mathbf{m} and \mathbf{e}_i is the unit vector in the direction i , i.e. zero in each component except for the i one in which is 1. The coefficient bk is defined recursively as

$$bk_{(i_{k,l}-i_{j,l})}(\mathbf{m}) = \frac{1}{R^2 |\mathbf{m}|} \left\{ (2|\mathbf{m}| - 1) \sum_{i=1}^3 (r_{k,i} - r_{j,i}) bk_{(i_{k,l}-i_{j,l})}(\mathbf{m} - \mathbf{e}_i) - (|\mathbf{m}| - 1) \sum_{i=1}^3 bk_{(i_{k,l}-i_{j,l})}(\mathbf{m} - 2\mathbf{e}_i) \right\} \quad (227)$$

with

$$bk(\mathbf{0}) = \frac{1}{4\pi R^2} \quad (228)$$

and where the regularized radius of the Rosenhead-Moore kernel is defined as $R^2 = (r_{k,i} - r_{j,i})^2 + \delta^2$ with δ as the regularization radius.

The derivative of the kernel for the gradient is obtained from the derivative of the kernel for the velocity

$$Dc_{(i_{k,l}-i_{j,l})}(:, i, \mathbf{m}) = -(1 + m_i)Dk_{(i_{k,l}-i_{j,l})}(i, \mathbf{m} + \mathbf{e}_i) \quad (229)$$

5.4.6 Multipole to local

After the multipole expansion was computed in each cell, it is necessary to compute the local expansions for the velocity and the gradient of the velocity, employing the pre computed derivatives of the kernel to interact with the cells in the interaction list, in all the active cells,

$$\forall k, l \notin X \quad b_{k,l}(:, \mathbf{m}) = \sum_{q \in I_{k,l}} \sum_{\mathbf{n}=0}^P (-1)^{|\mathbf{m}|} \frac{(\mathbf{m} + \mathbf{n})!}{\mathbf{m}!\mathbf{n}!} [Dk_{(i_{k,l}-i_q)}(:, \mathbf{m} + \mathbf{n}) \times a_q(:, \mathbf{n})] \quad (230)$$

$$\forall k, l \notin X \quad \forall i \in \{1,2,3\}$$

$$c_{k,l}(i, :, \mathbf{m}) = \sum_{q \in I_{k,l}} \sum_{\mathbf{n}=0}^P (-1)^{|\mathbf{m}|} \frac{(\mathbf{m} + \mathbf{n})!}{\mathbf{m}!\mathbf{n}!} [Dc_{(i_{k,l}-i_q)}(i, :, \mathbf{m} + \mathbf{n}) \times a_q(:, \mathbf{n})] \quad (231)$$

5.4.7 Local to local

In the dual way with respect to the multipole to multipole procedure, the contribution of the local expansion is inherited by the children from their parent cells

$$\forall k, \quad \forall l > 1 \quad b_{k,l}(:, \mathbf{m}) = b_{k,l}(:, \mathbf{m}) + \sum_{\mathbf{s}=\mathbf{m}}^P b_{P_{k,l}}(:, \mathbf{s}) \binom{\mathbf{s}}{\mathbf{m}} (c_{k,l} - c_{P_{k,l}})^{\mathbf{s}-\mathbf{m}} \quad (232)$$

$$\forall k, \quad \forall l > 1 \quad c_{k,l}(:, \mathbf{m}) = c_{k,l}(:, \mathbf{m}) + \sum_{\mathbf{s}=\mathbf{m}}^P c_{P_{k,l}}(:, \mathbf{s}) \binom{\mathbf{s}}{\mathbf{m}} (c_{k,l} - c_{P_{k,l}})^{\mathbf{s}-\mathbf{m}} \quad (233)$$

Starting from level $l = 2$ downwards the local to local allows to arrive to all the leaves bringing the contributions of the whole octree except for the immediate neighbours.

5.4.8 Application

Once all the coefficients of the local expansion b and c have been computed and inherited in all the leaves, it is possible to apply the local expansion to each particle in each leaf. The velocity contribution due to the fast multipole on the particle p is

$$\forall k, l \in L, \quad \forall p \in k, l \quad v_p(\cdot) = \sum_{\mathbf{m}=0}^P b(:, \mathbf{m})(\mathbf{r}_p - c_{k,l})^{\mathbf{m}}, \quad (234)$$

while the gradient contribution is

$$\forall k, l \in L, \quad \forall p \in k, l \quad Gv_p(\cdot) = \sum_{\mathbf{m}=0}^P c(\cdot, \cdot, \mathbf{m})(\mathbf{r}_p - \mathbf{c}_{k,l})^{\mathbf{m}}. \quad (235)$$

6 Loads

The loads acting on the components are computed differently according to the type of elements considered.

Loads acting on lifting lines comes automatically from the lookup tables employed to solve their intensity.

Loads acting on the vortex lattices rely on an unsteady formulation of the Kutta–Joukowski theorem.

The loads acting on three dimensional surface panels are evaluated using the Bernoulli polynomial, taking into account the vorticity of the flow.

6.1 Bernoulli equation

Using the Eulerian description of the system, the unsteady Bernoulli theorem for an irrotational flow of an incompressible fluid with constant density ρ , without any volume force states

$$\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial t} + \frac{|\mathbf{U}|^2}{2} + \frac{P}{\rho} = C(t) , \quad (236)$$

where ϕ is the kinetic potential, $\mathbf{U} = \nabla\phi$ the velocity field and P the pressure field. The kinetic potential and velocity fields can be decomposed as the sum of the free-stream and perturbation contributions as

$$\begin{aligned} \phi &= \phi_\infty + \varphi \quad , \quad \nabla\phi = \mathbf{U} = \mathbf{U}_\infty + \mathbf{u} \\ &= \nabla\phi_\infty + \nabla\varphi , \end{aligned} \quad (237)$$

so that $\phi_\infty = \mathbf{U}_\infty \cdot \mathbf{r}$, being \mathbf{r} the space variable.

In a panel method, it may be useful to write equations with an ‘‘ALE’’ description to compute loads on a moving body by means of the Bernoulli equation. This approach has the advantage of using the spatial derivatives computed with the surface grid of the body and the temporal derivatives for given material points of the solid surface. By means of differentiation of composite functions, the time derivative of a physical quantity for a material point \mathbf{r}_b (of the solid component) moving with velocity $\mathbf{u}_b = \left. \frac{\partial\mathbf{x}}{\partial t} \right|_{\mathbf{r}_b}$ is expressed as

$$\left. \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \right|_{\mathbf{r}_b} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u}_b \cdot \nabla . \quad (238)$$

Thus, the ‘‘ALE’’ description of the Bernoulli theorem (236) reads

$$\left. \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial t} \right|_{\mathbf{r}_b} - \mathbf{u}_b \cdot \nabla\phi + \frac{|\mathbf{U}|^2}{2} + \frac{P}{\rho} = C(t) . \quad (239)$$

Using the decomposition (237) and the free-stream condition as a reference, Bernoulli equation (239) becomes

$$\left. \frac{\partial(\phi_\infty + \varphi)}{\partial t} \right|_{\mathbf{r}_b} - \mathbf{u}_b \cdot \nabla(\phi_\infty + \varphi) + \frac{|\mathbf{U}|^2}{2} + \frac{P}{\rho} = \left. \frac{\partial\phi_\infty}{\partial t} \right|_{\mathbf{r}_b} - \mathbf{u}_b \cdot \nabla\phi_\infty + \frac{|\mathbf{U}_\infty|^2}{2} + \frac{P_\infty}{\rho} , \quad (240)$$

and thus

$$P = P_\infty + \rho \frac{|\mathbf{U}_\infty|^2}{2} - \left(\rho \left. \frac{\partial\varphi}{\partial t} \right|_{\mathbf{r}_b} - \mathbf{u}_b \cdot \nabla\varphi + \rho \frac{|\mathbf{U}|^2}{2} \right) . \quad (241)$$

6.2 Integral equation for Bernoulli polynomial - Uhlman's equation

Bernoulli theorems don't hold for rotational flows of viscous fluids. Even though the Bernoulli polynomial is not constant throughout the domain, it is possible to compute its value by means of an boundary integral equation. The Navier–Stokes' equations,

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{U} - \nu \nabla^2 \mathbf{U} + \frac{1}{\rho} \nabla P = \mathbf{0} \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{U} = 0, \end{cases} \quad (242)$$

can be manipulated to obtain the following alternative formulation,

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \nabla \frac{|\mathbf{U}|^2}{2} + \boldsymbol{\omega} \times \mathbf{U} - \nu \nabla^2 \mathbf{U} + \frac{1}{\rho} \nabla P = \mathbf{0} \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{U} = 0. \end{cases} \quad (243)$$

The Bernoulli polynomial $B := \frac{|\mathbf{U}|^2}{2} + \frac{P}{\rho}$ appears in the last form of the Navier–Stokes' equations. The gradient of the Bernoulli polynomial reads

$$\nabla B = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} - \boldsymbol{\omega} \times \mathbf{U} + \nu \nabla^2 \mathbf{U}. \quad (244)$$

Taking the divergence of ∇B and using the incompressibility constraint $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{U}$, the Laplacian of the Bernoulli polynomial reads

$$\nabla^2 B = -\nabla \cdot (\boldsymbol{\omega} \times \mathbf{U}). \quad (245)$$

Once the velocity field is known, it is possible to compute the value of the Bernoulli polynomial throughout the domain if the boundary conditions are supplied for the Poisson's equation for B . At the free far-field, it is possible to assume that the Bernoulli polynomial is constant and equal to the free-stream value

$$B|_{S_\infty} = B_\infty. \quad (246)$$

On solid bodies, it is possible to use the expression of ∇B to assign the natural boundary conditions,

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \nabla B \Big|_{S_b} = \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \left[-\frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} - \boldsymbol{\omega} \times \mathbf{U} + \nu \nabla^2 \mathbf{U} \right] \Big|_{S_b}. \quad (247)$$

The problem to be solved is then,

$$\begin{cases} -\nabla^2 B = \nabla \cdot (\boldsymbol{\omega} \times \mathbf{U}) & , \quad \text{in } \Omega \\ B|_{S_\infty} = B_\infty \\ \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \nabla B \Big|_{S_b} = \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \left[-\frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} - \boldsymbol{\omega} \times \mathbf{U} + \nu \nabla^2 \mathbf{U} \right] \Big|_{S_b}. \end{cases} \quad (248)$$

The Green's function method is used to obtain an integral boundary equation from the differential problem. The Green's function $G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0)$ of the Poisson problem is the same

as the Green's function of the Laplace problem used for the kinetic potential equation, solving the equation

$$-\nabla^2 G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) = \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0) .$$

$$\begin{aligned}
E(\mathbf{r}_0)B(\mathbf{r}_0) &= \int_V \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0) B(\mathbf{r}, t) = \\
&= - \int_V \nabla^2 G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) B(\mathbf{r}, t) = \\
&= - \int_V \nabla \cdot [B(\mathbf{r}, t) \nabla G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) - G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) \nabla B(\mathbf{r}, t)] - \int_V \nabla^2 B(\mathbf{r}) G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) = \\
&= - \oint_{\partial V} \tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \nabla G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) B(\mathbf{r}, t) + \oint_{\partial V} G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) \tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \nabla B(\mathbf{r}, t) + \\
&\quad + \int_V \nabla \cdot (\boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r}, t) \times \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{r}, t)) G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) ,
\end{aligned} \tag{249}$$

where the differential and the integral operators act on the spatial coordinates \mathbf{r} , and $\tilde{\mathbf{n}}$ is the unit normal vector pointing outward the fluid volume V . On the body surface, the unit vector pointing outward the body is equal to $\hat{\mathbf{n}} = -\tilde{\mathbf{n}}$. The boundary of the domain is composed of the union of the body surfaces S_b and the surface at far field S_∞ , $\partial V = S_b \cup S_\infty$. The surface integrals are written as the sum of the contributions of the body and the far field surfaces. The first term in the right hand side of eq.(249) becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
- \oint_{\partial V} \tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \nabla G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) B(\mathbf{r}, t) &= \\
&= - \oint_{S_b} \tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \nabla G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) B(\mathbf{r}, t) - \oint_{S_\infty} \tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \nabla G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) B(\mathbf{r}, t) .
\end{aligned} \tag{250}$$

The body surface contribution contains the unknown field on the body and thus it is moved to the left hand side. Dirichlet boundary conditions at the far field imply that the Bernoulli polynomial is constant on the far fields surface, $B|_{S_\infty} = B_\infty$. The far field contribution is manipulated to obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
- \oint_{S_\infty} \tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \nabla G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) B(\mathbf{r}, t) &= - \oint_{S_\infty} \tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \nabla G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) B_\infty = \\
&= \frac{1}{4\pi} \oint_{S_\infty} \tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \frac{\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0|^3} B_\infty = B_\infty ,
\end{aligned} \tag{251}$$

for any point \mathbf{r}_0 located in the interior of the far field surface S_∞ .² The third term of the equation can be integrated by parts so that eq. (249) becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
E(\mathbf{r}_0)B(\mathbf{r}_0, t) + \oint_{S_b} \tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \nabla G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) B(\mathbf{r}, t) &= \\
= B_\infty + \oint_{\partial V} G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) \tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \nabla B(\mathbf{r}, t) + \\
+ \oint_{\partial V} G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) \tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r}, t) \times \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{r}, t) - \int_V \nabla G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r}, t) \times \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{r}, t) .
\end{aligned} \tag{253}$$

Introducing the value of the gradient of the Bernoulli polynomial ∇B , equation (253) becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
E(\mathbf{r}_0)B(\mathbf{r}_0, t) + \oint_{S_b} \tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \nabla G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) B(\mathbf{r}, t) &= \\
= B_\infty + \\
+ \oint_{\partial V} G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) \tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \left[-\frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t}(\mathbf{r}, t) - \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r}, t) \times \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{r}, t) + \nu \nabla^2 \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{r}, t) \right] + \\
+ \oint_{\partial V} G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) \tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r}, t) \times \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{r}, t) - \int_V \nabla G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r}, t) \times \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{r}, t) ,
\end{aligned} \tag{254}$$

so that the boundary integral equation for the Bernoulli polynomial becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
E(\mathbf{r}_0)B(\mathbf{r}_0, t) + \oint_{S_b} \tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \nabla G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) B(\mathbf{r}, t) &= \\
= B_\infty + \oint_{\partial V} G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) \tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \left[-\frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t}(\mathbf{r}, t) + \nu \nabla^2 \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{r}, t) \right] \\
- \int_V \nabla G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r}, t) \times \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{r}, t) ,
\end{aligned} \tag{255}$$

Since the partial derivative is not well-defined for moving bodies, it is written in terms of the time derivative on the body,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Big|_{\mathbf{x}_b} - (\mathbf{U}_b \cdot \nabla) \text{ .} \tag{256}$$

²The integral is equivalent to the solid angle of the (closed) far field surface as seen from its interior,

$$\oint_{S_\infty} \tilde{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \frac{\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0|^3} = 4\pi . \tag{252}$$

and the integral equation is recast as

$$\begin{aligned}
E(\mathbf{r}_0)B(\mathbf{r}_0, t) - \oint_{S_b} \hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \nabla G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) B(\mathbf{r}, t) = & \\
= B_\infty + & \text{free stream} \\
+ \oint_{\partial V} G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) \hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} \Big|_{\mathbf{x}_b}(\mathbf{r}, t) - (\mathbf{U}_b(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{r}, t) \right] + & \text{time-dependent} \\
- \int_V \nabla G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega}(\mathbf{r}, t) \times \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{r}, t) + & \text{rotational} \\
- \nu \oint_{\partial V} G(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0) \hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \nabla^2 \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{r}, t) , & \text{viscous}
\end{aligned} \tag{257}$$

where the four terms on the right hand side respectively represent (1) the free stream conditions, (2) the effects of an unsteady flow, including moving bodies, (3) the rotational effects and (4) the viscous effects on the value of the Bernoulli polynomial.

7 Irrotational part of the velocity field

A complex configuration may be composed of several components. Two main types of component exist for representing either thick bodies or zero-thickness surfaces. Different aerodynamic elements and conditions to be satisfied are associated with different components types:

- thick components
 - composed of 3Dp elements;
 - Dirichlet condition, written in terms of the velocity potential φ (Morino-like formulation).
- zero-thickness surface
 - composed of VR elements
 - Neumann condition, written in terms of the boundary value of $\partial\varphi/\partial n = \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_\varphi$.

First Dirichlet and Neumann problems are formulated for thick bodies and zero-thickness surfaces, respectively. Then the mixed formulation for a complex configuration is introduced. Eventually, the treatment of wakes is presented.

7.1 Dirichlet problem: Morino formulation

The irrotational part \mathbf{u}_φ of the velocity field of an incompressible fluid, i.e. with $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{U} = 0$, is governed by Laplace equation for the velocity potential φ , already introduced in (??),

$$\nabla^2 \varphi(\mathbf{r}, t) = 0 \quad , \quad \mathbf{r} \in V \quad (258)$$

supplied with conditions on the boundary of the irrotational fluid domain V , i.e. body surfaces, free wakes and far-field. Multiplying this equation by the Green's function $G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0)$ for the Laplace problem³ and integrating over the whole space V , it is possible to obtain the integral equation

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \int_V G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) \nabla^2 \varphi(\mathbf{r}, t) = \\ &= \int_V \nabla \cdot [G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) \nabla \varphi(\mathbf{r}, t) - \varphi(\mathbf{r}, t) \nabla G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0)] + \int_V \nabla^2 G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) \varphi(\mathbf{r}, t) = \\ &= \oint_{\partial V} G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) \nabla \varphi(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{n}} - \oint_{\partial V} \varphi(\mathbf{r}, t) \nabla G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{n}} + \int_V \nabla^2 G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) \varphi(\mathbf{r}, t) , \end{aligned} \quad (260)$$

where **the differential and integral operators act on the variable \mathbf{r}** , while the position \mathbf{r}_0 appears as a parameter. The unit normal vector $\tilde{\mathbf{n}}$ points outward the fluid volume V , in the opposite direction of the unit normal vector $\hat{\mathbf{n}} = -\tilde{\mathbf{n}}$ pointing outward the body. The boundary ∂V of the domain is the union of the surface of the body S_b , the

³The Green's function is obtained as the solution of the problem $-\nabla^2 G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) = \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0)$. Exploiting the homogeneity of the space, the Green's function for the three-dimensional Laplace problem reads

$$G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) = \frac{1}{4\pi|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0|} . \quad (259)$$

“potential” part of the wake S_w ⁴ and the surface at infinity S_∞ . The surface at the infinity has no contribution, because of the asymptotic behavior of the perturbation potential for $r \rightarrow \infty$. Introducing the function $E(\mathbf{r}_0)$

$$E(\mathbf{r}_0) = \begin{cases} 1, & \mathbf{r}_0 \in V \\ 1/2, & \mathbf{r}_0 \in \partial V \\ 0, & \mathbf{r}_0 \notin V \cup \partial V \end{cases} \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \int_V \nabla^2 G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) \varphi(\mathbf{r}) = - \int_V \nabla^2 \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0) \varphi(\mathbf{r}) = -E(\mathbf{r}_0) \varphi(\mathbf{r}_0), \quad (261)$$

equation (260) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} E(\mathbf{r}_0) \varphi(\mathbf{r}_0) = & - \oint_{S_b} G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \nabla \varphi(\mathbf{r}, t) + \oint_{S_b} \varphi(\mathbf{r}, t) \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \nabla G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) + \\ & - \oint_{S_w} G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \nabla \varphi(\mathbf{r}, t) + \oint_{S_w} \varphi(\mathbf{r}, t) \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \nabla G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0). \end{aligned} \quad (262)$$

Defining $\sigma(\mathbf{r}, t) = \hat{\mathbf{n}}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \nabla \varphi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ and introducing the expression of the gradient of the Green’s function⁵, it is possible to identify in the right-hand side of eq. (262) the contributions of surface distributions of sources and doublets with intensity σ and $-\varphi$, respectively (see §7.1.1)

$$E(\mathbf{r}_0) \varphi(\mathbf{r}_0, t) = - \oint_{S_b} \frac{1}{4\pi |\mathbf{r}_0 - \mathbf{r}|} \sigma(\mathbf{r}, t) + \oint_{S_b} \frac{\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot (\mathbf{r}_0 - \mathbf{r})}{4\pi |\mathbf{r}_0 - \mathbf{r}|^3} \varphi(\mathbf{r}, t) + \oint_{S_w} \dots \quad (264)$$

Given the far-field velocity, the motion of the bodies and the rotational part of the velocity field \mathbf{u}_ψ (determined by the rotational part of the wake), the source intensity is known as well. Since \mathbf{u}_ψ is part of the unknown velocity, a **time-stepping** method alternately solving the problem in \mathbf{u}_φ and the problem in \mathbf{u}_ψ , see Section ... will be used: using this strategy, \mathbf{u}_ψ can be considered as a given known field in the problem for \mathbf{u}_φ and vice versa. The actual unknown of the problem is the velocity potential $\varphi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ on the surface of the body S_b , since boundary conditions on the surface of solid bodies define the intensity of the source distribution

$$\sigma = \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \nabla \varphi = \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot (\mathbf{u}_b - \mathbf{U}_\infty - \mathbf{u}_\psi). \quad (265)$$

Introducing two convolution kernels, S and D , it is possible to write eq.(264) in a compact form

$$([E\delta + D] * \varphi)(\mathbf{r}, t) = (S * \sigma)(\mathbf{r}, t) - (D^w * \varphi^w)(\mathbf{r}, t), \quad (266)$$

where D^w is the convolution kernel taking into account the contribution of the “potential” part of the wake. With the Kutta condition, it is possible to write the potential on

⁴The wake will be described with a combination of vortex lattice panels and vortex particles. The former constitute the “potential” part of the wake, since they are solutions of the Laplace equation, the latter constitute the “rotational” part of the wake, whose influence determine the “rotational” part of the velocity field \mathbf{u}_ψ . The See Section ...

⁵The gradient of the Green’s function $G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0)$ w.r.t. the space variable \mathbf{r} represents the potential induced in \mathbf{r}_0 (passive point) by a unit-intensity point doublet located in \mathbf{r} (active point). Its expression reads

$$\nabla G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) = \nabla_{\mathbf{r}} G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) = - \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{\mathbf{r}_0 - \mathbf{r}}{|\mathbf{r}_0 - \mathbf{r}|^3}. \quad (263)$$

the wake as a function of the potential on the body at the current time (“implicit ” contribution) and the previous instants of time (“explicit” contribution). Thus, eq.(266) becomes

$$\left([E\delta + D + D^{Kutta}] * \varphi \right) (\mathbf{r}, t) = (S * \sigma) (\mathbf{r}, t) - (D^{w,past} * \varphi^w) (\mathbf{r}, t) . \quad (267)$$

This integral equation can be solved with a **collocation** method. First, the surface of the body S_b is divided into two-dimensional panels S_k , s.t. $S_b = \cup_{k=1:N} S_k$, equation (264) becomes

$$E(\mathbf{r}_0)\varphi(\mathbf{r}_0, t) = - \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{S_k} \frac{1}{4\pi|\mathbf{r}_0 - \mathbf{r}|} \sigma(\mathbf{r}, t) + \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{S_k} \frac{\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot (\mathbf{r}_0 - \mathbf{r})}{4\pi|\mathbf{r}_0 - \mathbf{r}|^3} \varphi(\mathbf{r}, t) + \int_{S_w} \dots . \quad (268)$$

Then, the problem is recast as a linear system of equations, by evaluating eq.(268) at the collocation points. If the intensity of the singularity distributions is constant on each panel,

$$\varphi(\mathbf{r}, t)|_{S_i} = \varphi_i(t) \quad , \quad \sigma(\mathbf{r}, t)|_{S_i} = \sigma_i(t) \quad (269)$$

a N -dimensional discrete approximation of the continuous fields $\varphi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is obtained, so that N collocation points are required. If the collocation points are defined as the centres of the panels \mathbf{r}_i , where the boundary conditions are evaluated, eq.(268) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} E^{(i)}\varphi_i &= \sum_{k=1}^N \left[- \int_{S_k} \frac{1}{4\pi|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}|} \right] \sigma_k - \sum_{k=1}^N \left[- \int_{S_k} \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot (\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r})}{|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}|^3} \right] \varphi_k + \int_{S_w} \dots = \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^N S_{ik}\sigma_k - \sum_{k=1}^N D_{ik}\varphi_k - \sum_{\ell=1}^{N_w} D_{i\ell}^w \varphi_\ell^w \end{aligned} \quad (270)$$

where S_{ik} and D_{ik} are the aerodynamic influence coefficients (AICs) of the k -th panel on the i -th panel, associated with source and doublet surface distributions with unitary intensity, see §7.1.1. Retrieving φ_i from φ_i^w with Kutta condition, it is possible to obtain the discrete counterpart of eq.(267) as

$$\sum_{k=1}^N (E^{(i)}\delta_{ik} + D_{ik} + D_{ik}^{Kutta}) \varphi_k = \sum_{k=1}^N S_{ik}\sigma_k - \sum_{\ell=1}^{N_w} D_{i\ell}^{w,past} \varphi_\ell^w . \quad (271)$$

$$[\underline{E} + \underline{D} + \underline{D}^{Kutta}] \underline{\varphi} = \underline{S} \underline{\sigma} - \underline{D}^{w,past} \underline{\varphi}^w . \quad (272)$$

7.1.1 Point singularities. Source and doublets

The potential of a point source of intensity Q in the three-dimensional space is

$$\phi_S(r) = -\frac{Q}{4\pi r} , \quad (273)$$

where r is the distance from the point source. The velocity potential of a point doublet of intensity $\mu = \lim_{\substack{d \rightarrow 0 \\ q \rightarrow \infty}} qd$ is

$$\phi_D(r) = -\frac{\mu \cos \theta}{4\pi r^2} = -\frac{\mu z}{4\pi r^3} , \quad (274)$$

if the axis of the doublet points from the sink (intensity $-q$) to the source (intensity $+q$). Here, the origin O of the coordinate system coincides with the position of the point doublet, the z axis has the same direction $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ of the axis of the doublet and θ is the angle between the radius vector from O to a point P in the domain and the axis of the doublet. Since the coordinate z of the point P is $z = \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \mathbf{r}$, the potential of a doublet of intensity μ reads

$$\phi_D(r) = -\mu \frac{\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \mathbf{r}}{4\pi r^3} . \quad (275)$$

7.1.2 Equivalence doublet surface-vortex ring

Following [Katz and Plotkin \(2001\)](#) (p.250, §10.4.3) a constant-strength flat panel with intensity μ is equivalent to a vortex ring on the boundary of the panel with intensity $\Gamma = \mu$.

7.2 Neumann problem

The irrotational flow around a zero-thickness lifting surface S_s is obtained by means of the boundary condition

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \mathbf{U} = \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_b \quad , \quad \mathbf{r} \in S_s . \quad (276)$$

Introducing the decomposition (??) of the velocity field in eq.(276), the boundary condition for \mathbf{u}_φ reads

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_\varphi = \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot (\mathbf{u}_b - \mathbf{U}_\infty - \mathbf{u}_\psi) \quad , \quad \mathbf{r} \in S_s , \quad (277)$$

where $\mathbf{u}_\varphi = \mathbf{u}_{\varphi,s} + \mathbf{u}_{\varphi,w}$ contains both the contributions of the lifting surface $\mathbf{u}_{\varphi,s}$ and the potential part of the wake shed $\mathbf{u}_{\varphi,w}$, while \mathbf{u}_ψ is known if a time-stepping method is used, see Sec.7.1.

TODO. Add a dedicated section for time-stepping algorithm?

Zero-thickness lifting surfaces are modelled with a surface distribution of doublets only. The surface S_s is divided in N panels S_k , s.t. $S_s = \cup_{k=1:N} S_k$ and each panel has constant-strength distribution of doublets, $\varphi|_{S_k} = \varphi_k$. The surface doublet-vortex ring equivalence, see Sec.7.1.2, is exploited and the velocity induced by each panel is computed by means of the Biot-Savart law. The induced velocity from a unit-strength surface doublet S_k on the point \mathbf{r}_i is

$$\mathbf{u}_{ik}^1 = \mathbf{u}_{ik}^{dov,1} = \mathbf{u}_k^1(\mathbf{r}_i) = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \oint_{\partial S_k} \frac{\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}}{|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}|^3} \times \hat{\mathbf{t}} . \quad (278)$$

Writing the velocity field as the sum of the contributions from all the panels, the boundary condition (277) in the centre of the i^{th} panel becomes

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}}_i \cdot \left(\sum_{k=1}^N \mathbf{u}_{ik}^1 \varphi_k + \sum_{\ell=1}^{N_w} \mathbf{u}_{i\ell}^{1,w} \varphi_\ell^w \right) = \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i \cdot (\mathbf{u}_{b,i} - \mathbf{U}_\infty - \mathbf{u}_{\psi,i}) = \sigma_i \quad , \quad i = 1 : N \quad (279)$$

where $\mathbf{u}_{i\ell}^{1,w}$ is the velocity induced on \mathbf{r}_i by the ℓ^{th} panel of the wake, $\mathbf{u}_{b,i}$ is the velocity of the centre \mathbf{r}_i of the i^{th} panel of the body and $\mathbf{u}_{\psi,i} = \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r}_i, t)$. Both the geometry of the wake and the intensity of the doublet distribution on the wake is known from previous steps. Thus, the problem (279) can be recast as the linear system

$$\underline{\underline{U}} \underline{\underline{\varphi}} = \underline{\underline{\sigma}} - \underline{\underline{U}}^w \underline{\underline{\varphi}}^w , \quad (280)$$

with

$$U_{ik} = \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i \cdot \mathbf{u}_{ik}^1 \quad , \quad U_{il}^w = \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i \cdot \mathbf{u}_{il}^{1,w} \quad , \quad \sigma_i = \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i \cdot (\mathbf{u}_{b,i} - \mathbf{U}_\infty - \mathbf{u}_{\psi,i}) \quad . \quad (281)$$

Remark. The symbol $\underline{\sigma}$ is used in analogy with the source intensity appearing in the Dirichlet problem.

7.3 Mixed Dirichlet-Neumann problem

A complex aircraft configuration can be modelled with both thick bodies (e.g. fuselage, high-fidelity models of wings and blades) and zero-thickness lifting surfaces (e.g. lower-fidelity models of wings and blades). If panels and vortex rings are simultaneously present in the model, a mixed Dirichlet-Neumann problem must be solved.

Boundary conditions. Dirichlet boundary conditions resulting in Morino formulation are written for the thick bodies, Neumann boundary conditions for the zero-thickness surfaces.

Singularities. Doublet and source (whose intensity is known from the boundary condition (265)) singularities are distributed on the surface of thick bodies, while only doublets (equivalent to vortex rings) are distributed on lifting surfaces. The actual unknown of the problem is the potential field $\varphi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ on the surface of both thick bodies S_b and zero-thickness surfaces S_s .

The discrete version of the mixed Dirichlet-Neumann problem is derived here. The influence of S_s (doublets only) on S_b must be added to eq.(272), while the influence of S_b (doublets and sources) on S_s must be added to eq.(280). The intensities of the potential on each constant-strength panel are collected in the vector $\underline{\varphi} = (\underline{\varphi}^b, \underline{\varphi}^s)^T$, where $\underline{\varphi}^b$ and $\underline{\varphi}^s$ collect the contributions of the thick body and zero-thickness surface, respectively. The resulting overall linear system is

$$\begin{bmatrix} \underline{\underline{E}} + \underline{\underline{D}}^{bb} + \underline{\underline{D}}^{b,Kutta} & \underline{\underline{D}}^{bs} \\ \underline{\underline{U}}^{sb} & \underline{\underline{U}}^{ss} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \underline{\varphi}^b \\ \underline{\varphi}^s \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \underline{\underline{S}}^{bb} & \underline{\underline{0}} \\ -\underline{\underline{V}}^{sb} & \underline{\underline{I}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \underline{\sigma}^b \\ \underline{\sigma}^s \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -\underline{\underline{D}}^{bw} \\ -\underline{\underline{U}}^{sw} \end{bmatrix} \underline{\varphi}^w \quad , \quad (282)$$

where the matrix $\underline{\underline{V}}^{sb}$ contains the velocity induced by unit-strength source distributions of the panels S_k belonging to the surface S_b on the centre \mathbf{r}_i of the panels of the surface S_s ,

$$V_{ik}^{sb} = \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i \cdot \mathbf{u}_{ik}^{sou,1} = \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i \cdot \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{S_k} \frac{\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}}{|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}|^3} \quad . \quad (283)$$

7.4 Wake: potential part

The contribution of the potential part of the wake in eq.(262)

$$- \oint_{S_w} G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \nabla \varphi(\mathbf{r}, t) + \oint_{S_w} \varphi(\mathbf{r}, t) \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \nabla G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) \quad (284)$$

is manipulated as follows. Both sides S_w^+ and S_w^- of the zero-thickness model of the wake must be considered in S_w , defined as a part of the boundary of the potential domain. The normal unit vectors on the opposite sides of the wake are defined as $\hat{\mathbf{n}}^+$ and $\hat{\mathbf{n}}^-$. These

vectors point in opposite directions, $\hat{\mathbf{n}}^+ = -\hat{\mathbf{n}}^-$. Since there is no net mass flux across the wake, $\hat{\mathbf{n}}^+ \cdot \nabla \varphi^+ = \hat{\mathbf{n}}^+ \cdot \mathbf{u}^+ = -\hat{\mathbf{n}}^- \cdot \mathbf{u}^- = -\hat{\mathbf{n}}^- \cdot \nabla \varphi^-$. The expression in (284) becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
& - \int_{S_w^+} G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) \hat{\mathbf{n}}^+ \cdot \nabla \varphi^+(\mathbf{r}, t) - \int_{S_w^-} G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) \hat{\mathbf{n}}^- \cdot \nabla \varphi^-(\mathbf{r}, t) + \\
& + \int_{S_w^+} \varphi^+(\mathbf{r}, t) \hat{\mathbf{n}}^+ \cdot \nabla G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) + \int_{S_w^-} \varphi^-(\mathbf{r}, t) \hat{\mathbf{n}}^- \cdot \nabla G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) = \\
& = - \int_{S_w^+} G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) \underbrace{(\hat{\mathbf{n}}^+ \cdot \nabla \varphi^+(\mathbf{r}, t) + \hat{\mathbf{n}}^- \cdot \nabla \varphi^-(\mathbf{r}, t))}_{=0} + \\
& + \int_{S_w^+} \varphi^+(\mathbf{r}, t) \hat{\mathbf{n}}^+ \cdot \nabla G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) + \int_{S_w^-} \varphi^-(\mathbf{r}, t) \hat{\mathbf{n}}^- \cdot \nabla G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) = \\
& = \int_{S_w^+} \varphi^w(\mathbf{r}, t) \hat{\mathbf{n}}^+ \cdot \nabla G(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_0) ,
\end{aligned} \tag{285}$$

where $\varphi^w = \varphi^+ - \varphi^-$ indicates the potential jump across the surface of the potential part of the wake. The jump across the wake at the trailing edge can be retrieved from the potential jump at the trailing edge itself, by means of the Kutta condition. The intensity of the wake after its shedding behind a body is described by the vorticity equation, and thus it is known if a time-stepping method is used. Thus, the wake contribution result in two terms

$$(D^{Kutta} * \varphi)(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad , \quad (D^{w.past} * \varphi^w)(\mathbf{r}, t) \tag{286}$$

accounting for the both the Kutta condition and “old” wake contribution in the linear problem (267) and its discrete counterpart (272).

Remark. The symbol D is used as the doublet influence is recognised.

TODO. Reference to a “Wake” chapter for the overall description of the wake.

8 AIC computation

TODO. Update the old partial version of this section.

Some Aerodynamic Influence Coefficients (AIC) are required for the discretisation of both the equation of the potential part of the velocity field and the dynamical equation of the rotational part of the velocity field.

Eq. 282 of the potential part of the velocity contains the AICs for

- the kinetic potential induced by surface doublets and sources, $\underline{\underline{D}}$ and $\underline{\underline{S}}$ respectively;
- the velocity induced by surface doublets and sources, $\underline{\underline{U}}$ and $\underline{\underline{V}}$ respectively.

The discrete version of eq.s 151 contain the AIC

- for the velocity induced by surface, line and point singularities, in the dynamical equation of the particles;
- for the spatial derivatives of the induced velocity by surface, line and point singularities in the dynamical equation of the particle intensity.

Few integrals are required for the computation of the AICs of constant-strength 1D and 2D singularities. Computation of these AIC follows Newman (1986). First, the analytical expressions for point source and doublet singularities are reported for completeness.

8.1 Point singularities

8.1.1 Point sources

Kinetic potential. The potential induced in \mathbf{r} by a unit-intensity point source located in \mathbf{r}_0 is

$$\varphi^s(\mathbf{r}) = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{x}|}, \quad (287)$$

being $\mathbf{x} := \mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0$.

Velocity. The velocity induced in \mathbf{r} by a unit-intensity point source located in \mathbf{r}_0 is

$$\mathbf{u}^s(\mathbf{r}) = \nabla \varphi^s(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{\mathbf{x}}{|\mathbf{x}|^3}. \quad (288)$$

Velocity gradient. The velocity gradient induced in \mathbf{r} by a unit-intensity point source located in \mathbf{r}_0 is

$$\nabla \mathbf{u}^s(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \left\{ \frac{1}{|\mathbf{x}|^3} \mathbf{I} - \frac{3}{|\mathbf{x}|^5} \mathbf{x} \otimes \mathbf{x} \right\}. \quad (289)$$

8.1.2 Point doublets

Kinetic potential. The potential induced in \mathbf{r} by a unit-intensity point doublet located in \mathbf{r}_0 is

$$\varphi^d(\mathbf{r}) = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \mathbf{x}}{|\mathbf{x}|^3}. \quad (290)$$

Velocity. The velocity induced in \mathbf{r} by a unit-intensity point doublet located in \mathbf{r}_0 is

$$\mathbf{u}^d(\mathbf{r}) = \nabla \varphi^d(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \left\{ -\frac{\hat{\mathbf{n}}}{|\mathbf{x}|^3} + 3\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \mathbf{x} \frac{\mathbf{x}}{|\mathbf{x}|^5} \right\}. \quad (291)$$

Velocity gradient. The velocity gradient induced in \mathbf{r} by a unit-intensity point doublet located in \mathbf{r}_0 is

$$\nabla \mathbf{u}^d(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \left\{ \frac{3}{|\mathbf{x}|^5} \left(\hat{\mathbf{n}} \otimes \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{x} \otimes \hat{\mathbf{n}} + \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \mathbf{x} \mathbf{I} \right) - 15\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \mathbf{x} \frac{\mathbf{x} \otimes \mathbf{x}}{|\mathbf{x}|^7} \right\}. \quad (292)$$

8.2 Surface doublets

8.2.1 Surface doublets: kinetic potential, D

The potential induced in \mathbf{r}_i (passive point) by the unit-strength intensity surface doublet S_k (active surface) is

$$D_{ik} = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{S_k} \frac{\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot (\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r})}{|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}|^3}. \quad (293)$$

Following Newman (1986), $\Phi = -4\pi D_{ik}$ is recognised to be the solid angle of the panel S_k , as seen from the passive point \mathbf{r}_i . From the Gauss-Bonnet theorem, the solid angle Φ is equal to

$$\Phi = \sum_{\ell=1}^{N_e} \beta_\ell - (N_e - 2)\pi, \quad (294)$$

i.e. the sum of the angles β_ℓ of the projection of the N_e edges of the element on the unit sphere, centered in \mathbf{r}_i .

For each element Φ can be computed with a loop over the vertices of a element, as follows

- the unit vector aligned with the vector from the passive point P_0 to the vertex of the element is computed: $\mathbf{e}_i = (P_i - P_0)/|P_i - P_0|$
- normal projection of the edges $\mathbf{l}_i = P_{i+1} - P_i$, $\mathbf{l}_{i-1} = P_i - P_{i-1}$ w.r.t. \mathbf{e}_i is computed

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{a}_i = \mathbf{l}_i - \mathbf{l}_i \cdot \hat{\mathbf{e}}_i \hat{\mathbf{e}}_i \\ \mathbf{a}_{i-1} = -(\mathbf{l}_{i-1} - \mathbf{l}_{i-1} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{e}}_i \hat{\mathbf{e}}_i) \end{cases} \quad (295)$$

- the desired angle β_i , is the angle included between \mathbf{a}_i and \mathbf{a}_{i-1}

$$\begin{cases} \sin \beta_i = \frac{|\mathbf{a}_i \times \mathbf{a}_{i-1}| \cdot \hat{\mathbf{e}}_i}{|\mathbf{a}_i| |\mathbf{a}_{i-1}|} \\ \cos \beta_i = \frac{\mathbf{a}_i \cdot \mathbf{a}_{i-1}}{|\mathbf{a}_i| |\mathbf{a}_{i-1}|} \end{cases} \quad (296)$$

and can be computed with `atan2` function, providing only the numerators of the ratios appearing in $\sin \beta_i$ and $\cos \beta_i$.

8.2.2 Surface doublets: velocity, U

The induced velocity of a constant-strength doublet surface distribution is computed exploiting the doublet-vortex ring equivalence and the Biot-Savart law, see Sec. §8.4.1.

8.2.3 Surface doublets: velocity gradient

The velocity gradient induced by a constant-strength doublet surface distribution is obtained exploiting the results for the vortex line, see Sec. §8.4.2.

Figure 4: Definition of the quantities for the computation of the surface singularity AICs.

8.3 Surface sources

8.3.1 Surface sources: kinetic potential, S

The potential induced in \mathbf{r}_i (passive point) by the unit-strength intensity surface source S_k (active surface) is

$$S_{ik} = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{S_k} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}|} . \quad (297)$$

The computation of the velocity potential of a constant-strength source surface distribution exploits the expression of the Φ term appeared in the computation of the doublet potential, see Sec.§8.2.1. Following Newman (1986), the integral $\Psi = -4\pi S$ is defined as the potential of a surface doublet of intensity -4π . It is possible to show

$$\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \zeta} = -\Phi \quad \text{and thus} \quad \Psi = - \int_{\zeta}^{\infty} \zeta' d\Phi - \zeta \Phi . \quad (298)$$

Proof. If $\Psi(\mathbf{r}_0)$ represents the potential induced in \mathbf{r}_0 by the surface source S ,

$$\Psi(\mathbf{r}_0) = \Psi(\xi_0, \eta_0, \zeta_0) = \int_S \frac{1}{|\mathbf{r}_0 - \mathbf{r}|} , \quad (299)$$

its derivative w.r.t. the ζ coordinate of the passive point reads

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \zeta}(\xi_0, \eta_0, \zeta_0) &= - \int_S \frac{\zeta_0}{((\xi_0 - \xi)^2 + (\eta_0 - \eta)^2 + \zeta_0^2)^{3/2}} = \\ &= - \int_S \hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{r}_0 - \mathbf{r}}{|\mathbf{r}_0 - \mathbf{r}|^3} , \end{aligned} \quad (300)$$

being ζ the coordinate along the direction normal to the flat element, living in the plane $\zeta = 0$.

Exploiting the integration by part in the integration of the first equation of eqs.(298),

$$\underbrace{\Psi(\xi, \eta, \zeta_{\infty})}_{=0} - \Psi(\xi, \eta, \zeta) = \int_{\zeta}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \zeta} = - \int_{\zeta}^{\infty} \Phi d\zeta = (I \times P) = - [\zeta \Phi] \Big|_{\zeta}^{\infty} + \int_{\zeta}^{\infty} \zeta d\Phi . \quad (301)$$

Exploiting $\zeta \Phi \rightarrow 0$ as $\zeta \rightarrow \infty$, the desired second equation in (298) is obtained. \square

Following Newman (1986), the term Ψ for a flat N-edge panel becomes

$$\Psi(\xi, \eta, \zeta) = -\zeta \Phi(\xi, \eta, \zeta) + \sum_{k=1}^N v_k Q_k , \quad (302)$$

where v_k is the distance of the projection Q_0 of P_0 on the panel from the edge $P_k P_{k+1}$ and

$$Q_k = \ln \frac{R_k + R_{k+1} + s_k}{R_k + R_{k+1} - s_k} . \quad (303)$$

8.3.2 Surface sources: velocity, V

The velocity induced in \mathbf{r}_i (passive point) by the unit-strength intensity surface source S_k (active surface) is

$$\mathbf{u}^d(\mathbf{r}_i) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{S_k} \frac{\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}}{|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}|^3} . \quad (304)$$

This integral is computed exploiting the local orthogonal reference frame of the element $(\hat{\xi}, \hat{\eta}, \hat{\zeta})$

$$4\pi\mathbf{u}^d(\mathbf{r}_i) = \int_{S_k} \frac{\xi}{\rho^3} \hat{\xi} + \int_{S_k} \frac{\eta}{\rho^3} \hat{\eta} + \int_{S_k} \frac{\zeta}{\rho^3} \hat{\zeta} , \quad (305)$$

where $\rho^2 = |\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}|^2 = \xi^2 + \eta^2 + \zeta^2$ is the distance between the active point on the panel surface \mathbf{r} and the passive point \mathbf{r}_i . Given the local orthogonal reference system, [see Sec.§...](#), the relative coordinates read

$$\xi = (\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}) \cdot \hat{\xi} \quad , \quad \eta = (\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}) \cdot \hat{\eta} \quad , \quad \zeta = (\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}) \cdot \hat{\zeta} . \quad (306)$$

Since the unit vector $\hat{\zeta}$ coincides with the unit normal vector $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$, the coordinate ζ in the third integral is constant and this integral is equal to Φ , computed in [Sec.§8.2.1](#). Following [Newman \(1986\)](#), the first two integrals are computed exploiting Green's lemma: surface integrals are transformed in a contour integrals

$$\begin{aligned} I_\xi &= \int_S \frac{\xi}{\rho^3} = - \int_S \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} \frac{1}{\rho} = \oint_{\partial S} \frac{1}{\rho} d\eta = \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{\ell_k} \frac{1}{\rho} d\eta \\ I_\eta &= \int_S \frac{\eta}{\rho^3} = - \int_S \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta} \frac{1}{\rho} = - \oint_{\partial S} \frac{1}{\rho} d\xi = - \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{\ell_k} \frac{1}{\rho} d\xi \end{aligned} \quad (307)$$

that are computed as sums of the contributions from all the sides of the element. For the k -th side, the elementary elements

$$d\xi = ds \cos \theta_k \quad , \quad d\eta = ds \sin \theta_k , \quad (308)$$

the computation integrals I_ξ, I_η only involves the computation of line integrals of the form

$$Q_k = \int_{\ell_k} \frac{1}{\rho} ds . \quad (309)$$

so that

$$I_\xi = \sum_{k=1}^N Q_k \sin \theta_k \quad , \quad I_\eta = - \sum_{k=1}^N Q_k \cos \theta_k . \quad (310)$$

Keep following [Newman \(1986\)](#), with reference to [Fig.4](#), the integral Q_k on the k -th side reads

$$Q_k = \ln \frac{R_k + R_{k+1} + s_k}{R_k + R_{k+1} - s_k} , \quad (311)$$

Figure 5: Local reference system.

so that the expression (305) of the velocity induced by a constant-strength flat source panel S reads

$$4\pi\mathbf{u}^d = \sum_{k=1}^N Q_k(\xi,\eta,\zeta) \sin\theta_k \hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}} - \sum_{k=1}^N Q_k(\xi,\eta,\zeta) \cos\theta_k \hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}} + \Phi(\xi,\eta,\zeta) \hat{\boldsymbol{\zeta}}, \quad (312)$$

where all the dependences on the space coordinates have been explicitly written.

8.3.3 Surface sources: velocity gradient

In the previous section, the velocity induced by a source surface has been written with the coordinates (ξ, η, ζ) of the local reference system. First the components in the local reference frame of the velocity gradient will be computed; then the transformation rule for the components of tensors is used to obtain the components in the base reference frame, to be used in the dynamical equation of the vorticity.

First the transformation rule for tensor in orthogonal coordinate systems is derived. Then the computation of the spatial derivatives of the velocity field w.r.t. the local coordinates follows. Given the unit vectors $\hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_i$ of the local reference system and the unit vectors $\hat{\boldsymbol{x}}_k$ of the base reference system, the transformation rule between these vectors reads

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_i = \hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_i \cdot \hat{\boldsymbol{x}}_k \hat{\boldsymbol{x}}_k = T_{ik} \hat{\boldsymbol{x}}_k, \quad (313)$$

having introduced the definition $T_{ik} = \hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_i \cdot \hat{\boldsymbol{x}}_k$. If the geometry and the orientation of the element is known, **the coefficients T_{ik} are known** as well. A vector field \mathbf{u} can be expressed in these two coordinate system as

$$\mathbf{u} = u^k \hat{\boldsymbol{x}}_k = v^k \hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_k, \quad (314)$$

where u^k are the components of the vector in the base reference system $\{\hat{\boldsymbol{x}}_i\}$ and v^k the coordinates in the local reference system $\{\hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_i\}$. The definition of the gradient of a vector field reads

$$\boldsymbol{\nabla}\mathbf{u} = \frac{\partial v^k}{\partial \xi_i} \hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_i \otimes \hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_k = \frac{\partial u^k}{\partial x_i} \hat{\boldsymbol{x}}_i \otimes \hat{\boldsymbol{x}}_k. \quad (315)$$

Introducing the transformation rule for the vectors of the base,

$$\boldsymbol{\nabla}\mathbf{u} = \frac{\partial v^k}{\partial \xi_i} T_{il} T_{km} \hat{\boldsymbol{x}}_l \otimes \hat{\boldsymbol{x}}_m \quad \rightarrow \quad \frac{\partial u^m}{\partial x_\ell} = \frac{\partial v^k}{\partial \xi_i} T_{il} T_{km} \quad , \quad [\boldsymbol{\nabla}\mathbf{u}]_x = \underline{\underline{T}}^T [\boldsymbol{\nabla}\mathbf{u}]_\xi \underline{\underline{T}}, \quad (316)$$

where the components of the gradient of vector field are organised in the array as follows

$$[\boldsymbol{\nabla}\mathbf{u}]_x = \begin{bmatrix} \partial_x u_x & \partial_x u_y & \partial_x u_z \\ \partial_y u_x & \partial_y u_y & \partial_y u_z \\ \partial_z u_x & \partial_z u_y & \partial_z u_z \end{bmatrix}. \quad (317)$$

Explicitly writing all the functions of the space coordinates in expression (312)

$$4\pi\mathbf{u}^d = \sum_{k=1}^N Q_k(\xi,\eta,\zeta) \sin\theta_k \hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}} - \sum_{k=1}^N Q_k(\xi,\eta,\zeta) \cos\theta_k \hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}} + \Phi(\xi,\eta,\zeta) \hat{\boldsymbol{\zeta}}, \quad (318)$$

it is possible to figure out the terms to be differentiated in order to compute the gradient of the velocity field: it is clear that only the derivatives of the terms $Q_k(\xi, \eta, \zeta)$ and $\Phi(\xi, \eta, \zeta)$ are required. Since the length s_k of the k -th side is independent from the spatial coordinates, the derivatives of $Q_k(\xi, \eta, \zeta)$ reads

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial Q_k}{\partial \xi_i} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_i} \frac{R_k + R_{k+1} + s_k}{R_k + R_{k+1} - s_k} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_i} \frac{N_k}{D_k} = \\ &= \frac{R_k + R_{k+1} - s_k}{R_k + R_{k+1} + s_k} \cdot \frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_i} (R_k + R_{k+1}) (R_k + R_{k+1} - s_k) - \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_i} (R_k + R_{k+1}) (R_k + R_{k+1} + s_k)}{(R_k + R_{k+1} - s_k)^2} = \\ &= -\frac{2 s_k}{(R_k + R_{k+1} + s_k)(R_k + R_{k+1} - s_k)} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_i} (R_k + R_{k+1}) = -\frac{2 s_k}{N_k D_k} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_i} (R_k + R_{k+1}), \end{aligned} \quad (319)$$

being $R_k = |\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{P}_k| = \sqrt{(\xi - \xi^{(k)})^2 + (\eta - \eta^{(k)})^2 + \zeta^2}$ the distance between the passive point \mathbf{r} and the node \mathbf{P}_k of the surface element S . Differentiating the definition of R_k , the last missing term needed for $\partial Q_k / \partial \xi_i$ is computed as

$$\frac{\partial R_k}{\partial \xi_i} = \frac{\xi_i - \xi_i^{(k)}}{R_k}. \quad (320)$$

The spatial derivatives of Φ are computed starting from the expression of Φ , **as reported in the manual of VSAERO.** ← **TODO:** add citation.

TODO: add the computation of $\partial \Phi / \partial \xi_i$.

8.4 Line vortices

8.4.1 Line vortices: velocity

The velocity induced in \mathbf{r}_i by the vortex-ring ℓ , whose intensity is Γ , is computed by means of Biot-Savart law,

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r}_i) = -\frac{\Gamma}{4\pi} \oint_{\ell} \frac{\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}}{|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}|^3} \times \hat{\mathbf{t}}. \quad (321)$$

For vortex ring, whose sides are straight lines, a simple analytical expression of the previous integral can be found. After dividing the vortex ring ℓ in segments ℓ_k , the induced velocity reads

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r}_i) = -\frac{\Gamma}{4\pi} \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{\ell_k} \frac{\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}}{|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}|^3} \times \hat{\mathbf{t}}_k = \frac{\Gamma}{4\pi} \mathbf{I}_k, \quad (322)$$

having introduced the definition of \mathbf{I}_k as the velocity induced by the k -th side with intensity -4π . It is possible to prove (**TODO: cite or prove**) that \mathbf{I}_k can be computed as

$$\mathbf{I}_k = \frac{\mathbf{R}_k \times \mathbf{R}_{k+1} (R_k + R_{k+1})}{R_k R_{k+1} (R_k R_{k+1} + \mathbf{R}_k \cdot \mathbf{R}_{k+1})}, \quad (323)$$

being $\mathbf{R}_k = \mathbf{r} - \mathbf{P}_k$ the vector “connecting” the k -th vertex of the element with the passive point \mathbf{r}_i .

8.4.2 Line vortices: velocity gradient

The velocity gradient is directly computed in the base coordinate system. Direct differentiation of (323) reads

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{I}}{\partial x_i} = & \frac{1}{AB(AB + \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b})} \left\{ \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}}{\partial x_i} \times \mathbf{b}(A + B) + \mathbf{a} \times \frac{\partial \mathbf{b}}{\partial x_i} (A + B) + \mathbf{a} \times \mathbf{b} \left(\frac{\partial A}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial B}{\partial x_i} \right) \right\} + \\ & - \frac{\mathbf{a} \times \mathbf{b}(A + B)}{B[AB + \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b}]^2} \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial A}{\partial x_i} B + A \frac{\partial B}{\partial x_i} \right) (AB + \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b}) + AB \left(\frac{\partial A}{\partial x_i} B + A \frac{\partial B}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{a}}{\partial x_i} \cdot \mathbf{b} + \mathbf{a} \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{b}}{\partial x_i} \right) \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (324)$$

having defined $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{R}_k$, $\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{R}_{k+1}$, $A = |\mathbf{a}|$, $B = |\mathbf{b}|$. The derivatives in eq.(323) are easily obtained as

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{a}}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{b}}{\partial x_i} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i \quad , \quad \frac{\partial A}{\partial x_i} = \frac{x_i}{A} \quad , \quad \frac{\partial B}{\partial x_i} = \frac{x_i}{B} \quad . \quad (325)$$

8.5 Particles

8.5.1 Particles: velocity

8.5.2 Particles: velocity gradient

9 Geometry and Motion – Reference Frames

DUST allows to define different reference frames in order to simplify the relative placement of the geometry and the description of the movement of the geometry itself.

The reference frames must be defined in a hierarchical way, i.e. a reference frame K must be defined with respect to a "parent" reference frame J . In this way it is possible to define a tree of reference frames, which must however be attached at its root to the base reference frame, which is the simple orthogonal, right-hand-ordered reference frame in which all the actual computations are performed after transforming the coordinates from the defined reference frames to the base one.

A reference frame K is recursively defined through the relative position $\mathbf{o}_{k/J}$ of its reference point O_K and the orientation with respect to its parent reference frame J , identified by the rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}^{J \leftarrow K}$,

$$\mathbf{R}^{J \leftarrow K} = \mathbf{I} + \sin \vartheta_K \hat{\mathbf{a}}_{K \times}^J + (1 - \cos \vartheta_K) \hat{\mathbf{a}}_{K \times}^J \hat{\mathbf{a}}_{K \times}^J \quad , \quad (326)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{a}}_{K \times}^J$ is the unit normal vector aligned with the rotation axis, expressed in the reference frame J , and ϑ_K is the rotation angle around this axis. The relative angular velocity defined in the parent reference frame J reads $\boldsymbol{\Omega}_K^J = \dot{\vartheta}_K \hat{\mathbf{a}}_{K \times}^J$.

The relative position $\mathbf{r}_{b/J}^J$ of a point P in the a reference frame J is expressed as the sum of the relative position $\mathbf{o}_{k/J}^J$ of the reference point O_K of the child reference frame K and its relative position $\mathbf{r}_{b/K}^J$ in the reference frame K ,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{r}_{b/J}^J &= \mathbf{o}_{k/J}^J + \mathbf{r}_{b/K}^J \\ &= \mathbf{o}_{k/J}^J + \mathbf{R}^{J \leftarrow K} \mathbf{r}_{b/K}^K \quad , \end{aligned} \quad (327)$$

and its time derivative becomes

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\mathbf{r}}_{b/J}^J &= \dot{\mathbf{o}}_{k/J}^J + \dot{\mathbf{r}}_{b/K}^J \\ &= \dot{\mathbf{o}}_{k/J}^J + \dot{\mathbf{R}}^{J\leftarrow K} \mathbf{r}_{b/K}^K + \mathbf{R}^{J\leftarrow K} \dot{\mathbf{r}}_{b/K}^K .\end{aligned}\quad (328)$$

The aerodynamic solver requires the position \mathbf{r}_b and the velocity $\dot{\mathbf{r}}_b$ of the surface of the model, defined in the global reference system. Combining the child-parent K -to- J relative kinematics relations (327-328) with the relative kinematics relations linking the reference frame J to the global coordinate system, for the position

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{r}_b &= \mathbf{o}_j + \mathbf{R}^{0\leftarrow J} \mathbf{r}_{b/J}^J \\ &= \mathbf{o}_j + \mathbf{R}^{0\leftarrow J} (\mathbf{o}_{k/J}^J + \mathbf{R}^{J\leftarrow K} \mathbf{r}_{b/K}^K) \\ &= \mathbf{o}_k + \mathbf{R}^{0\leftarrow K} \mathbf{r}_{b/K}^K ,\end{aligned}\quad (329)$$

and for the velocity,

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{u}_b &= \dot{\mathbf{r}}_b \\ &= \dot{\mathbf{o}}_j + \dot{\mathbf{R}}^{0\leftarrow J} \mathbf{r}_{b/J}^J + \mathbf{R}^{0\leftarrow J} \dot{\mathbf{r}}_{b/J}^J \\ &= \dot{\mathbf{o}}_j + \dot{\mathbf{R}}^{0\leftarrow J} (\mathbf{o}_{k/J}^J + \mathbf{R}^{J\leftarrow K} \mathbf{r}_{b/K}^K) \\ &\quad + \mathbf{R}^{0\leftarrow J} (\dot{\mathbf{o}}_{k/J}^J + \dot{\mathbf{R}}^{J\leftarrow K} \mathbf{r}_{b/K}^K + \mathbf{R}^{J\leftarrow K} \dot{\mathbf{r}}_{b/K}^K) \\ &= \dot{\mathbf{o}}_k + \dot{\mathbf{R}}^{0\leftarrow K} \mathbf{r}_{b/K}^K + \mathbf{R}^{0\leftarrow K} \dot{\mathbf{r}}_{b/K}^K ,\end{aligned}\quad (330)$$

it is possible to obtain the recurrence relation for describing the global motion of a reference frame K , given its motion relative to its parent J and the global motion of J . The recurrence relations for the position and the velocity of the reference point O_K read,

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{o}_k &= \mathbf{o}_j + \mathbf{R}^{0\leftarrow J} \mathbf{o}_{k/J}^J \\ \dot{\mathbf{o}}_k &= \dot{\mathbf{o}}_j + \dot{\mathbf{R}}^{0\leftarrow J} \mathbf{o}_{k/J}^J + \mathbf{R}^{0\leftarrow J} \dot{\mathbf{o}}_{k/J}^J ,\end{aligned}\quad (331)$$

and the recurrence relations for the rotation matrix and its derivative read,

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{R}^{0\leftarrow K} &= \mathbf{R}^{0\leftarrow J} \mathbf{R}^{J\leftarrow K} \\ \dot{\mathbf{R}}^{0\leftarrow K} &= \dot{\mathbf{R}}^{0\leftarrow J} \mathbf{R}^{J\leftarrow K} + \mathbf{R}^{0\leftarrow J} \dot{\mathbf{R}}^{J\leftarrow K} .\end{aligned}\quad (332)$$

References

- Richard E Brown and Andrew J Line. Efficient high-resolution wake modeling using the vorticity transport equation. *AIAA Journal*, 43(7):1434–1443, 2005.
- S Gallay and E Laurendeau. Nonlinear generalized lifting-line coupling algorithms for pre/poststall flows. *AIAA Journal*, 53(7):1784–1792, 2015.
- J. Katz and A. Plotkin. *Low-Speed Aerodynamics*. Cambridge University Press, 2001.
- Keith Lindsay and Robert Krasny. A particle method and adaptive treecode for vortex sheet motion in three-dimensional flow. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 172(2): 879–907, 2001.
- Luigi Morino and Ching-Chiang Kuot. Subsonic potential aerodynamics for complex configurations: a general theory. *AIAA Journal*, 12(2):191–197, 1974.
- JN Newman. Distributions of sources and normal dipoles over a quadrilateral panel. *Journal of Engineering Mathematics*, 20(2):113–126, 1986.
- Stanley T Piszkin and ES Levinsky. Nonlinear lifting line theory for predicting stalling instabilities on wings of moderate aspect ratio. Technical report, GENERAL DYNAMICS SAN DIEGO CA CONVAIR DIV, 1976.
- Gregoire Stephane Winckelmans. *Topics in vortex methods for the computation of three- and two-dimensional incompressible unsteady flows*. PhD thesis, California Institute of Technology, 1989.